

Late Breaking Papers from the IEEE 2023 Congress on Evolutionary Computation

Chicago, IL, July 2023

CEC 2023

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This volume contains the papers submitted to IEEE CEC2023 as Late Breaking, describing recent research in the areas or topics of the IEEE CEC2023. These papers represent last moment research developed by their authors. The papers were presented at the conference after being checked for novelty, fitness and technical appropriateness.

Volume compiled by Rui Jorge Almeida
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Welcome to the IEEE CEC 2023!!!

IEEE CEC 2023 is a world-class conference that brings together researchers and practitioners in the field of evolutionary computation and computational intelligence from around the globe. The conference program includes plenary talks, lectures, regular and special sessions, tutorials, competitions, and workshops.

This was a challenging year for CEC 2023! Being the first all in-person CEC post COVID, the conference faced new and unexpected hurdles, such as high airplane ticket prices from many countries to the USA, high value of the dollar for travelers, tedious US visa application processes, and so on. But despite all that, the CEC 2023 brings new and promising changes. For one, the CEC 2023 was the first CIS conference to hold a double-blind, two-cycle review process, which in our view was a huge success. But you will be the judge of that because besides being a fairer process, the two-cycle review allowed the CEC to control the acceptance rate, while raising the quality of the papers – the revision and resubmission of papers after the reviewers’ comments, hugely improved the quality of those original papers. Also, the high number of excellent reviewers and meta reviewers, who worked together like reviewers and associate editors in many of our Transactions, provided the largest average number of reviews ever seen in a CIS conference: an average of 3.9 reviewers per paper, and an average of 2.6 meta-reviewers per paper, which represents a total average of 6.5 people reviewing and recommending improvements for each and every paper.

In the end, 230 regular papers were submitted, with 36 papers accepted in the first review cycle, 55 papers immediately rejected, and 139 papers marked Revise/Resubmit also in the first review cycle. After that, 94 additional papers were accepted in the second cycle, and 45 additional papers were rejected in the same second cycle. In summary, a total of 130 papers were accepted and 100 were reject (or 56.5% acceptance rate). Besides that, 32 papers were submitted as Late Breaking, and 6 Journal to Conference (J2C) were selected for presentations, together with 18 Tutorials, 1 Workshop, 3 Plenary talks (including the 2023 Pioneer Awardee), and various Student Competitions.

Finally, the conference will provide an exciting and interesting evening banquet, onboard the Sprit of Chicago, on the 4th of July, with a spectacular view of the Chicago Skyline during the Fireworks Celebration of Independence Day.

So, welcome again and enjoy the CEC 2023!!

Gui DeSouza and Gary Yen
General Co-Chairs

Rui Jorge Almeida and Joao Carvalho
Publication Co-Chairs

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Exploring Radiologists' Workload-Related Gaze Patterns with AI: A Study of Workload and X-ray Abnormalities

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Abstract— In recent years, the workload of some radiologists has increased dramatically, which potentially led to a decrease in the quality of treatment. This study aims to analyze how radiologists cover chest X-rays with their gaze when faced with different chest anomalies and increased workload. A database of 400 chest X-rays with reference diagnoses was collected for the study. As radiologists read an increased number of chest X-Ray images, their focus on the pulmonary fields becomes more limited. A randomized experiment was suggested to record and quantify the progressive changes in X-ray interpretations for different lung anomalies caused by intense workload.

Keywords— lung fields, U-Net, eye-tracking, human-AI interaction, radiologist performance

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade, the burden on radiologists has increased dramatically. Due to artificial intelligence, it has become possible to solve some problems in the field of radiology. During the pandemic, such systems have found practical applications in medicine. One of the strategic pathways of artificial intelligence's application in medicine is radiologist-AI interaction, where AI provides some other aid through constant communication with radiology technologists.

One of the new areas of research using artificial intelligence is the analysis of radiological eye movements. The study of Krupinski et al [1] was based on the Swedish Occupational Fatigue Inventory (SOFI) and oculomotor strain subscale from the Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (SSQ) questionnaires for radiologists' fatigue estimation. 40 radiologists participated in the experiment, and each of them had to view 60 X-rays. Krupinski concluded that there was an increase in symptoms of fatigue, oculomotor strain, and deterioration in diagnostic quality.

In this study, we investigate how lung field coverage with radiologists' gaze varies over time against different abnormality types. For this reason, we developed a workstation fitted with a framework for X-ray reading that simulates a workstation of radiologists. Two practicing radiologists with different levels of experience have been recruited to analyze lung X-rays while their eye movement and voice, and workstation controller commands were recorded. A dedicated randomization methodology was formulated to reduce the impact of reading patterns among individual radiologists and to capture the collective reading patterns regarding lung field coverage for various categories of abnormalities and different time points of the experiment.

II. METHODOLOGY

400 chest X-rays with unambiguous labels were selected from the public database chest X-rays. Among them, there are 168 X-rays with no lung abnormalities, i.e., normal subjects, 60 X-rays with unambiguous nodule/masses labels, 72 X-rays with chest infiltrations, 48 X-rays with pneumothorax, 12 X-rays with atelectasis, and 40 X-rays with cardiomegaly. From the selected data, it can be concluded that the average age of the patients was 49 years (144 X-rays), with 61% males and 39% females (260 X-rays). Resolutions of various scanners that were applied for getting X-rays to vary from 1624×1775 to 3320×3408 pixels.

The special framework that was developed for this experiment simulates a radiological workstation for the analysis of X-rays. The aim of the framework as a part of our research is compiling eye movement data and capturing the time points when the radiologist starts and finishes reading the image.

After some sessions of calibration, we decided to add the voice recording function. It was necessary because the gaze of the radiologist moves too often to the keyboard for typing the diagnosis and switching to a new image. The framework was

equipped with a 10-bit monitor with a resolution of 3840×2160 px and a pixel density of $\rho = 7.31$ px/mm to display X-ray images. Tobii Eye Tracker 4C was used for eye-movement tracking, while Logitech 960 headsets were used for voice recording.

A primary concept of this experiment is evaluating how lung coverage with gaze changes over time and if it remains non-alterable for all radiologists.

To monitor the fatigue levels of radiologists, we utilized an SSQ test. The SSQ test is divided into three subscales: oculomotor strain, disorientation, and nausea, encompassing a total of 16 questions. Each question is scored on a four-point scale, where a score of four indicates the maximum fatigue level, and one represents the minimum. We used oculomotor strain subscale, which includes the following questions which attempts to assess fatigue levels: general discomfort, headache, eye strain, difficulty focusing and concentrating and blurred vision.

The algorithm for lung segmentation relies upon the convolutional neural network architecture of U-Net [2]. The architecture of the system is founded upon an encoder-decoder concept. It captures not only the area inside the lungs but also their contours. The intuition of explicitly requesting lung contours from the U-Net is to apply supplementary penalties for inaccuracies located on the border of the target lungs.

In this study, the primary encoder utilized in U-Net was substituted with the pre-trained ResNeXt50 [3] via the ImageNet [4] public database. The process of extracting contours from the lungs was achieved via a morphological erode operation. The loss function was based on a combination of Dice Loss and binary cross-entropy:

$$L(X, Y) = - \sum_{i=0}^N \sum_{p \in P_i} y_p \log x_p - \log \sum_{i=0}^N \frac{2 \sum_{p \in P_i} x_p y_p}{\sum_{p \in P_i} x_p^2 + \sum_{p \in P_i} y_p^2}$$

where x, y predicted and ground-truth segmentation mask, P_i is the set of pixels in the mask of sample number i .

The segmented lungs combined with gaze data allow us to quantitatively estimate the coverage of the lung fields during X-ray reading. According to studies by Wolfe and Stransburger [5,6], we set up $\theta=2$ degrees. The area A_t of perceived visual information at the gaze point $g(t)$ at time t can be calculated as:

$$A_t = \{(x, y): \sqrt{(x - x_t)^2 + (y - y_t)^2} \leq z_t \rho \tan\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)\},$$

where $x_t, y_t \in g(t)$ are gaze coordinates on the monitor, $z_t \in g(t)$ is the distance in mm between a participant and gaze coordinates, θ is the visual angle, ρ is the pixel density of the monitor, and x, y are the absolute image coordinates in pixels.

The lung coverage area $C_\tau^{imglung}$ calculated for a time period of τ seconds from the beginning of the X-ray reading is:

$$C_\tau^{lung} = \frac{|\bigcup_{t=0}^{\tau} (A_t \cap L)|}{|L|},$$

where $|A|$ measures cardinality of the set A , and L is the set pixels that belong to lung fields. The coverage information allows us to quantitatively assess the portion of the lungs observed by the reader at each time moment and the end of the reading process (Fig. 1).

This study assumes that lung coverage is noticeably reduced when the number of images that radiologists read increases. Also, the changes are consistent with viewed abnormality types. In our study, radiologists viewed X-rays in an individually randomized order. This approach provides an independent result because different images were taken by different radiologists at the beginning and the end of the experiment.

Figure 1. Example of lung segmentation results and radiologists' gaze heatmaps superimposed over randomly selected X-ray. The segmentations were automatically generated using a modified U-Net algorithm. The heatmaps were recorded during X-ray reading.

Two practicing radiologists were recruited to participate in the experiment. The radiologists were asked to mention all abnormalities they observe and comment on the confidence they have in their decision. The decision was considered correct if the radiologist mentions, potentially among other abnormalities, the abnormality that was unanimously diagnosed by the reference radiological team [7].

III. RESULTS

At the beginning of the experiment, both Radiologists have reported no fatigue, i.e., they graded all seven oculomotor SSQ measurements with the lowest allowed grade 1 or 7 overall. After analyzing 200 X-rays, the average self-reported fatigue of radiologists grew from 7 to 11.5 (10 for radiologist C and 13 for radiologist D). After lunch, the average was 7.5 (7 for radiologist C and 8 for radiologist D). At the end of the experiment, the average self-reported fatigue reached 11.5 (10 for radiologist C and 13 for radiologist D). Figure 2 shows the results of the SSQ test.

Figure 2. The results of the Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (SSQ) for both radiologists. Testing was carried out before the start of the experiment, after every 200 analyzed X-Rays, and after the lunch break.

The average (\pm standard deviation) lung coverage for Radiologists A is 58 ± 17 %, for Radiologist B is 55 ± 17 %. Figure 3 depicts the regression models with the confidence intervals shaded. Linear regression models were fitted to each X-ray from the database (Fig 3a) and then grouped for each lung abnormality type (Fig 3b).

(a) Linear regression models of lung coverage by number of X-Rays viewed for each radiologists. (b) Linear regression models of lung coverage by number of X-Rays viewed for both radiologists. Models are grouped by pathology.

Figure 3. These illustrations demonstrate how lung coverage with radiologists' gaze changes with the number of images analyzed by the radiologists. These linear regression models are then aggregated for individual abnormalities. The linear regression models are overlapped with the corresponding data points, the points are averaged over 20 data samples for better visibility.

IV. DISCUSSION

This study provides a randomized experiment, aimed at monitoring the prospective modifications in radiologists' chest X-ray reading patterns through the application of eye-tracking technology and artificial intelligence AI-based lung segmentation.

We designed a data randomization protocol for the chest X-ray reading by two radiologists. This approach facilitated the evaluation of statistical variations in chest coverage on an individual radiologist basis, as well as tracking changes in

individual lung abnormalities. Through the assessment of the modifications in lung coverage for each radiologist, the intuitive assumption that the lung coverage for all radiologists decreases with a concomitant escalation in the quantity of X-ray analyses has been confirmed.

Lung coverage is significantly reduced after reading 400 X-rays. This finding corroborates the hypothesis that the decrease in coverage is uniform across all radiologists, whereas the variations observed in Figure 3 are due to different orders of X-rays assigned to each radiologist. The radiologists appear to cover a larger part of the lungs with their gaze when the patient has atelectasis. One of the possible explanations is that nonobstructive atelectasis is caused by lung diseases such as pleural effusion, pneumonia, pneumothorax, fibrosis, etc. [8].

The randomized experiment has a significant benefit in identifying the consistent image reading patterns invariant to the viewing order of the X-rays for different radiologists. A noticeable trend observed among radiologists is a gradual reduction in lung coverage upon increasing the number of viewed images, as evidenced by the visual data (Fig. 3a).

The current study has limitations that merit consideration. The current study suggests that the radiologist's workload could increase more than during a typical work schedule. This is because over half of the X-rays had abnormalities, and in everyday practice, the radiologist pauses briefly after conducting a visual evaluation to produce a report. Another limitation is related to the gaze coverage approach. A fixed view angle value was used; however, this may differ for each radiologist. In addition, the inclusion of peripheral vision was not taken into account during the computation of eye coverage. The present methodological approach can be effectively applied to measuring the visual skills of radiology residents. An additional utility may be identified for assessing variations in the perspective of a radiologist in active clinical practice.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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Multilevel Image Segmentation of Breast Cancer using Improved Differential Evolution

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Abstract—Breast cancer is the top cause of mortality for women worldwide. Early breast cancer identification using diagnostic imaging, such as mammography, is essential for effective therapy. However, accurate segmentation of breast tumors from medical images is a challenging task due to variations in the shape, size, and intensity of tumors. In this paper, we propose a novel multilevel breast cancer image segmentation approach using an improved differential evolution algorithm. We evaluate the proposed method on benchmark functions. We incorporate the Otsu method to ensure the smoothness and accuracy of the segmentation. The results on a sample of mammogram images show that our proposed method has the potential to assist radiologists in detecting breast cancer at an early stage, which can significantly improve patient outcomes.

Index Terms—multilevel image segmentation, differential evolution, breast cancer segmentation

I. INTRODUCTION

Many challenging problems have been solved using the biological system of nature for millions of years. Nature-inspired meta-heuristics include physics-inspired algorithms, evolutionary algorithms, and swarm intelligence. In solving optimization problems, the evolutionary algorithm is most effective in finding a near-optimal solution among the existing algorithms [1]. These systems have shown good efficiency with the maximization of evolutionary processes.

Differential Evolution (DE) is one such evolutionary algorithm with strong global optimality. DE employs a straightforward mutation operator that seeks to determine the direction of a search based on the variations between pairs of solutions, often known as vectors. This search direction depends on the variability of solutions in the existing population [2]. The computational steps of DE are similar to those of a standard evolutionary algorithm. Classical DE suffers from premature convergence in some suboptimal regions of search space. Its effectiveness mainly depends on the generated trial vectors and constraints used. Several attempts have been done to enhance the quality of DE [3]. Still, there is a need to improve the

efficiency, scalability, and robustness of these evolutionary algorithms for specific applications.

Breast cancer is a major health concern worldwide, and early detection through accurate image segmentation is crucial for effective diagnosis and treatment. Image segmentation approaches need optimal threshold values to segregate the image into multiple segments. For such problem-specific tasks, an evolutionary algorithm is a better approach to follow, as it performs optimal search. In recent years, several image segmentation techniques have been proposed for breast cancer detection [4], and among them, the differential evolution algorithm has gained considerable attention due to its efficiency and effectiveness [5].

Therefore, we have proposed a Improved DE algorithm that guides the search process by improving diversification and avoiding premature convergence. We have tested the same algorithm for breast cancer image segmentation using Otsu's method. The results on a sample image showed that the proposed method achieved good results in segmenting the breast tumor region and outperformed other segmentation methods in terms of computational efficiency.

The organization of the paper is as follows: Sections 2 and 3 briefly describe the workings of the DE algorithm and the proposed methodology. Sections 4 and 5 show the experimental outcomes and the application of the algorithm to image segmentation. The results are discussed in Section 6, with a conclusion in Section 7.

II. DIFFERENTIAL EVOLUTION

DE starts with a population of N candidate solutions, each represented as a D -dimensional vector. The goal is to find the solution that minimizes or maximizes an objective function, $f(x)$, defined in the search space [6].

The algorithm consists of three operators: mutation, crossover, and selection. These operators are iteratively applied to the population to generate new candidate solutions until a stopping criterion is met.

The mutation operator creates a new candidate solution by perturbing the randomly selected three vectors from the population, denoted by $X_{r1,G}$, $X_{r2,G}$, and $X_{r3,G}$, and computing a new vector, V_i :

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$$V_i = X_{r1,G} + F * (X_{r2,G} - X_{r3,G}) \quad (1)$$

where F controls the scale of the perturbation. Typically, F is set to a value between 0.5 and 2.

The crossover operator combines the information from the mutated vector and the original vector to create a new candidate solution. It is performed by selecting a random index, denoted by $jrand$, and copying the elements of the mutated vector up to the index and the elements of the original vector after the index. The formula for the crossover operator is:

$$\begin{aligned} U_i &= V_i, j = jrand \text{ or } rand() \leq CR \\ V_i \oplus X_i, j &\neq jrand \text{ and } rand() > CR \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

here, U_i and CR are trial vector and crossover probability, and \oplus denotes element-wise crossover. $rand()$ is a uniform random number between 0 and 1.

Finally, the selection operator chooses the candidate solution that has a higher fitness value between the trial vector, U_i , and the original vector, X_i :

$$X'_i = \begin{cases} U_i & \text{if } f(U_i) < f(X_i) \\ X_i & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $f(X)$ is the fitness function of solution X .

The DE algorithm has several variants, such as the DE/rand/1/bin and DE/current-to-best/1/bin, that differ in the selection of the parent vectors and the mutation scheme.

III. IMPROVED DIFFERENTIAL EVOLUTION

Here, we have used three control parameters. The newly introduced constraints $F1$ and F take random values between 0 and 1. N is the product of $F1$ and F and $X_{r1,G}$, $X_{r2,G}$, $X_{r3,G}$ are randomly chosen variables. By involving the best solution vector $X_{best,G}$, this approach converges faster compared to other DE algorithms. The proposed approach is:

$$X' = (X_{best,G} - X_{r1,G}) + N * (F * (X_{best,G} - X_{r2,G}) - F1 * (X_{best,G} - X_{r3,G})) \quad (4)$$

IV. EXPERIMENTAL OUTCOMES

MATLABr2018b was used to implement the suggested IDE approach. By taking into account the crossover probability Cr of 0.8, the results obtained using the five traditional mutation techniques of the DE and IDE methodologies. The number of iterations for fifteen benchmark functions was fixed for different magnitudes. CPU elapsed time of the different algorithms, as presented in Table 1.

V. IMAGE SEGMENTATION

In multi-level threshold based image segmentation, an image histogram is divided into several pixels groups $p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots, p_n$ that are each characterised by grayscale intensity values. There are various multi-level thresholding techniques. One of the most popular is Otsu's method that works on graylevel histogram and finds the threshold by reducing the

within-class variance of the two pixels groups. Here we have combined the Otsu's method with IDE. In Otsu's method, the total variance is calculated as the sum of the weighted within-class variances and the between-class variance for any given threshold (n):

$$\sigma^2 = \sigma_w^2(n) + c_1(t)[1 - c_1(t)][\mu_1(n) - \mu_2(n)]^2 \quad (5)$$

here σ_w and individual class variances are formulated as:

$$\sigma_1^2(n) = \sum_{i=1}^n [i - \mu_1(n)]^2 \frac{p(i)}{c_1(n)} \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_2^2(n) = \sum_{i=n+1}^I [i - \mu_2(n)]^2 \frac{p(i)}{c_2(n)} \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma_w^2(n) = c_1(n)\sigma_1^2(n) + c_2(n)\sigma_2^2(n) \quad (8)$$

where $c_1(n)$ and $c_2(n)$ are class probabilities:

$$c_1(n) = \sum_{i=1}^n p(i) \quad c_2(n) = \sum_{i=n+1}^I p(i) \quad (9)$$

And their means are:

$$\mu_1(n) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{ip(i)}{c_1(n)} \quad \mu_2(n) = \sum_{i=n+1}^I \frac{ip(i)}{c_2(n)} \quad (10)$$

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The proposed method was applied on breast tumor dataset obtained from [] to find the tumor. A sample of breast MRI image and the segmented tumor image using IDE technique is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Left side: Original Image, right: Segmented Tumor by proposed algorithm

This preliminary study's outcomes reveal that the proposed algorithm with Otsu's method shows good results for image segmentation. It further helps in the extraction and study of the breast tumor region, which aids in the fast diagnosis and treatment of cancer. It motivates us to analyze the results on a large dataset with other variants of entropy to check their robustness and applicability.

TABLE I
SAMPLE OF RESULT BASED ON CPU TIME TAKEN AFTER 100 RUNS ON BENCHMARK FUNCTIONS

Function	DE/best/1	DE/rand/1	DE/best-to-rand/1	DE/best/2	DE/rand/2	IDE
Sphere	27.55	165.79	22.54	161.9	25.62	20.2
Beale	20.62	10.819	9.96	11.08	11.25	10.5
Booth	13.4	9.6	6.9	11.66	7.71	6.6
Schwefel	8.73	7.93	7.81	5.4	5.54	5.52
Michlewicz	8.7	4.7	5.82	4.89	4.74	4.8
Schaffer N.2	13.1	21.24	14.79	16.94	23.23	13.5
Schaffer N.4	352.4	330.23	324.5	342.3	332.3	323.4
HimmelBlau	6.85	10.98	12.51	9.3	16.27	11.85
Bird	9.73	8.11	5.18	5.27	8.52	4.6
Extended Cube	477.7	462.04	484.06	482.64	464.8	430.3
Ackley	345.9	297.57	323.7	300.56	305.08	305.4
Gold	296.37	261.7	276.5	256.3	267.3	258.3
Griewank	340.55	257.91	317.3	256.6	335.8	250.3
Rastrigin	296.7	246.3	258.7	267.07	258.6	210.4
Rosenbrock	28.08	258.6	278.7	261.8	269.3	17.8

VII. CONCLUSION

Improved DE algorithm (IDE) is proposed, whose results were compared with classical DE algorithms to verify its efficiency. IDE is further combined with the Otsu thresholding technique to segregate the tumorous region in the MRI image. It is observed that it can better segment the image compared to the DE algorithm. In the future, we will apply it to a larger dataset to verify its robustness. The new method can be used in various fields, such as weather prediction.

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Identifying Regions of Intensive Cyclone using Multilevel Thresholding with Variant of Differential Evolution

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Abstract—Cyclones are natural disasters that can cause significant damage to infrastructure and loss of life. Climatologists analyze and study the climate conditions and atmospheric compositions to handle this natural calamity beforehand. Weather radar images help in predicting and understanding the patterns and intensity of the cyclone by segmenting the regions using different color codes. However, selection of the optimal threshold values for each region is a challenging task that can be obtained by using evolutionary algorithms. In this paper, we propose a novel multilevel cyclone image segmentation approach using a variant of the differential evolution algorithm. We evaluate the proposed method on benchmark functions. We incorporate the Renyi entropy to ensure the smoothness and accuracy of the segmentation. The results on a sample of satellite images show that our proposed method has the potential to assist climatologists in identifying the cyclone-intensive regions at an early stage, which can aid in the prediction and management of these natural disasters.

Index Terms—multilevel image segmentation, differential evolution, cyclone region detection, satellite image segmentation, Renyi entropy

I. INTRODUCTION

Climate is a synthesis of the daily weather over a long period of time, whereas weather defines the state of our atmosphere within a given period of time. In order for society to make appropriate plans, climatology aims to analyze and explain the effects of the changing climate. In order to find the velocity, movement, and kind of precipitation, weather monitoring radar is used. Radar pictures of diverse climatic conditions are frequently used in climatology analysis [1]. The photos from the weather radar show reflected particles for a particular region surrounding the radar on a map. Different color codes are used to illustrate precipitation's varied intensities. These photos include a scale of intensity that varies according to the study's chosen meteorological parameter,

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such as a cyclone [2]. The exact sort of threat may be seen by segmenting the photos according to color code, and based on the magnitude, people can get the necessary notifications to ensure their safety.

Automated analysis of weather-related situations uses segmentation of the radar picture. Thresholding is a fundamental method of segmenting photographs into foreground and background images [3]. By adjusting the color components in accordance with color spaces, thresholding is done on colored pictures. However, selecting optimal threshold values for each region can be a challenging task, as it involves finding a balance between sensitivity and specificity. To address this problem, researchers have proposed using optimization algorithms to automate the process of selecting optimal thresholds [4].

In solving optimization problems, the evolutionary algorithms are most effective in finding a near-optimal solution among the existing algorithms [5]. These systems have shown good efficiency with the maximization of evolutionary processes. Differential Evolution (DE) is one such evolutionary algorithm with strong global optimality [2]. In this paper, we have proposed a variant of the differential evolution algorithm. It is combined with a popular multi-thresholding technique called Renyi entropy. This technique has shown promising results in accurately identifying and segregating intense regions of cyclones from satellite images.

The organization of the paper is as follows: Sections 2 and 3 briefly describe the workings of the DE algorithm and the proposed methodology. Sections 4 and 5 show the experimental outcomes and the application of the algorithm to cyclone image segmentation. The results are discussed in Section 6, with a conclusion in Section 7.

II. DIFFERENTIAL EVOLUTION

Differential evolution (DE) is a powerful optimization algorithm that is commonly used in various fields, including image processing, engineering design, and finance. It starts by randomly initializing a population of candidate solutions. These individuals are represented as vectors in the search space,

where each component corresponds to a decision variable. The algorithm then iteratively updates the population using a combination of mutation, crossover, and selection operations.

In the mutation operation, the algorithm creates a new individual V_i by adding a scaled difference between two randomly selected individuals $X_{r1,G}$, $X_{r2,G}$, to a third individual $X_{r3,G}$:

$$V_i = X_{r1,G} + F * (X_{r2,G} - X_{r3,G}) \quad (1)$$

where F controls the scale of the perturbation. Typically, F is set to a value between 0.5 and 2. The crossover operation then combines the new individual with a target individual to create a trial individual.

$$\begin{aligned} U_i &= V_i, j = jrand \text{ or } rand() \leq CR \\ V_i \oplus X_i, j &\neq jrand \text{ and } rand() > CR \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

here, U_i and CR are trial vector and crossover probability, and \oplus denotes element-wise crossover. $rand() \in (0, 1)$ give a uniform random number. Finally, the selection operation chooses the better individual between the trial U_i , and target X_i individuals based on a fitness function.

$$\begin{aligned} X'_i &= U_i \text{ if } f(U_i) < f(X_i) \\ &X_i, \text{ otherwise} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $f(X)$ is the fitness function of solution X . The algorithm repeats these operations until a termination criterion is met [?].

III. VARIANT OF DIFFERENTIAL EVOLUTION

In VaDE, the mutation strategy has three control parameters: a constant parameter F , variables $N1$ and $N2 \in (0, 1)$, where $N2$ is a complement value of $N1$. Random variables X_{r1} and X_{r2} are also used. The mutation factor parameter F accepts a constant value. Traditional tactics have also made use of the mutation factor F . The value of the donor vector is significantly increased due to the use of three separate control settings. Using $N1$ and $N2$, this approach determines the weighted difference of the solution vectors. The weighted difference of these values is calculated as the difference between these values, and it is added to the solution vector.

$$F1 = 0.5 * (1 - F), \quad F = rand(0, 1) \quad (4)$$

$$N = F * F1 \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} X' &= N * (X_{best} + (F * (X_{best} - X_{r1}) \\ &\quad - F1 * (X_{best} - X_{r2}))) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

IV. EXPERIMENTAL OUTCOMES

MATLABr2018b was used to implement the suggested VaDE approach. By taking into account the crossover probability Cr of 0.8, the results obtained using the five traditional mutation techniques of the DE and IDE methodologies The number of iterations for fifteen benchmark functions was fixed for different magnitudes. CPU elapsed time of the different algorithms, as presented in Table 1.

V. MULTI-LEVEL IMAGE SEGMENTATION WITH VADE

Thresholding is a fundamental method of segmenting photographs into foreground and background images. A statistical measure entropy is used to segment the image. In other words, entropy is the statistical measure of randomness to characterize the texture of the input image:

$$Entropy = - \sum_j^m p_j * \log(p_j) \quad (7)$$

The chance that the difference between two adjacent pixels will equal the grey scale values of j and m in this case is given by the symbol p_j . Entropy of a picture gives the amount of information needed for image analysis. In low-entropy systems, little difference exists between pixels and extended runs of pixels. Run is a series of identically colored pixels. Therefore, there will be more consecutive pixels with the same color under low entropy. Low-entropy images contain less information and are more readily compressed. Entropy in a flat picture is zero. High-entropy photos cannot be compressed due to their extremely high pixel contrast. Renyi Entropy is the most popular method among various multi-level thresholding techniques [2]. Here we have combined it with the VaDE technique for segregating the cyclone images. The formula for Renyi entropy with $\alpha >= 0$ is:

$$H_\alpha(X) = \frac{1}{(1 - \alpha)} \log\left(\sum_{i=1}^n p_i^\alpha\right) \quad (8)$$

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The proposed method was applied on satellite radar images obtained from [] to identify the intense regions of the cyclone. A sample of cyclone image and the segmented image for different severity levels using the VaDE technique are shown in Fig. 1.

This preliminary study's outcomes reveal that the proposed algorithm with Renyi entropy shows good results for image segmentation. It further helps in the extraction and study of the cyclone-intensive regions, which helps the climatologist take further actions. The results motivate us to analyze the proposed technique on a large dataset with other variants of entropy to check its robustness and wider applicability.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a variant of the DE algorithm is proposed by reconfiguring the mutation operator. The results were compared with the existing DE algorithms. It is further combined with Renyi entropy to segregate the satellite image of the cyclone based on intensity levels. We found that the proposed VaDE algorithm performed better than the classical DE approach. The work can be further extended to larger datasets to check the wider applicability and robustness of the technique. The new method can be used in various fields, such as land topology and medical image segmentation.

TABLE I
SAMPLE OF RESULT BASED ON CPU TIME TAKEN AFTER 100 RUNS ON BENCHMARK FUNCTIONS

Function	DE/best/1	DE/rand/1	DE/best-to-rand/1	DE/best/2	DE/rand/2	VaDE
Sphere	27.55	165.79	22.54	161.9	25.62	8.2
Beale	20.62	10.819	9.96	11.08	11.25	7.8
Booth	13.4	9.6	6.9	11.66	7.71	12.3
Schwefel	8.73	7.93	7.81	5.4	5.54	6.5
Michlewicz	8.7	4.7	5.82	4.89	4.74	4.66
Schaffer N.2	13.1	21.24	14.79	16.94	23.23	12.3
Schaffer N.4	352.4	330.23	324.5	342.3	332.3	325.7
HimmelBlau	6.85	10.98	12.51	9.3	16.27	6.2
Bird	9.73	8.11	5.18	5.27	8.52	5.2
Extended Cube	477.7	462.04	484.06	482.64	464.8	470.3
Ackley	345.9	297.57	323.7	300.56	305.08	250.4
Gold	296.37	261.7	276.5	256.3	267.3	80.1
Griewank	340.55	257.91	317.3	256.6	335.8	250.1
Rastrigin	296.7	246.3	258.7	267.07	258.6	100.2
Rosenbrock	28.08	258.6	278.7	261.8	269.3	77.1

Fig. 1. Original image and thresholded images at different severity levels.

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Whale Optimization of an Echo State Neural Network for Electric Load Forecasting

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Abstract—In the past years planning and monitoring power generation and consumption has become crucial, in particular when considering renewable energy sources. For this reason, effective load forecasting techniques can guarantee the short-term energy operators to manage their assets efficiently. The aim of this paper is to present a recurrent neural network model for power forecasting, by adopting Whale Optimization Algorithm (WOA) as a tool to increase reliability of load consumption predictions: in particular, standard Feed-Forward Neural Network and Echo State Network are here employed. In order to properly tune each network’s weights and parameters, the recently developed WOA has been used, leading to significant improvements of Echo State Network’s performance. Thus, this model was used for the considered case study, based on open-access data from a power utility in North America. Suitably defined forecasting error indicators have been considered, reporting significant level of accuracy, thus confirming the implemented model and recursive approach’s reliability in terms of standard performance metrics.

Index Terms—whale optimization, load power forecasting, echo state network

I. INTRODUCTION

The real-time balancing of the electricity market and the stability of the electrical grid are very important because electrical energy cannot be stored in bulk and must be consumed as soon as it is produced. This issue becomes even more critical with the increasing penetration of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) into the grid. [1].

In this respect, both load and generation forecasting play an essential role in decision making. In particular, power system planning can be conducted for short-term to long-term period. Often, there are three types of load forecasting categorized as the following [2]: Short-Term Load Forecasting (STLF): One hour to one week load prediction is often called STLF. It is essential for daily operations of the electric power system and can reduce daily running and dispatching costs. Mid-Term Load Forecasting (MTLF): Weekly, or monthly, or yearly up to 10 years ahead load forecasting is labeled as MTLF. It is used to carry out operational power system planning such as maintenance schedule, fuel supply and minor plant activities. Long-Term Load Forecasting (LTLF): One year, or a decade,

or up to several decades ahead load forecasting is named LTLF. It is utilized to facilitate planning extensions such as new power stations, and developing the electric utility.

In particular, a reliable STLF is a crucial requirement for a power market to be efficient, economic, and secure. The more accurate the load forecast, the less the operational costs, and the higher the revenue. Nowadays, STLF has become a critical issue due to the more and more complex loads, deregulation, and more strict power quality and system requirements. In fact, the demand electricity consumption load is quite unpredictable and non-linear because it depends on many factors. Economic factors, time factors, weather variables, geographical parameters, consumption behaviors, and other random factors affect the amount of electric load consumption. Thereby, STLF is a complex and difficult task [3].

To satisfy the prominent STLF, many models have been proposed and used in literature. Several follow conventional approaches, while novel techniques based on computational intelligence have been developed recently, which employ appropriate models to overcome the inherent complexity of the problem. [4], [5].

In this paper we propose a novel way to perform STLF by means of an Echo State Network (ESN) model that can be tuned using the Whale Optimization Algorithm (WOA), a recently proposed evolutionary computation algorithm. The case study considered in this work focuses on hourly forecasting of load consumption, due to its relevance to the daily operations of a power utility, such as load dispatch, energy transfer scheduling, and unit commitment of power plants.

II. RESERVOIR COMPUTING

Conventional feed-forward neural networks (FNN) rely on the assumption that training and testing data sets are independent [6] i.e., the connections between network neurons are not allowed to form cycles (information feedback). However, data are often related in time and space. Therefore, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) can be used, which allow the neurons to have directed cycles within their connections.

Reservoir Computing (RC) [7] is a new approach to RNN design and training, in which only the weights between the reservoir and the outputs are trained. The RNN in this case refers to a fixed “reservoir” that is initially randomly

```

Input: Input data set  $[u(1), \dots, u(T)]$ , and output data set  $[y^{target}(1), \dots, y^{target}(T)]$ 
Output: Trained ESN, forecasted readout  $y^{forecast}(m)$ , and NRMSE of the testing error

//Prepare the data
Preprocess the input and output data sets using Moving Average Filter
Normalize the input and output data sets
Divide the input and output data sets to training sequence and testing sequence

//Generate an ESN reservoir
Choose weight matrices  $W^{in}$  and  $W$ 
Select reservoir size  $N$ , spectral radius  $\rho$ , input scaling, shifting range, washout time  $T_0$ 
Scale matrix  $W$  with  $1/\rho_{max}$  and  $\rho$ 

//Train ESN
Import the training input and output sequences
Initialize the network state as  $x(0) = 0$  and also consequently  $y(0) = 0$ 
 $m = 0$ ;
while ( $m < T_{train}$ )
    Calculate the reservoir activation states  $x(m)$ 
    for ( $T_0 < m < T_{train}$ )
        Update the state collection matrix  $X(m)$ 
    end for
     $m = m + 1$ ;
end while
ESN is trained by calculating the output weight matrix  $W^{out}$ 

//Test ESN
Import the testing input and output sequences in the trained network
Initialize the network state as  $x(0) = 0$  and also consequently  $y(0) = 0$ 
 $m = 0$ ;
while ( $m < T_{test}$ )
    Calculate the reservoir activation states  $x(m)$ 
    for ( $T_0 < m < T_{test}$ )
        Update the state collection matrix  $X(m)$ 
    end for
     $m = m + 1$ ;
end while
Calculate the forecasted output
Compute the NRMSE testing error

```

Fig. 1. Pseudo-code of ESN algorithm.

generated, and the states within it maintain a non-linear transformation of the input signals. Then the linear aggregation of the units of the reservoir gives the desired output, which can be obtained by linear regression using the teacher output (known output) as the target.

Echo State Network (ESN) is a recently proposed implementation of RC [8]: indeed, a generic ESN is a discrete-time recurrent neural network consisting of K input units, a reservoir consisting of N internal units, and M output units. The term *echo* means that the activation states of the internal neurons of the reservoir of an arbitrary recurrent neural network are a function of the history of the inputs presented to the reservoir. ESNs have been widely used in various fields in recent years, especially in engineering [9]–[11].

In Figure 1 the detailed step by step procedure of ESN used in this study is summarized.

III. WHALE OPTIMIZATION

WOA is a very recent meta-heuristic evolutionary algorithm introduced by S. Mirjalili [12] and based on the behavior of humpback whales.

In WOA the exploration phase of the search space happens when the whales are looking for the prey and the exploitation phase takes place while attacking. As a consequence, WOA

```

Input: Objective function,  $N$ ,  $Max_{iter}$ ,  $UB$ ,  $LB$ , and  $b$ 
Output: Global optimum, Global optimizer

Initialize the whales' population  $X \in \mathbb{R}^{(N \times Dim)}$  randomly between  $[LB, UB]$ 
 $t = 0$ ;
while ( $t < Max_{iter}$ )
    Calculate the objective function of each search agent
    Update the leader position:  $X^*$  = the best search agent
    Update the leader score: the best objective function
    Update  $a$ 
    for each search agent
        Update  $A$ ,  $C$ ,  $l$ , and  $p$ 
        if ( $p < 0.5$ )
            if ( $|A| \geq 1$ )
                Select a random search agent  $X_{rand}$ 
                Update the position of the current search agent
            else if ( $|A| < 1$ )
                Update the position of the current search agent
            end if
        else if ( $p \geq 0.5$ )
            Update the position of the current search agent
        end if
    end for
    Check if any search agent goes beyond the search space and scale it back accordingly
     $t = t + 1$ ;
end while
Return best search agent  $X^*$  as the global optimizer
Return the best objective function as the global optimum

```

Fig. 2. Pseudo-code of WOA algorithm.

employs two searching schemes and three sub-schemes to resemble the chasing and hunting behavior of whales: (i) bubble-net foraging maneuver (which includes the encircling prey and spiral-shape movement); (ii) search for prey.

Conversely, the exploitation phase simulates the whales' bubble net method of attack. To hunt, the whales simultaneously explore the search space around the candidate prey (i.e., the optimal solution so far) in a shrinking circle and in a spiral, at the same time. Therefore, it is assumed that there is a 50% chance for each of these two behaviours. Consequently, a new parameter p between $[0,1]$ is randomly generated for each agent to help choose the mechanism for updating the whales' positions.

To better understand the procedure used in WOA, its pseudo-code is displayed in Figure 2. The algorithm starts with generating a set of random solutions for the search agents. Then, at each iteration the agents update their position with respect to either the best agent or a randomly selected agent depending on the value of A . The range that the random parameter A is selected from reduces linearly by each iteration from 2 to 0. It allows the WOA algorithm to smoothly transit from exploration (when $|A| \geq 1$) to exploitation (when $|A| < 1$). Moreover, subject to the value of p , WOA can switch between either a circular path (when $p < 0.5$) or a spiral shape (when $p \geq 0.5$). And finally, WOA is terminated when it reaches a stopping criterion.

Since ESN hyperparameters require fine-tuning to maximise performance, as is usual with computational intelligence techniques that depend on many parameters, the use of a meta-heuristic global optimisation algorithm can fulfill this need: in this work, WOA is used to optimise the hyperparameters of ESN.

In general, the ESN optimisation parameters were consid-

Fig. 3. The proposed recursive approach flowchart, following [14].

ered as spectral radius ρ between $[0, 1]$; input scaling and input shift between $[-1, 1]$; and weight matrices such as input weight W^{in} and internal weight W in the range of $[-1, 1]$. For a better understanding of the proposed WOA-ESN procedure, the flowchart of the model is shown in Figure 3.

For all the case studies in this paper, the WOA settings considered are as follows: number of search agents $N=30$; termination criteria $T_{max} = 40$; and the constant defining the logarithmic spiral shape $b=1$.

IV. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

The considered case study deals with a dataset made available by Puget power utility, a real case in Seattle, USA, with hourly temperature and electricity load data over the period of more than 7 years (68208 hours) [13].

The aim of the simulations was to compare the performance of the above proposed WOA-ESN with other STLF results in literature [14]–[17] on the same dataset. We used input-output of the first 2 years as the training data set, while the last 2 years were used as the testing data set.

One-hour ahead STLF is considered in this case. The ESN has three inputs such as temperature, load and day index, and one output named the forecasted load. The proposed recursive load forecaster method is depicted in Figure 3.

WOA-ESN algorithm was developed in MATLAB software. Raw source code of ESN is taken from Jaeger [18] and WOA raw source code was taken from Mirjalili [12].

The forecasting performance metrics used for the preliminary case are Absolute Error (AE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE). These metrics are chosen to be able to compare the results of WOA-ESN with the previous studies on the same real data sets Puget power utility [14]–[17].

The comparison of the proposed WOA-ESN model with the results obtained by the literature [14]–[17] for 1-hour ahead load forecasting of Puget power utility is reported in Figure 4 which show the resulting MAPE of 1-h ahead load for each day of the week and their average.

It is worth noting that WESN, as described in [14], is based on wavelet transform for multi-resolution decomposition (approximation and detail) of the load or temperature time series. As a result, it is a very complex and time-consuming prediction model, in contrast to the proposed WOA-ESN

Fig. 4. Comparison of WOA-ESN results and other models in terms of MAPE (%), per day.

Fig. 5. Convergence process of WOA optimization algorithm for 1-h load forecasting

model, which achieves the same performance with significantly less computational effort.

Figure 5 demonstrates how the WOA optimization process reached to the optimum NRMSE value. It took the optimization algorithm around 10 iterations out of 30 maximum iterations to achieve the global optimum NRMSE=0.042. In optimization cases, there should be an offset for computational burden and accuracy. It is always a matter of compensation between how many optimization agents are needed in each iteration and how many iterations are estimated to reach an acceptable global optimum. Therefore, the figure establishes that the number of agents which were considered in this case were enough to approach the optimum value quickly and reliably.

Figure 6 represents 1-hour ahead load forecast and AE for

Fig. 6. 1-hour ahead load forecast for 300 hours of the testing period

300 hours of the testing period. Only 300 hours is considered here as a typical sample over the whole 15624 hours of the testing period for better demonstration purposes. The load forecast is depicted in blue and the actual (teacher) load is represented by red color. As it can be seen, the predicted loads are very well aligned on the real loads.

These results show the great capabilities of WOA-ESN to learn the complex dynamics of electricity load time series and predict the near future loads with acceptable high accuracies and relatively fast method.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Considering the importance of power forecasting in current electrical energy application, this work was aimed at proposing a STLF with improved accuracy by means of ESN optimization. ESN is a type of recurrent neural network which is a powerful stand-alone neural network. However, it has many hyper parameters, such as input scaling, input shift, input weight, internal weight, teacher scaling, and teacher shift matrices, and spectral radius, that need to be optimized. Therefore, WOA, a global evolutionary optimization algorithm, was combined to ESN to control and improve its performance. In particular, a recursive approach has been used here to compare with previous work in the literature.

The reported results are promising, especially considering the computational burden of the proposed algorithm compared to previous studies in the literature, thus, showing how an effective STLF can be achieved with a simple WOA-ESN, with high acceptable accuracy.

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Multi-Scale Evolving Deep Neural Networks for Retinal Funds Image Segmentation

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Abstract—Manually designed deep neural network-based architectures are frequently used for segmentation of retinal fundus images, and accurate segmentation of the capillary portion of retinal fundus images is of indispensable importance for clinical diagnosis of ophthalmic diseases. In order to capture the local and global scale information of retinal images more effectively to improve the segmentation accuracy, a multi-scale evolutionary neural network architecture is proposed in this paper. The individual components of the network are specified by a carefully designed encoding strategy, and then the network with the highest adaptation is searched by a genetic evolutionary algorithm (GA) to finally obtain the optimal network structure. In addition, to combine the advantages of both convolutional neural network (CNN) and Transformer, both convolutional and Transformer layers are used as alternative feature extractors, and the GA process determines the optimal perceptual field arrangement. Finally, a perceptual field adaptive multi-scale retinal segmentation model is automatically given by the GA process. The proposed model is evaluated on the public datasets DRIVE, STARE and CHASE_DB1 respectively. The experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of in the proposed method. method.

Keywords—Retinal vessel image segmentation, Deep Neural network, Transformer Unet, Neuroevolution, evolutionary computation

I. INTRODUCTION

Retinal fundus images contain significant numbers of arterial vessels, and changes in their internal morphology and characteristics are the basis for the diagnosis of many diseases. Current medical research has shown that retinal vascular abnormalities are closely associated with many cardio-vascular diseases, such as hypertension, coronary heart disease and diabetes mellitus. In recent years, with the intensive research on retinal vessel segmentation algorithms, exploring an automatic fine segmentation method for retinal vessels has become a critical problem. However, there are many complex structures in the retinal image, such as the optic disc and the central sulcus. In addition, the low contrast between blood vessels and the background makes automatic segmentation of retinal vessel images a great challenge.

In recent years, deep learning-based methods have been rapidly developed. It automatically learns deeper features from a large amount of training data to perform segmentation, and

achieves better results in retinal vessel segmentation tasks. Ronneberger et al. [1] proposed the Unet neural network, which has been widely used in the field of retinal segmentation. In the literature [2]-[5], the accuracy of vessel segmentation is improved by introducing attention modules and residual blocks in the Unet network to obtain features of retinal images. Sha et al. [6] proposed the Transformer Unet (TUnet) neural network. It is based on the Unet network with the transformer module embedded in the encoding part. The local scale information and global scale topological information of retinal images are obtained by convolution and multi-head attention mechanisms, respectively. However, TUnet's network design only fuses the feature maps obtained by the multi-head attention mechanism with the last layer of feature maps in the encoding part, which cannot adequately obtain the multi scale information of images. Deep neural network models require manual setting of the topology and its corresponding hyperparameters. It requires a large number of experienced experts with time. And it is not always possible to design the optimal network structure. Therefore, neuroevolutionary techniques are proposed.

Neuroevolution is an optimization technique that is based on evolutionary computation for generating suitable neural network topologies and their hyperparameters. Evolutionary algorithms start with a population, calculates fitness value for every individual in each generation, and creates the next generation accordingly. Fitness values help the population to converge towards the optimal solution. In neuroevolution, evolutionary algorithms have become a very prevalent method due to its ability to automatically design neural networks. GA [7] is the most popular algorithm among evolutionary algorithms. This is due to its well-established theory and its good performance in solving different optimization problems. It is also recognized that GA can produce high-quality optimal solutions by using mutation, crossover and selection.

Considering the limited amount of data and the complex topology of retinal images, it is crucial for segmentation result to effectively capture local scale and global scale information of retinal images. Therefore, we propose a multi-scale evolving deep neural network for retinal fundus image segmentation. Firstly, an evolutionary strategy based on TUnet is proposed to create retinal segmentation networks. This strategy uses a genotype encoding model based on fixed-length blocks to create a network of variable depth. Secondly, 13 parameters are

optimized using GA. Among the candidate types of feature extraction layers within each block include the multi-head attention layer and the convolutional layer, which are used to obtain global scale and local scale information of retinal images, respectively. The intra-block configurations of the multi-head attention layer and the convolutional layer are automatically searched by a network evolution strategy. Finally, our proposed method is tested with three publicly available retinal datasets, obtaining outstanding segmentation results. Our contributions are as follows:

- We propose a multi-scale evolving deep neural networks for retinal funds image segmentation.
- We propose to use a genotype encoding strategy based on fixed-length blocks to create a variable-depth network, which is optimized by GA.
- We propose to introduce a multi-head attention layer and a convolutional layer among the candidate types of the feature extraction layer for obtaining multi-scale information of retinal images.
- Experiments conducted on three retinal vessel image segmentation datasets demonstrate the effectiveness of our proposed method.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Deep learning for retinal vessel image segmentation

As the field of deep learning is rapidly evolving, many researchers are working on retinal segmentation tasks based on deep neural networks. Huisi Wu et al. [2] proposed a novel scale- and context-sensitive network for retinal vascular segmentation, CS-Net. It includes a feature aggregation module, an adaptive feature fusion module and a multi-level semantic supervision module. Tim Laibacher et al. [3] proposed a retinal image segmentation architecture that can run in real time. It incorporates a pre-training component in the encoder part and a novel systolic bottleneck block in the decoder part with reduced parameters. Zhixin Jiang et al. [4] transformed a global-based segmentation task into a regional task to expand the training samples and combined migration learning to compensate for the lack of training data in retinal images. Kaiqi Li et al. [5] proposed an attention-based mechanism for vascular segmentation network (FANet).

B. Transformer module

The Transformer Unet neural network is based on the Unet network (left in Figure 1) and the encoding part embeds the transformer module to obtain the global topology information of the retinal image. In the right of Figure 1 shows the structure of the transformer module. The transformer module requires sequence data as input to perform the segmentation task through one-dimensional data. Therefore, the original retinal images need to be sprawled into arrays with image patches of size $n \times n$. Transformer encoder outputs feature maps with different receptive domains. Then, they are reshaped to match the size of the Unet encoder feature map and are given directly to the decoder. Finally, the feature maps in the decoder to which they are attached. This guarantees that the input to the decoder contains different information about the image patches, which is more beneficial for the final prediction.

Fig. 1. Unet model and Transformer module

C. Evolving deep neural networks

Designing a neural network manually requires an in-depth knowledge of neural networks, as well as significant computational facilities and time, and it is not always possible to design the optimal topology. A solution to this problem is to use evolutionary computation to automatically design the network. Koutník et al. [9] first applied evolutionary computation to deep networks in 2014. There they applied neuroevolution to compress a visual-based reinforcement learning (RL) neural network. Martín et al. [10] proposed EvoDeep, constructed using a cluster of graphs created by a finite state machine (FSM). The finite state machine has a start and an end node to specify the first and last layers of the network, and other nodes determine the remaining layers. Sun et al. [11] proposed EvoCNN, an evolved DCNN for image classification applications. EvoCNN uses variable length coding to create chromosomes, which in turn create networks of various lengths. In EvoCNN, a GA equipped with a new crossover strategy is utilised for a network's evolution. Shafiee et al. [12] proposed evolutionary synthesis of DNNs as a nature-inspired approach for image segmentation.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

In this paper, we propose a TUNet-based evolutionary strategy to create TUNet-based evolutionary networks, which uses a fixed-length block-based genotype encoding model to create variable-depth networks. In order to create a two-dimensional network architecture, 13 parameters need to be optimized using GA, namely: number of blocks, type of feature extraction layers, number of convolutional layers in each block, number of filters, filter size, dropout, pooling, activation function, shortcut connection, long connection, batch normalization (BN), optimizer, and learning rate.

Table I shows the parameters used to create the network block by block and their corresponding candidate ranges. In the genotype coding model proposed in this paper, each chromosome contains five blocks. Thus there are 57 genes per chromosome, of which 55 are used to create five blocks and the remaining two are used to find the appropriate optimizer and learning rate to train the network. The number of blocks denotes the number of blocks in the down-sampled portion of the network as well as a bridging block. The upsampling block is generated by the parameters of the downsampling block. The candidate types of feature extraction layers include multi-head attention layers and convolutional layers. The multi-head attention layer can acquire the global features of retinal images, and the convolution layer can acquire the local features of retinal images. The multi-scale information of the retinal image is fully obtained by evolving the optimal intra-block feature extraction

layer by GA. Next, we use an example to describe how a (GA) can be used to carry out the evolution of a network.

Since the model proposed in this paper is block-based, we require building the network one block at a time. Thus, 7 parameters are employed to stand for each block. All parameters need to be randomly initialized and then iteratively updated according to the GA. Table II shows an example of the genotype of a block. It can be seen that the first gene indicates whether the block is active (1) or inactive (0) and that all active blocks will be configured into the structure of the network. The block is active and there is a shortcut connection that copies the input feature map of the block to its output; there is also a long connection between the block of the downsampled part of the block and the corresponding block in its upsampled part. The feature extraction layer of this block is based on a local convolutional layer. There is a two-dimensional convolutional layer with a filter size of 3×3 and 16 feature maps as the output of the block. The activation function is Relu and the batch normalization is consistent with the output features. The dropout rate is 0.5, and average pooling is chosen. In the proposed model, the convolution and pooling steps are maintained fixed to two.

TABLE I
HYPERPARAMETERS AND THEIR CORRESPONDING SCOPES

Hyper-parameters	Scope
Number of blocks	5
Type of feature extraction layer	[Multi-head attention (0), Convolution (1)]
Number of convolution layers per block	[1 - 3]
Number of filters	[8, 16, 32, 64]
Filter size	[3×3 , 5×5 , 7×7]
Dropout	[0 - 0.7]
Pooling	[Average pooling (0), Max pooling (1)]
Activation function	[Sigmoid (0), Relu (1)]
Shortcut connection	[0, 1]
Long connection	[0, 1]
Batch Normalisation	[0, 1]
Optimiser	[adam, adagrad, adamax, rmsprop]
Learning rate	[0.1, 0.01, 0.001]

After each genotype is transformed to its corresponding network and the network is trained, the segmentation accuracy value represents the fitness value of each chromosome. In order to create a new generation, the best chromosomes are directly transferred to the next generation. The remaining populations are selected by using the roulette wheel method [13] and a single point crossover operation is used to create a new generation. The chromosomes are mutated to increase the diversity and exploratory power of the GA. For each chromosome, the number of mutations in each chromosome ranges from 0 to 3. Ultimately, the optimal deep neural network for retinal vessel segmentation is obtained.

TABLE II
HYPERPARAMETERS AND THEIR CORRESPONDING SCOPES

Block Activation	Type of feature extraction layer	Number of Conv Layers	Short Connection	Long Connection	Filter size
1	1	1	1	1	3
Number of Filters	Batch Normalisation	Activation Function	Dropout	Pooling	
16	1	1	0.5	0	

IV. EXPERIMENTS RESULTS

A. Implementation details

The proposed model is assessed on three standard datasets: DRIVE [14], STARE [15], CHASE_DB1 [16]. In the above three datasets, we select the data marked by the first independent expert. We perform data enhancements on the three public data sets. The operations used include rotation, flip, and scaling. Vessels of different orientations are extracted from the network by rotation and flipping. Batch size is set to 1. The Tensorflow function library is utilized to implement the proposed model. The experimental computer CPU model is Intel 4214R and the GPU model is NVIDIA Tesla T4.

B. Evaluation metrics

In this paper four performance metrics are selected to measure: accuracy (Acc), sensitivity (Sen), specificity (Spe) and Area under a ROC (AUC).

$$\begin{cases} Acc = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \\ Sen = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}, Spe = \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \\ AUC = \frac{Sen + Spe}{2} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

TP indicates true positive, which refers to correctly identified vascular pixels. FN represents false positive, which means incorrectly identified pixels. TN denotes true negative, the correctly recognized background pixels and FP denotes false negative, the incorrectly recognized background pixels.

TABLE III
COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED METHOD WITH OTHER METHODS

Dataset	Metrics	Unet	Tunet	Zhang[17]	Yan[8]	Optimal Evolutionary Network
DRIVE	Acc	0.9511	0.9579	0.9466	0.9542	0.9610
	AUC	0.8744	0.8907	0.8787	0.8736	0.8925
	Sen	0.7746	0.7901	0.7861	0.7653	0.8040
	Spe	0.9741	0.9732	0.9712	0.9818	0.9809
STARE	Acc	0.9541	0.9631	0.9547	0.9612	0.9631
	AUC	0.8818	0.8904	0.8806	0.8714	0.8979
	Sen	0.7924	0.7953	0.7882	0.7581	0.8104
	Spe	0.9711	0.9712	0.9729	0.9846	0.9852
CHASE_DB1	Acc	0.9146	0.9538	0.9502	0.9610	0.9648
	AUC	0.8186	0.8658	0.8680	0.8721	0.8882
	Sen	0.6759	0.7576	0.7644	0.7633	0.7954
	Spe	0.9632	0.9739	0.9716	0.9809	0.9810

C. Qualitative analysis of experimental results

We test the segmentation results of the optimal evolutionary network in this paper on the DRIVE, STARE and CHASE_DB1 datasets. The first and second rows in Figure 2 show the retinal test images and the corresponding annotated images for each of the three datasets, respectively. The third row of Figure 2 shows the results of the segmentation of the selected test images by the optimal evolutionary network. The segmentation results show that it can effectively detect the fine vessels and the connections between the vessels while segmenting the coarse vessels. The global and local scale information of the retinal image are fully captured. The fourth row in Figure 2 shows the segmentation results of the Tunet model. By comparison, the network proposed in this paper performs better in fine segmentation.

Fig. 2. Comparison of segmentation results of the optimal evolutionary network and the TUNet network for retinal vessel images

D. Quantitative analysis of experimental results

Table III compares the segmentation results of the optimal evolutionary network with the currently popular retinal segmentation models by four evaluation metrics. For the DRIVE dataset, the Optimal Evolutionary Network model achieve the highest Acc, AUC, Sen and Spe values compared to other literature. Among them, the Acc value is significantly higher compared to other literature, reaching 0.9610. For the STARE dataset and CHASE_DB1 dataset, the Optimal Evolutionary Network model have higher Acc, AUC, Sen, S pe values compared to other literature.

V. CONCLUSION

Deep neural network architectures based on artificial design are widely deployed in retinal fundus image segmentation tasks. These models usually consist of a CNN-based encoder and decoder. Instead of CNNs, some network architectures that use the Transformer as an encoder have been widely investigated. Unlike the local field of perception of CNN, Transformer has a global field of perception, which enables better extraction of global topological features of retinal images. However, the ability of CNN to capture local features of the retina is also indispensable. In order to segment retinal fundus images more effectively, a multi-scale evolutionary neural network architecture is proposed in this paper. The components of the network are specified by a carefully designed coding strategy, and then the best network structure is searched by GA. In addition, convolutional and Transformer layers are used as alternative feature extractors, and the GA process determines the optimal perceptual field arrangement. Finally, a perceptual field adaptive multi-scale retinal segmentation model is automatically given by the GA process. The proposed model is evaluated on

three public datasets. Comparisons with the contemporary popular retinal segmentation literature are made better segmentation results.

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Approximating and Predicting Energy Consumption of Portable Devices

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Abstract—In this paper we discuss the importance of software energy consumption, particularly in mobile devices, and the need to estimate the impact of applications on the availability of electrical energy stored in these devices. For this purpose, a series of experiments are presented to collect data on resource utilisation, such as CPU, GPU and RAM, in order to predict the energy consumption of applications. We analysed the loss of information between experiments conducted at different time intervals and found that the best interval for collecting information was 120 seconds. The results of the experiments show good custom accuracy due to the custom loss with hyperparameters, and the neural model has higher performance with alpha equal to 1 for both loss functions.

Index Terms—energy consumption, approximation, modeling, loss function, mobile

I. INTRODUCTION

In the modern world, energy consumption is a major problem for systems [5, 10, 22, 21]. Supercomputers, for instance, currently consume several megawatts of electric energy per hour, making it crucial to identify the processes that consume the most energy. This has led to a growing interest in software energy consumption. Kaushik and Johnson were among the first to discuss the importance of software energy consumption and its impact on hardware [26]. Much of the past work in this area has focused on managing hardware/software systems measurements and optimization [6, 7, 20, 18].

Despite the fact that mobile devices, such as laptops, smartphones, and smart devices, have greatly improved in terms of processing power and information storage capacity, their main limitation is still the energy capacity that they can store. This limitation affects the activities that users can perform on these devices. Therefore, research has been conducted to estimate the impact of the applications executed by the user on the availability of electrical energy stored on these mobile devices [28, 17].

To estimate this impact, a series of experiments have been carried out to collect data on the utilization of resources, such as CPU, GPU, and RAM, among others, in order to predict the energy that could be consumed by applications [19, 3, 12, 9]. Tiwari et al. [29, 26] conducted one of the earliest studies on power measurements by demonstrating the energy of CPU

instructions utilizing a base energy, just as a progress energy for each pair of instructions. Lorch and Smith [24] examined programming methods to use power saving arrangements provided by different hardware components. Other research has focused on the energy efficiency of software by addressing memory-related energy consumption [4, 1], I/O operations and storage [1], and operating system (OS) efficiency at a daily routine or OS call level [23].

Gurumurthi et al. [15] presented a power simulator, SoftWatt, to simulate power utilization on mostly hardware components such as CPU or memory systems. Amsel et al. [2] built a tool, GreenTracker, that mimics a real system's power utilization dependent on CPU measurements, and benchmarks each application power. Gupta et al. [14] described a strategy for estimating the power utilization of applications running on a Windows Phone 7. In summary, the goal of all these researches has been to study the energy consumption of system resources with respect to specific hardware.

It is for this reason that we have decided to be involved in a research that helps us to be able to make an approximation of the impact that the applications executed by the user have on the availability of electrical energy stored on these mobile devices. To do this, we have carried out a series of experiments so that we can make an estimation and at the same time collect data on the resources utilization such as the use of CPU, GPU, RAM, among others, to be able to predict the energy that could be consumed by applications.

II. APPROXIMATING ENERGY CONSUMPTION

Energy consumption is a significant problem of the modern-day, which impacts our environment, and this is the time to realize how we can minimize our energy consumption [27]. Monitoring activities of the user on systems is a common task nowadays, and there are so many different computer programs that are being used to track the activity and simulate the user's productivity in various industries. We conducted several experiments to take the measurements of effects to monitor the information. The goal of our research is to find out the optimal sampling time that will not have a significant effect on energy consumption. As even if we talk about only in the software engineering industry, companies are trying to monitor the activity of developer to capture daily productivity and also use such data to simulate productivity or use for

different analysis. We know data is a significant asset, but even such products consume energy, which makes us think, if there is any reasonable way to collect and monitor, in such a way, that will be optimal concerning the energy consumption and it will not reflect the actual monitoring tool. We capture information of the system at different time intervals from 15 seconds to 5 minutes due to our end goal for such experiments is to find the information loss between different intervals, and also we can find out how the information capture tool impacts our energy. We will address the problem of losing information by capturing it in different intervals in this section. Thus, We have conducted experiments on a constant load on a machine to find the exact data loss between two experiments. To neglect the effect of our data collector, we measure the time and energy consumed in mW (milliwatts) to take the average energy consumed per seconds in mW. So that, we call this as "baseline energy consumption per second" by our machine, and to take out the effect of the data collector, we subtract that baseline consumption value from experiments values and take the average consumption by data collector and to dismiss the impact, we deducted that average effect of data collector from the original values.

Experiments we have conducted were based on different intervals and on the same workload, on the same machine and subtracting the collector effect due to energy consumed by data collector on less interval or big interval. In our first experiment to capture information after 15 seconds. We use InnoDataCollector [13, 11] in order to capture information at different intervals in order to complete our experiments.

We ran a 15-seconds experiment as our baseline experiment and throughout this paper, we will compare all other experiments to our baseline, to see how much information we can lose if we change our interval. A constant amount of power has been consumed throughout the experiment once we charge our device to full power and we start our data collector and set the timer to collect data after every 15 seconds and monitor how much energy in terms of mW has been consumed in 15 seconds and collect data until device consumed all the power of the battery. In Figure 1, we are showing power consumed for the whole battery until all power of the battery consumed.

After all, experiments we collect, we try to figure out which experiment is fit and best in order to save our energy and don't lose information that we want to collect. The main goal of this research is to find the optimal interval on which we can collect information with optimal consumption of energy and without losing much information.

III. PREDICTING ENERGY CONSUMPTION

As we have discussed before, energy consumption has a significant impact on our environment. And due to this, now we know that it is becoming a concern among society. But unfortunately, nowadays, there is no clear understanding of how to solve energy problems in the software engineering process. So we can say that every application should pass through a redesigning process in which it will help reduce

environmental issue associated with inefficient energy consumption. So prediction models play a fundamental role in the decision-making process.

We conducted several experiments and predicted energy consumption per timestamp according to RAM, VRAM, CPU and time interval. We choose LSTM(long short-term memory) recurrent neural network because of time series nature of data. Due to small intervals, we had in battery consumption values a lot zeros(66%). In our case we can't use Poisson regression or negative binomial regression because we have time series data. Also from a lot o studies we can say that neural networks can give us better results. So there a lot of papers about zero inflated problems. A lot of works are connected to medicine or natural disasters.

Because in this areas it is not possible to generate data and there are many zero values due to the rare occurrence of any such as death or tornado, a large number of zeros can indicate not only zero inflated problem but also hurdle problem.[25] A hurdle model posits that the zeros and non-zeros occur from different processes.They compared ZIP regression model, hurdle Poisson regression model and ANN. So neural network shows the best result. In this paper they used Artificial Neural Network with loss function MSE(mean square error).

In paper [8] they tried to predict property damage from tornadoes with zero-inflated neural networks.They identified several models and developed several neural models. Combined models without any regularization showed lowest performance. Deep neural network architectures were explored for combined conditional models, wide models displayed the best performance. We can see another paper with comparison of different models in [16]. They compared Poisson regression (PR), negative binomial regression (NBR), zero-inflated Poisson regression (ZIPR) and zero-inflated negative binomial regression (ZINBR) and ANN. They predicted people who had a first-time successful donation were followed for five years. They used independent variables such as sex, age, weight, marital status, education, job, blood group. Percent of zeros is 50,9%. ANN model had the best performance of prediction of number of return to blood donation in both training and test data set compared with models that was used in this article.

According to this papers we can say that neural networks show better results than more simple models. Simple models have limitations that may not presence in actual data that can lead to turbulence in predictions. For these situations, neural networks could be suitable alternative rather than classical statistical methods such as PR, NBR.

A. Predictions

For predictions we used bidirectional LSTM model with two layers. This kind of model are suit for our data, because we have time series data with 14 processes for one time stamp. Parameters for neural network were CPU, RAM, VRAM and interval. For fitting models, 67% cases were used as training set, and 33% were used as test set. We tried to predict battery consumption, we distributed the value of the batter

Fig. 1: Experiment

consumption for each process by distributing it according to the percentage of RAM for each time period:

$$battery\ consumption_{for\ process} = \frac{battery\ consumption * RAM}{sum(RAM)}$$

We didn't use CPU parameter for this because of small interval of time when data was collected and part values of CPU are equals to zero.

Also big concern is about loss function. The reason is big amount of zeros in battery consumption values. Because of this standard loss functions are shows poor results(almost all predicted values were very small). For this case we checked different loss functions such as mean absolute error(MAE), mean square error(MSE) , LogCosh. Idea is to create custom loss function that can penalize model if predictions are equals to zero when true values are not zero. Lets define loss function $F = \sum_{i=1}^n f(pred_i, true_i)$. We decided to implement two loss functions:

$$f_1(pred_i, true_i) = \begin{cases} c * |true_i|^\alpha, & \text{if } true_i \neq 0, pred_i = 0, \\ |pred_i - true_i|^\alpha, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

$$f_2(pred_i, true_i) = \begin{cases} c * |pred_i|^\alpha, & \text{if } pred_i \neq 0, true_i = 0, \\ |pred_i - true_i|^\alpha, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

In this case c and α is some hyper parameters that should be tuned. We tried to find hyper parameter c in this values [1, 1.5, 2, 2, 5] and α n this values [10, 30, 100, 300, 1000, 3000]. We tried to find the best hyper parameters for LSTM.

Also there are question how to evaluate model accuracy. We come up for this decision: count all match zeros in true data and predictions and when they are both not zeros. Then sum up this and find percent of total amount of data.

For this experiment we run our model with all hyper parameters, with 20 epochs and to assess the effectiveness of the model, we used our custom accuracy.

According to this we have found the maximum accuracy value according to our accuracy. The best results for F_1 (Table

TABLE I: Best results for $loss_1$ function

hyper parameters	in-sample data	out-of-sample data
$\alpha = 1, c = 10$	0.837	0.841
$\alpha = 1, c = 300$	0.835	0.838
$\alpha = 1, c = 3000$	0.836	0.840
$\alpha = 1.5, c = 10$	0.792	0.795
$\alpha = 1.5, c = 300$	0.821	0.826
$\alpha = 1.5, c = 3000$	0.789	0.792
$\alpha = 2, c = 30$	0.744	0.745

TABLE II: Best results for $loss_2$ function

hyper parameters	in-sample data	out-of-sample data
$\alpha = 1, c = 30$	0.814	0.819
$\alpha = 1, c = 100$	0.803	0.805
$\alpha = 1.5, c = 3000$	0.686	0.686
$\alpha = 2, c = 3000$	0.688	0.689
$\alpha = 2.5, c = 3000$	0.744	0.745

I) is hyper parameters $\alpha = 1$ and $c = 3000$. Accuracy for train data is 83% and for test data 84% . The best results for F_2 (Table II) is hyper parameters $\alpha = 1$ and $c = 30$. Accuracy for train data is 81% and for test data 81%.

For both of this losses we can see that the best results are for $\alpha = 1$ and for all coefficients c . After $\alpha = 1$ as the value α increases, the accuracy decreases.

IV. CONCLUSION

We conduct different experiments and find the difference between information collected by experiments, and find-out information loss between each experiment. We assume that information that we collected on 15 seconds interval is our required baseline information that we need, but if we collect that information so frequently we spend a lot of energy in order to collect information. We take out the effect of data collector and remains only information that we want to collect and we did for all experiments, and with the assumption of that we collect almost correct information with 15 seconds interval, we normalize all other intervals data we collect with

TABLE III: Error between experiments with respect to information collected during 15 seconds experiment.

Interval(seconds)	MAE	MSE	Curve Area (W)
30	25.399	997.32	59571.73
60	23.012	899.55	79235.22
120	21.817	713.112	19692.80
180	22.92	842.41	3152.47
240	22.50	831.657	13888.36

15 seconds interval, we take different metrics in order to find the information loss between two curves, we consider three different metrics: a) MAE (Mean Absolute Error), b) MSE (Mean Squared Error), and c) Area under the curve difference.

Table III represents the information loss of intervals, as we can see from table information loss between really big intervals is really high and also we measure that interval to collect information after each 120 seconds is the best interval with respect information loss, in that interval we don't lose much information as compared to any other interval. As a result this analysis and approximation we believe will help a lot of modern days software and products that is used to monitor activity of system or monitor the activity of the user on system in order to estimate the productivity of their employees.

According to the results that were provided we can see good custom accuracy due to our custom loss with hyper parameters. We can see that neural model have higher performance with $\alpha = 1$ for both loss functions. Since a large α does not give great results, we should continue to work with $\alpha = 1$ and come up with more metrics that can help evaluate the model and choose which of the coefficient c values is best suited and how much the coefficient c in the loss function affects the model.

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Examining the Success of an Open Source Software Project Analysing Its Repository

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Abstract—The aim of this study is to explore the concept of success of an open source project by pursuing two objectives. The first objective is to gain a comprehensive understanding of the factors that contribute to project success by collecting and analyzing project metrics from various sources. The second objective is to identify a relevant subset of project metrics that can be used to cluster projects based on their success.

Overall, the originality of this study lies in its approach to identifying successful open source projects. While previous studies have focused on identifying successful GitHub projects, this study takes a more consistent approach of project clustering based on specific success criteria. To achieve the first objective, we conducted a thorough literature review to identify the most relevant project metrics. To achieve the second objective, we collected two sets of project metrics data, including a training set of 3,124 projects from GitHub repositories and a test set of 228 projects from the Apache Incubator website. We applied the DBSCAN clustering algorithm, using different combinations of selected metrics to create clusters associated with success. To evaluate the effectiveness of our approach, we developed a simple KNN classifier to categorize projects as successful or unsuccessful based on the resulting clusters. The model testing results showed an accuracy of 88.5%, a specificity of 78.26%, and an F1-Score of 80%.

Index Terms—repository, assessment, metrics, data retrieval, machine learning, DBSCAN

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past few decades, developers have been exploring various methodologies, techniques, and tools to increase the likelihood of successfully achieving software project goals [1]–[3]. The use of these systems has led to the generation of numerous project metrics [4]–[6], which we can explore to better understand the success of software projects. Many researchers have already investigated the idea of using project metrics to infer additional information about open-source projects [7]–[9]. These works often focus on general repository metrics, such as the number of commits, pull requests, forks, stars, and watchers [10], [11]. The authors also categorized metrics available on GitHub as having either a low or high impact on success. They found that project forks and watchers had the most influence on success, while the number of

commits, branches, releases, contributors, and issues had less impact. As a result, we can conclude that “failure to meet one of these High Impact criteria will have a greater impact on the outcome, which in this case is the success or popularity of the project or the opposite” [10, p. 150]. However, the number of potential project metrics is overwhelming, and while the meaning behind major metrics has been explored in many works, the understanding of other, possibly more obscure, metrics is still shallow.

In this paper, we have two primary goals. The first is to investigate the idea of project success and analyze potentially related project metrics. The second is to identify a subset of project metrics that can allow clustering algorithms to produce success-related clusters and test to what extent the resulting clusters model the concept of success.

To achieve these goals, we pose the following research questions:

RQ 1. What are the objective criteria for determining project success?

To understand what contributes to project success, it is important to have a clear understanding of what this concept entails. One reliable approach to gain such an understanding is to consult existing studies. Therefore, in our investigation, we aim to explore how various research studies view project success, with a particular focus on open source projects hosted on services like GitHub.

RQ 2. What project metrics can be derived from open-source repositories?

In addition to defining what success means, we are also keen to explore the indicators that help us identify it. These indicators can be found in the state of the project, such as its metrics. Although some researchers have their own perspectives on which metrics are associated with success, we do not want to restrict ourselves to their views. Therefore, we aim to compile a set of metrics that align with our research goals.

RQ 3. Can we classify the ongoing projects by their success rate using project metrics and clustering algorithms?

To create a classifier, a labeled dataset is essential. However, GitHub does not provide explicit success measures, making it challenging to gather the necessary data. To overcome this challenge, we need an automatic and objective method to label projects in terms of their success. A potential solution is to hypothesize that projects form natural clusters with different degrees of success. To test this hypothesis, we can apply DBSCAN clustering algorithm, since it is able to handle clusters of different shapes and sizes and, more importantly, to identify and exclude noise points that do not belong to any cluster [12]. This approach will allow us to identify success indicators within each cluster and use them to label the rest of the projects in the dataset.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II provides an overview of works that define the success of a software project and utilizes various GitHub metrics to derive its meaning in the context of GitHub. Section III lists the metrics we will use. Section IV provides reasoning behind the creation of metric groups, details on the application of analysis and clustering. Section V explains the need to create our own dataset, and provides principles for the formation of train and test datasets. Section VI presents the collected dataset via various statistical descriptions, provides the results of the clustering, and reviews the performance of the devised classifier on a test dataset.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Numerous studies have examined different aspects of project success, with the most common perspective being from a business [13] or project management viewpoint [14]. Generally, researchers consider economic success and user satisfaction as part of product success, while compliance with expected time and budget constraints, along with the quality of project management, fall under management success. However, there is no common viewpoint on system quality, and some researchers list it under management success, while others consider it a part of product success [15].

Despite extensive research on project success, only a few studies provide a specific definition [14]. Therefore, this study aims to explore available definitions of project success in terms of both project management and product success.

Traditionally, a project is considered successful from a project management perspective if it is delivered within the estimated time, cost, and effort [16], [17]. However, this definition may prove invalid if the project goes over the time and budget constraints but still has business success. Hence, relying solely on managerial success might be insufficient for measuring project success [18]. Ultimately, most managerial success criteria come down to determining whether the project meets the organizational needs of the organization and satisfies the stakeholders [19], which in turn depends on the competences of managers and leaders [14], [20], [21].

Project metrics can be derived from the project's state. For example, in agile projects, project metrics can be easily derived from lead time, velocity, throughput, story points, etc., but next to none of the GitHub projects provide such metrics.

Nevertheless, project metrics suitable for GitHub projects do exist.

One such fascinating metric is the Truck Factor, which refers to the "minimal number of developers that have to be hit by a truck (or quit) before a project is incapacitated" [22, p. 1]. A high value of Truck Factor implies that the amount of common knowledge between developers is enough for the project to be maintained even in dire situations [23]. Another applicable project metric is churn, which refers to the changes in project source code, specifically additions and deletions [24]. Guerrouj *et al.* [25] discovered that a higher churn rate might harm the project rating and popularity, and as we have already discovered, popularity influences the success of the project [26].

Moreover, product success can be generally defined as the extent to which a project meets the needs of its owners and users [17]. Alternatively, it can be viewed as the business value of the project [16], [27], which is the amount of profit that investors gain as the project is improved and generates more revenue. In agile projects, business value is also relevant to managerial success and specifically focuses on perceived quality and delivery time as key factors [28]. Maximizing business value can increase project visibility for both developers and customers [29].

It's worth noting that business value needs to be defined specifically by the project's organization to address its needs, and there is no one specific way to measure business value [18]. As for GitHub projects, repository owners usually do not define business value or make it unavailable to the public. The same goes for other similar metrics; most of the time, they are simply not accessible or cannot be clearly defined.

Nonetheless, the definition of product success can be partially useful. Its only aspect that is applicable to GitHub is the project's popularity. Most works about GitHub success share this point of view; as stated by Bissyande *et al.* [30, p. 309], "A project is found successful user-wise if many GitHub users watch its development." Even so, since the most common success criteria do not apply to GitHub projects, researchers attempt to measure success via publicly available metrics on GitHub.

GitHub tracks a lot of information about the project and stores most of it, meaning that a lot of public data is available for extraction. In GitHub-related papers, researchers either go in-depth about one specific metric or draw conclusions based on an aggregation of metrics. The first group uses metrics such as watchers [31], [32], stars [33], issues [34], and forks [35]. As for the second group, Maqsood *et al.* [10] consider how pull requests, commits, and forks altogether affect the project's success. Kobayakawa *et al.* [36] explore how the presence and contents of the `Contributing.md` file influence the project's commits, contributors, and pull requests. Coelho *et al.* [37] take into account a variety of project metrics to identify not actively maintained projects. We can use their experiences to build our own set of metrics.

III. EXPLORING GITHUB METRICS

GitHub stores a vast amount of historical information for every project. The information provided by the various repository sections on GitHub can be divided into the following groups: general repository information, commits, issues, pull requests, releases, workflows, forks, stars, and insights. The list of GitHub-provided metrics for each group can be found in Table I.

While the names of most metrics in Table I are self-explanatory, we would like to cover the ones in the "insights" group more in-depth. Various combinations of metrics can be used together to gather insight on the project's state. One such grouping allows viewing the repository's activity over a certain period of time. GitHub refers to it as the repository's "pulse". Pulse takes three groups of metrics into account: active pull requests in the form of merged and newly opened ones, active issues in the form of closed and newly created ones, and the number of new commits. Aside from pulse, the insights group presents the user with a variety of graphs and text data related to events that take place in the project. We should mention one of the insights called "viewing traffic". It allows for the project's popularity to be tracked throughout its existence in great detail. However, we do not consider this a viable metric since only GitHub repository owners can access it. Entries in Table I, aside from just being used as project metrics, can also be combined to produce more complex metrics to represent various specific metrics relations. For instance, the total number of commits can be combined with the age of the repository to reveal the average number of commits made per day. The full list of such metrics can be found in Table II.

IV. METHODOLOGY

To achieve our objectives we planned our work in two parts: identification of the relevant metrics and classification of the projects. Literature review helped us to define the indicators of the project success. Using them we were able to construct train and test sets for the proposed classification algorithm which employed DBSCAN and Cartesian distances.

A. Identification of the relevant metrics

In the Literature Review we concluded that there is no uniform standard that allow us to reason about the success of projects. The only information we can base our reasoning around is a set of project metrics that was deemed to reflect the project's success across works of other researchers. For instance, Canovas Izquierdo *et al.* [38] used the number of commits in the project's pull requests to study its popularity among external contributors. Maqsood *et al.* [10] attempted to derive project popularity, which they concluded is akin to success, by examining the amount of stars, forks, and watchers a project has. Bissyande *et al.* [34] considered the number of issue reporters and its correlation with such metrics as watchers and pull requests. Consequently, we are to consider the number of watchers [31], stars [33], and forks as the primary indicators of project success.

Table I: Directly accessible project metrics

Metric Group	Related metrics Per Every Item In The Group	Related Metrics Per Whole Project
Commits	Additions, Deletions, Date, Commit Message Length, Affected/Added/Deleted Files	Total Count, Total Additions, Total Deletions, Days Since First Commit, Days Since Last Commit
Issues	Comments, Labels, Participants, Assignees, Date Closed/Opened, Title Length In Characters, Body Length In Characters, Total Comment Reactions, Interval Between Comments	Total Count, Open Count, Closed Count, Bugs Count, Total Labels, Total Comments
Pulls	Days To Close, Title Length In Characters, Body Length In Characters, Assignees, Reviewers, Commits, Comments Of Users, Comments Of Reviewers, Additions, Deletions, Files Added/Changed/Deleted, Labels, Date Opened/-Closed/Merged	Total Count, Open Count, Merged Count, Closed Count, Total Lines Added/Deleted
Releases	Tags, Body Length In Characters, Title Length In Characters, Date Created, Number Of Assets, Asset Sizes, Asset Downloads	Total Count, Total Downloads
Workflow Runs	Duration In ms, Result (success/failure), Date Ran	Total Count
Forks	Date Forked	Total Count
Stars	Date Starred	Total Count
Insights	-	Active Issues, Active Pull Requests, Active Commits, Active stars
General	-	Watchers, Size in Kb, Folders, Files, Topics, Branches, Contributors, Age In Days, Number Of Workflows, Number Of Programming Languages Used, README Length In Characters

However, any given project can be reasoned about based on a number of its aspects. We hypothesize that a measure of project success that is based solely on the success aspect of the project might not be objective. For instance, it is logical to assume that a small project with 100 stars is successful, while an enormous years-old project with 100 is unsuccessful. Additionally, for any two projects similar in size and with the same values of success metrics, where one is still active, and the other one has been abandoned for several years, it is reasonable to assume that the still active one is more successful.

As a result, we decided that there are two more project aspects that should be taken into account when reasoning about success: activity, and project size; the usage of project size lessens the bias associated with it, while activity reveals which projects are abandoned. Size metrics allow for better identification of success in small projects, because big successful projects are bound to have higher values of success metrics. To account for project size, we utilize metrics that reflect the

Table II: Derived project metrics

Metric Group	Derived project metrics
Commits	Average Commits Per Day, Average Additions, Average Deletions, Average Number Of Changed Files, Average Message Length in characters, Maximum Commits Per Day
Issues	Average Participants, Average Assignees, Average Labels, Average Reactions, Average Closing Time In Days, Average Amount Of Comments, Average Interval Between Comments, Average Comment Length In Characters, Average Title Length In Characters, Average Body Length In Characters, Maximum Per Day, Average Opened Per Day, Closed To Total, Bugs To Total
Pull Requests	Closed To Total, Average Lines Added/Deleted, Average Closing Time In Days, Average Reviewers, Average Assignees, Average Comments, Average Review Comments, Average Commits, Average Body Length In Characters, Average Title Length In Characters, Average Labels, Created Per Day, Maximum Created Per Day
Releases	Average Body Length In Characters, Average Title Length In Characters, Average Assets, Average Asset Downloads, Average Aster Size, Created Per Day, Average Downloads Per Day
Workflow Runs	Successful To Total, Failed To Total, Skipped To Total, Average Duration In ms, Average Failures/Successes Per Day
Forks	Average Forks Per Day
Stars	Average Stars Per Day, Maximum Stars Per Day
Insights	-
General	-

Table III: Project aspects and corresponding metrics

Aspect	Associated Metrics
Size	Files, Folders, Size in Kb
Success	Total Star Count, Total Fork Count, Total Watcher Count
Activity	Active commits, Active pull requests, Active issues

amount of data in the repository: number of folders/files, and the total project size in bytes. As for the project activity, we are to use the pulse metrics from the “insights” metric group. Table III presents the resulting list of project aspects and related metrics.

To reiterate, we would like to study such aspects of a project as its success, size, and activity. We have already concluded that certain sets of metrics represent these aspects, but the groups of associated metrics can be expanded. The number of metrics potentially related to each aspect is overwhelming; thus, it is important to research how different metrics are linked to the aforementioned aspects. To do so we assume that the metrics associated with each aspect represent it. We can then determine how values of all project metrics are associated with the ones representing the aspects. In other words, we can calculate the correlation coefficients for all possible metric pairs, specifically the Spearman correlation coefficient [39]. The correlations values allow us to judge how metrics are associated to each other. We are to include additional associated metrics to the aspects they have strong correlation with (correlation value higher than 0.6).

B. Classification of the projects

After the metric groups are expanded, we can proceed with the classification of the projects. The classification is

composed of two parts. First is concerned with labeling the obtained train dataset, because, as mentioned before, GitHub does not provide explicit information about project success. The second part covers the process we adopted to reason about the degree of success of any GitHub project based on the labeled dataset.

In order to label the dataset, we turned to clustering algorithms, specifically DBSCAN [40], [41]. In our case, the feature space for the DBSCAN is a combination of metrics that represent project size, success, and activity. We investigated all possible combinations of them: we run DBSCAN on every set of metrics that can be formed based on the chosen ones. To roughly quantify the performance of DBSCAN we calculate average values of success metrics for each produced cluster and compare them. Hyperparameter tuning is done until only two clusters are produced and one of the clusters has lower average values of activity metrics and significantly lower average values of success metrics.

After having procured the clusters where projects are split based on their success, we used the acquired clusters to construct a process that allows us to determine the success of any given project. Foremost, we found the centroids of the produced clusters in the space, where dimensions correspond to all available project metrics. Then, we represented the given GitHub repository as a point in the aforementioned space. To determine the success of the project, we calculated the Cartesian distances from the corresponding point to the centroids of clusters; the project is deemed to belong to the cluster it has shorter distance to.

V. DATA COLLECTION

Although GitHub data can be obtained from existing datasets such as the MSR 2016 challenge dataset [42] or the GHTorrent [43] dataset, they are generally not tailored to specific research objectives. These datasets collect either specific types of information or shallow general information. To obtain the necessary data for our research, we developed our own scraper that interacts directly with the GitHub API. This approach is more efficient than querying multiple services, some of which may not provide the necessary data or may provide corrupted data [10].

The scraping process heavily relies on the PyGithub [44] library, to the extent that all requests to the API are made using it. The library is mainly used because it provides convenient Python wrappers for all GitHub objects and has functions that perform requests to all the API endpoints. The architecture of the scraper is divided into three categories: fetching data from the API, saving data to disk, and calculating results from the saved data. The “Metric group” described in Section IV was chosen as the object type to model the classes after. Ultimately, the following nine groups of metrics were separated: issues, pull requests, releases, workflows, commits, contributors, forks, stars, and general repository information.

A. Train Dataset

Currently, more than 45 million public repositories are hosted on GitHub [45]. However, the selection of GitHub projects suitable for analysis is a non-trivial task: it is necessary to filter out certain repositories in order to get representative results. Firstly, we should exclude personal projects. Secondly, every project we analyze must have existed for a specific period of time for the analysis to prove meaningful. Both requirements can be satisfied by introducing inclusion criteria.

The first requirement can be met by only accepting projects with more than a certain number of contributors and forks. We made a reasonable assumption that most personal repositories have one contributor. Then, we investigated how the number of forks corresponds to the state of the project for a random sample of 100 small GitHub projects. We concluded that small projects are less likely to be personal if they have three or more forks. Thus, having at least three forks was chosen as the first inclusion criterion.

As for the second requirement, we decided that repositories need to mature for a certain amount of time. Such a period is necessary for all the development processes to be fully set up and the developers to start consistently working on the project. We turned to the existing literature to find a suitable time period.

Consequently, the project is deemed fit for analysis if it meets the following requirements:

- 1) Has at least two contributors;
- 2) Has at least three forks;
- 3) Has existed for at least two years.

The resulting train dataset must include both successful and unsuccessful projects. Thus, to retrieve success projects we made use of the “Collections” service GitHub provides. The service is meant to aggregate promising (mostly successful) repositories into collections. For no specific reason, we decided to retrieve repositories from all currently available “Made in ...” collections.

Then, to further expand the dataset with either successful and unsuccessful projects, we turned to GitHub’s search functionality. Before explaining the search process, we must note that GitHub API is made to provide only the first 1000 results based on the given query. Thus, to get repositories that fit the inclusion criteria, we used the advanced search functionality to specify the required age of the repository and the required number of forks; the number of contributors had to be accounted for in code, as GitHub does not provide such a filter. As a result, we included all the repositories API provided into the dataset.

Lastly, we decided to expand the dataset specifically with unsuccessful repositories. We assumed that unsuccessful repositories are more likely to include specific negative keywords in their issues, about page, and README. It should be noted that even if a successful repository is unintentionally retrieved this way, it regardless allows us to expand the dataset. We then proceeded to include all repositories fitting inclusion criteria, that the following Google queries have resulted in:

```
site:github.com abandoned
site:github.com dead
site:github.com unmaintained
site:github.com retired
```

B. Test Dataset

Aside from the main dataset containing GitHub project metrics, we also need to collect a test dataset to check the performance of the classifier. We had to create our own test dataset, since the search for datasets that contain success labels for GitHub repositories did not provide any results. Building such a dataset implies that we need to find some information source that keeps track of GitHub project status, and ideally decides its success. The search has resulted in us exploring the Apache Incubator¹. Apache incubator is a gateway for promising open-source projects to adopt Apache practices. As a result, Apache staff keep track of each project’s status and have experts periodically reevaluate it. The list of participating projects and their statuses is publicly available. Every project is assigned one of the following statuses:

- 1) Incubating - the project is not mature enough to have its status decided;
- 2) Retired - the project has been abandoned by developers or was deemed neglected by the experts;
- 3) Graduated - the project development team has successfully adopted the Apache development practices, and is deemed successful by experts.

Thus, we ignored the “Incubating” projects, and treated “Retired” ones as unsuccessful, while “Graduated” ones as successful.

However, the information presented on the website is not available for download. Additionally, not all listed projects have a link to the corresponding GitHub repository. Consequently, project list maintainers are free to put the link anywhere in the description or avoid providing it altogether. Hence, to collect the necessary data we have to first scrape the website for project names along with their statuses and then find the corresponding GitHub repositories.

Apache aggregates all these repositories in the Apache GitHub organization². Therefore, the scope of our search is reduced to this organization. However, the organization is missing the repositories for a portion of retired projects. In addition, most of the available projects use external bug trackers, meaning that the “issues” sections and the corresponding metrics are missing. After collecting all the projects that have GitHub repositories, we still had to manually review the resulting test dataset. As discovered, the retrieved list of “Graduated” projects contained several mislabeled entries. This supposedly happened because the Apache staff stopped tracking the project status after its graduation.

C. Collected Data

The first goal of this work was to compile test and train datasets of project metrics. For the train dataset, we collected

¹<https://incubator.apache.org/>

²<https://github.com/apache>

Table IV: Information on training and test datasets

Dataset	Number of projects	Number of features in each project
Train	3124	48
Test	228	48

Figure 1: Ratio of retrieved Apache Incubator projects

information for a total of 3124 GitHub repositories. We made publicly available the metrics extracted from the trained dataset for the purpose of reconstruction and verification of our research process³. For the test dataset, we managed to collect information about 228 out of 299 projects currently listed on the Apache Incubator website. This data is also publicly available⁴. Table IV shows the number of calculated metrics for each project. The additional information on what projects we failed to retrieve can be seen in Figure 1.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first aspect of the project that we wish to investigate pertains to releases. GitHub provides developers with the option of creating two types of releases, one comprising solely source code, and the other containing source code as well as binaries. However, developers can also choose to refrain from creating releases altogether. Information concerning releases for the train dataset is presented in Figure 2, while comparable information for the test dataset can be observed in Figure 3.

Subsequently, we seek to compare the value ranges of several project metrics between the two datasets using box plots. Our focus lies specifically on project size metrics

³<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1FjMynxFaNpOHonn-YPI9iaFgL8WmU0pC0X3ZE1y1qzA/>

⁴https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1yZ3B7Fu9DAwIBswkHWkf_RCQX9uEMlwd/

Figure 2: Train dataset project releases

Figure 3: Test dataset project releases

Figure 4: Repositories size distributions

and the metrics used in the inclusion criteria, namely, the number of contributors, the number of forks, and project age. Comparisons of the datasets in Figure 4 and Figure 5 reveal that the test dataset comprises more mature projects. This observation is expected, as Apache enforces its own development methodologies on the incubated projects. The evidence is further supported by the data in Figure 6 and Figure 7.

Lastly, we present statistical descriptions for a few selected project metrics in Table V and Table VI.

A. Clustering

We calculated correlation coefficients for all metric pairs. As a result, expanded the groups of metrics associated with different project aspects. The newly compiled list can be seen in Table VII.

As shown in Table VII, there are a total of 14 possible metrics, and running DBSCAN on all subsets of these metrics is a combinatorial problem. Notably, the most of the presented metrics have correlation with success-related metrics and we

Figure 5: Repositories age distributions

Figure 6: Repositories fork distributions

Figure 7: Repositories contributors distributions

Table V: Statistical description of the train dataset

Metric	mean	std	25%	50%	75%
Folders	169.72	1544.66	7	24	86
Files	796.37	7088.41	25	79	301.75
Age (days)	2607.54	970.88	1945.5	2611	3265
Size (Kb)	38672.77	190163.2	300	1760	12286.75
Watchers	140.97	459.81	9	19	68
Contributors	44.84	79.96	4	13	41
Commits	1684.53	5779.48	2	89	280
Forks	766.59	3176.35	13	40.5	290.25
Pulls	433.8	1602.62	8	52	247.5
Stars	3528.47	11464.23	110	299	1172.5
Issues	473.54	1731.56	6	32	215

Table VI: Statistical description of the test dataset

Metric	mean	std	25%	50%	75%
Folders	1146.65	2125.58	209.75	515.5	1294
Files	3631.12	7625.13	657	1814.5	3764.75
Age (days)	3057.65	1006.82	2362	2955.5	3828.75
Size (Kb)	133510.7	486690	12171.25	38750.5	126864.8
Watchers	136.64	331.54	18	33.5	101.25
Contributors	77.28	102.48	12	30	104
Commits	5935.43	8191.46	1153	2810	7101
Forks	953.34	3005.25	42.75	115	600
Pulls	1341.32	3531.77	25.75	178.5	952.5
Stars	2057.36	5801.09	56.75	169	1205.5
Issues	323.21	1354.78	0	0	0

Table VII: Extended list of project aspects and corresponding metrics

Aspect	Metrics
Size	Files, Folders, Size in KB, Contributors Average participation weeks
Success	Stars, Forks, Watchers, Pull Requests, Contributors, Number of Comments in Issues and Pull Requests
Pulse	Active commits, Active pull-requests, Active issues, Active stars

Figure 8: Subsets with relatively high performance measures

can use them to identify project success. To quantify performance, we will mainly rely on the F1-score and specificity. Specificity has been included to improve understanding of how the classifier identifies unsuccessful projects.

The subsets in Table VIII have the lowest specificity values. Low specificity indicates that the cluster of unsuccessful projects fails to represent the underlying concept. This is expected because almost all included metrics are related to either the size or the activity project aspects. The F1-score is rather high because it does not account for negative results. In our case, almost no projects are classified as unsuccessful, resulting in few false negatives and true negatives. The same is true for entries in Table IX.

Several selected subsets that have resulted in the best performance measures (by F1-Score and specificity) are given in Table X. It is notable that DBSCAN is able to procure reasonable results even if only two metrics – watchers and active issues – are used in its feature space. The listed subsets are the ones that either have the best overall performance measures or are the best among the subsets of the specified size. As can be seen, all subsets utilize metrics related to multiple project aspects.

We also investigated how many subsets with relatively good results are present among the subsets of all sizes. For our test dataset we considered that a subset produces good results if its specificity measure exceeds 72% and its F1-score is higher than 81%. The resulting bar chart can be seen in Figure 8. As we expected, the higher numbers of metrics included in the feature space results in better performance. Additionally, the number of repositories in the cluster of unsuccessful projects, increases with the number of included metrics.

B. Differences Between Success Groups

In this study, we aim to examine significant differences in project metric values between successful and unsuccessful projects, and compare these values using side-by-side box plots based on the project group for both the test and a certain clustering of the train dataset.

This paragraph explores the values of metrics that directly reflect project success. As hypothesized, our analysis indicates that successful projects have higher success metric values. This

Table VIII: Subsets that represent success the worst by specificity

List of metrics	F1-score	Accuracy	Specificity	Recall	Precision
Folders	51.55	68.85	0	98.75	69.4
Active Pull Requests, Contributors Average participation weeks	81.25	68.42	0	98.11	69.33
Files, Contributors	80.93	67.98	0	97.46	69.19
Contributors Average Participation Weeks, Contributors, Active Commits	81.25	68.42	0	98.11	69.33
Active Pull Requests	77.29	63.15	1.44	89.73	67.77
Files, Folders, Pull Requests	74.3	59.64	4.34	83.64	66.83
Size in Kb, Contributors	57.87	42.54	10.14	56.6	59.21

Table IX: Subsets that represent success the worst by F1-score

List of metrics	F1-score	Accuracy	Specificity	Recall	Precision
Files, Contributors, Contributors Average participation weeks	51.36	37.71	15.94	47.16	56.39
Files, Contributors Average participation weeks	52.7	38.56	14.49	49.05	56.93
Folders, Contributors Average participation weeks, Active Stars	55.73	40.78	11.59	53.45	58.21
Files, Size, Contributors	55.92	41.22	13.04	53.45	58.62
Active Stars, Total Comments, Contributors Average participation weeks	54.74	41.22	18.84	50.94	59.14
Size, Contributors	57.87	42.54	10.14	56.6	59.21
Total Comments, Active Stars	56.94	44.29	24.63	52.83	61.74

Table X: Subsets that represent success the best

List of metrics	# of metrics	F1-score	Accuracy	Specificity	Recall	Precision
Files, Size, Contributors Average participation weeks, Total Comments, Pull Requests, Forks, Active Stars, Active Pull Requests, Active Issues	9	82.39	76.75	73.91	77.98	87.32
Files, Size, Pull Requests, Stars, Forks, Active Stars, Active Issues	7	81.6	75.87	73.91	76.72	87.14
Stars, Forks, Active Commits, Active Stars, Active Pulls	5	80.8	75	73.91	75.47	86.95
Files, Folders, Size, Contributors Average participation weeks, Total Comments, Pull Requests, Contributors, Stars, Forks, Watchers, Active Commits, Active Stars, Active Issues	13	80	74.12	73.91	74.21	86.76
Total Comments, Contributors, Active Commits, Active Pull Requests	4	80	74.12	73.91	74.21	86.76
Files, Forks, Watchers	3	80.53	74.56	72.46	75.47	86.33
Files, Contributors, Watchers	3	80.13	74.12	72.46	74.84	86.23
Contributors Average participation weeks, Contributors, Active Stars	3	80.53	74.56	72.46	75.47	86.33
Watchers, Active Issues	2	81.45	75.43	71.01	77.35	86.01

Figure 9: Comparison of successful and unsuccessful projects by stars

Figure 10: Comparison of successful and unsuccessful projects by forks

trend is evident in both train and test datasets, particularly for the following metrics: stars in Figure 9, forks in Figure 10, watchers in Figure 11, and the total number of comments on pull requests and issues in Figure 12.

VII. CONCLUSION

The goals of this study were successfully achieved. First, we identified existing project metrics, analyzed the correlations between them, and selected a subset of metrics that were associated with success and minimized selection bias. To accomplish our second objective, we collected train and test datasets. The train dataset was obtained through Google and

Figure 11: Comparison of successful and unsuccessful projects by watchers

Figure 12: Comparison of successful and unsuccessful projects by issue and pull requests comments

GitHub searches, while the test dataset was scraped from the Apache Incubator website. We then applied the DBSCAN clustering algorithm to the train dataset, using various combinations of selected metrics, and evaluated the performance of the resulting clusters calculating the Cartesian distances between the test set points and the centroids of the clusters.

The results of the suggested classification model were satisfactory, but there is room for improvement. To increase the reliability of the results, we suggest collecting a larger train dataset or cross-checking the results on other datasets. Additionally, using more sophisticated classifiers, such as decision trees, could provide more interpretable results by identifying specific thresholds of the project metrics.

In comparison to previous studies on the identification of successful GitHub projects [10], [46], our work stands out by using a more consistent approach of project clustering based on specific success criteria. Our results contribute to the body of literature on this topic and demonstrate the adaptability of our workflow to other project hosting websites such as Source Forge⁵ or GitLab⁶.

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Evolutionary Computation-based Assessment Model for Human-Machine Co-Learning on Taiwanese and English Language between Taiwan and Japan

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Abstract—This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of a Meta AI tool using a human-machine co-learning model for practicing and learning Taiwanese and English languages between Taiwan and Japan. Teachers and students from both countries followed a six-step human-machine co-learning model that integrated both the human and machine co-learning process in the Taiwanese and English languages to conduct the study. We assessed the performance of both human intelligence and machine intelligence in Taiwanese language practice using the sentence BERT similarity approach, to measure how similar the source sentences were to the Meta AI tool-generated sentences. Human experts then extracted important features of the source sentences to construct a knowledge model, and we employed the proposed evolutionary computation-based assessment model to analyze the similarity in learning effectiveness between human and machine evaluations. Our findings indicate that the Meta AI tool has a positive impact on language practice and learning, and the human-machine co-learning model will be an effective approach for Taiwanese and English language learning between Taiwan and Japan in the future.

Keywords—Evolutionary Computation, Human and Machine Co-Learning Model, Taiwanese-English Language Co-Learning, Meta AI Tool, Human Intelligence, Open AI ChatGPT, Sentence BERT Agent

I. INTRODUCTION

In this study, an Evolutionary Computation (EC) model was developed to assess the effectiveness of a Meta AI tool for co-learning Taiwanese and English languages [1], and to evaluate the performance of both human intelligence (HI) and machine intelligence (MI) with computational intelligence (CI) in the learning process. A six-step process was employed during the stage of data preparation and collection to practice and study the basic concepts of CI for young students. This process integrates a human and machine co-learning model, which is depicted in Fig. 1 and described as follows:

1) **Observation and participation in CI learning activities:** The teacher observes the abilities of the learners, prepares corresponding CI teaching content, and goes to the learning site. 2) **Learning and researching CI knowledge:** In the learning field, the teacher and the learners experience CI conceptual learning together and conduct in-depth research on the corresponding CI content. 3) **Utilizing and following CI learning tools:** After CI learning, the learners can utilize and follow them for CI experiential learning. 4) **Understanding and**

knowing the application of CI: After CI experiential learning, learners understand and know the principles of CI and can carry out CI practical and operational learning. 5) **Explaining and speaking CI knowledge concepts:** Learners can explain and speak the CI learning content to other learners for CI expression-based learning. 6) **Applying CI knowledge to solve real-world problems:** Learners can use the learned CI knowledge to solve practical problems and constantly improve and optimize the CI learning process [2]. Through observation, learning, experience, and application, learners can effectively express and utilize their knowledge and skills for practical problem-solving based on the studied computational intelligence knowledge.

Fig. 1. Human-machine co-learning model for Taiwanese and English language practice and learning.

We extracted important features from the data collection to construct an EC-based model for assessing the performance of both HI and MI. Participant performance is evaluated by humans based on the number of key concepts translated by a CI&AI-FML human and machine co-learning agent, which is integrated with the Meta AI Speech-to-speech translation tool [1]. Meanwhile, the machine evaluates their performance based on the similarity of translated sentences to standard sentences, which is implemented by the Sentence-BERT (SBERT) agent [3]. The EC model we constructed assesses the performance of both HI and MI based on the extracted features from the collected data.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II briefly introduces the methodology of the Taiwanese and English language co-learning with the CI&AI-FML human and machine co-learning agent and the SBERT agent. Additionally, Section II describes the EC-based assessment model. Finally, the discussion and future work are presented in Section III.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Structure of Language Co-Learning with CI&AI-FML Human and Machine Co-learning Agent and SBERT Agent

Fig. 2 describes a three-stage research design that includes the participants, procedures, and materials used in the study to understand clearly the interaction in the proposed framework. This video (<https://youtu.be/dMarvERmgII>) demonstrates a scene from our research project where participants read the short story in either Taiwanese or English and interact with the machine to co-learn together. The stages are as follows:

1) **Stage I: Learning data preparation:** Initially, a human designer creates a short story consisting of 5 to 10 sentences using Chinese or Taiwanese daily life vocabulary as the basis for the ground truth. The story is then translated into English using the OpenAI tool, ChatGPT, to create the English ground truth.

2) **Stage II: Learning data collection:** The Meta AI tool is integrated into the developed CI&AI-FML (Artificial Intelligence-Fuzzy Markup Language) human and machine co-learning agent to provide speech-to-speech translation between Taiwanese and English. Participants read the short story in either Taiwanese or English, and Meta AI Tool translates it into speeches in English and Taiwanese, as well as texts in English and Chinese. The source of the speeches and the output of speeches and texts are all stored.

3) **Stage III: Learning data analysis:** The evaluation of participant performance by humans is based on the number of key concepts translated by Meta AI tools compared to the ground truth. Meanwhile, the machine analyzes the similarity between the translated texts and the ground truth using the Sentence-BERT (SBERT) agent. The results evaluated by humans are stored in the HI repository, while those evaluated by machines are stored in the MI repository.

Fig. 2. Structure of Taiwanese and English language co-learning with CI&AI-FML human and machine co-learning agent and SBERT agent.

B. Evolutionary Computation-based Assessment Model

In this section, the construction of an EC-based assessment model and its connection to a six-step human and machine co-learning model are described. Fig. 3 illustrates the EC-based assessment model construction and its link to the six-step human

and machine co-learning model. The model's performance is assessed using three input features, namely *the level of learner participation, the level of learner tool utilization, and the extent to which the learner follows the learned knowledge*, which is extracted from Steps 1, 4, and 5, respectively. The objective is to predict the effectiveness of the learner's speaking proficiency extracted from Step 6. The target data may include results evaluated by both humans and machines, which can be used to validate the performance of both. Using the collected data, we construct the knowledge base (KB) and rule base (RB) of the model. We then optimize its parameters using EC-based methods, such as GA-based fuzzy markup language (GFML), PSO-based fuzzy markup language (PFML), and Genetic Algorithm Neural Network (GANN) methods.

Fig. 3. EC-based assessment model construction linking the six-step human and machine co-learning.

III. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

The objective of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of learning Taiwanese and English languages using a human-machine co-learning approach. The initial experiment was conducted in Taiwan and Japan from Dec. 2022 to Feb. 2023, with a total of 117 participants, including 43 involved in Taiwanese language practice and learning, and 74 involved in English practice and learning. The participants in this experiment were from Taiwan, Japan, China, and Malaysia. Fig. 4 shows their language level in Taiwanese and English, including *below-basic, basic, proficient, and advanced*. Additionally, we designed seven short stories in Taiwanese and English languages for the participants to read, consisting of 534 and 739 sentences, respectively.

Fig. 4. Participants' language level of Taiwanese and English.

Fig. 5 compares the results of the average sentence similarity, evaluated by humans and machines, as well as the accuracy of the machine. In this experiment, four speakers from Taiwan (TW 1 to TW 4), three speakers from Japan (JP 1 to JP 3), and two speakers from China (CN 1 and CN 2) spoke short and simple Taiwanese daily life vocabulary. The results indicate that: 1) The machine’s accuracy can reach 0.6, except for JP 2. 2) There is a large difference between the averages evaluated by humans and machines for JP 2 and JP 3. 3) People with a below-basic level of Taiwanese can achieve good performance after co-learning with the machine, as seen in TW 4, JP 1, CN 1, CN 2, and JP 3. 4) The accuracy of JP 3 reaches 1.

Fig. 5. Average sentence similarity evaluated by humans and machines and the accuracy of the machine.

Moreover, we found that JP 1, a junior high school student, was able to speak certain specific Taiwanese daily life vocabulary, such as 洗衣褲 (laundry pants), 腳踏車 (bicycle), 讀書 (study), 真有趣 (really interesting), and 可愛 (cute), well enough for the machine to understand after trying about three times with the necessary guidance from CN 1, who is proficient in Japanese and advanced in Chinese. This guidance includes providing the Romanization of Taiwanese. JP 1 was very happy and gave applause when the machine translated her Taiwanese into English and spoke translated English correctly, indicating her good performance. However, we found this sentence 老師

和機器人讀書 (The teacher and the robot are studying) is still difficult for her to read, especially the Taiwanese pronunciation of 機器人 (robot).

The experimental results indicate that the human and machine co-learning model has a positive impact on language learning. In the future, we plan to implement this approach using EC-based methods and quantum fuzzy inference engines to validate the performance of humans and machines. By doing so, we will gain a deeper understanding of the potential of combining our developed systems with AI tools such as Meta AI S2ST, OpenAI ChatGPT, and machine translators in human-machine co-learning for language learning.

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Nature-Inspired Techniques for Dynamic Constraint Satisfaction Problems

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Abstract—One of the main challenges when designing a constraint-based system is the ability to deal with constraints in a dynamic and evolutive environment. Given the combinatorial nature of the problems tackled, an efficient solving approach is needed, especially in the case of time-critical applications. That is to check the consistency of the current solution anytime new constraints are added, and if not, find a new scenario satisfying the old and new constraints. In this context, we proposed a new method based on nature-inspired techniques for solving constraint problems in a dynamic environment. Indeed, nature-inspired techniques are best suited for these types of applications given their iterative solving process.

Index Terms—Constraint Satisfaction Problem (CSP), Dynamic Constraints, Nature-Inspired Techniques, Metaheuristics

I. INTRODUCTION

Many real-world applications, such as resource allocation [1], vehicle routing [2], configuration [3], scheduling [4], and planning [5], often operate under highly dynamic environments. While several solving methods and tools have been developed to tackle these applications, they often work under idealized assumptions of environmental stability. One main challenge is maintaining a consistent solution anytime new constraints are added. To address this challenge efficiently, we propose a methodology relying on population-based nature-inspired techniques [6], [7], given their iterative capability to maintain a set of promising solutions at each iteration. More precisely, our proposed procedure solves the original constraint problem and saves the related context (population) produced to obtain the first consistent solution. This saved context will then be used as a resume point for incrementally finding new solutions anytime new constraints are added. Indeed, once a solution is found, we resume from the current state to search for a new one when new constraints are added. In this context, solving a dynamic constraint problem can be seen as an optimization problem where we look for a new feasible solution satisfying the old and new constraints while minimizing the differences with the solution of the previous problem instance in sequence. The latter objective ensures finding the least disruptive solution [8]. Following our proposed methodology, we developed the dynamic variant of several nature-inspired techniques [9]–[14]. We model constraint problems using the well-known constraint satisfaction problem (CSP) paradigm [15]. Constraint additions in a dynamic environment can then

be expressed as a series of static CSPs, each resulting from a change in the previous one by adding new constraints [16]. To assess the performance of our proposed methodology, we conducted several experiments on randomly generated dynamic CSP instances. The results of the experiments are reported and discussed. This work has been published in [17].

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Fake News Identification Using Artificial Immune Systems

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Abstract—The dissemination of fake news through unreliable media can have severe negative consequences on national security and society, making it a significant issue in modern society. Although there has been an increase in awareness of fake news since the 2016 US presidential election, effectively detecting and preventing its rapid spread online remains a challenge. This work investigates the feasibility of identifying fake news on social media by combining Artificial Immune Systems and Genetic Algorithms. To identify fake news online, the proposed approach employs a Genetic Algorithm-based detector optimization scheme for the Negative Selection Algorithm, a vital component of Artificial Immune Systems. The experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of the Genetic Algorithm-based optimization scheme for generating the Negative Selection Algorithm detector in identifying fake news articles online.

Index Terms—artificial immune systems, fake news, negative selection algorithm, self/nonself recognition, pattern detector

I. INTRODUCTION

The advancement and easy access to the internet and technology have revolutionized news platforms. Social media and micro-blogging platforms have become the primary news source for many people, replacing traditional media channels like newspapers and television. According to a study, approximately two-thirds of Americans now access news through social media [1]. While social networks are helpful during crisis situations, there needs to be more control and fact-checking over posts. With millions of articles published every minute, manually checking them is not feasible. This absence of control or fact-checking makes social media a breeding ground for spreading unverified news, rumours or fake news at a fast pace and with little to no cost [2]. This can seriously affect society, commerce, national security, and democracy worldwide. For instance, when a fake news report about former US President Barack Obama being injured in an explosion was circulated, it triggered a US \$130 billion loss in the stock

market [3]. Consequently, there has been a growing interest in the automatic detection of fake news in social media and online platforms in recent years.

The majority of works in the literature have formulated fake news detection as either a classification or anomaly detection problem. A comprehensive survey is available in [4]–[7]. The existing approaches can be broadly categorized into four groups: natural language processing, data mining, social network analysis, and machine/deep learning. Among these approaches, machine/deep learning techniques have shown promising results [5]. Traditional machine/deep learning algorithms utilized for fake news detection include Support Vector Machines [8], Decision Trees [9], Random Forests [4], k-Nearest Neighbors [10], Naïve Bayes Classifiers [11], Convolutional Neural Networks [3], Recurrent Neural Networks [3], and Long Short-Term Memory [11]. Over the past few years, bio-inspired algorithms modeled after the principles of biological evolution have led to new and effective techniques for similar classification and detection tasks in various domains [12]–[14]. Inspired by the success, this work explores the potential of utilizing a hybrid approach combining two bio-inspired algorithms, Artificial Immune Systems (AISs) and Genetic Algorithms (GAs), to detect fake news articles online.

In recent years, AIS has emerged as a newer computational paradigm based on principles derived from the Biological Immune System (BIS) [15]. The BIS is a robust, highly parallel, distributed, self-organize, and adaptive system that defends our body from foreign pathogens by distinguishing between *self* (body cells) and *nonself* (foreign materials/pathogen). It uses learning, memory, and associative retrieval to solve recognition and classification tasks. By employing similar sophisticated pattern recognition and response mechanisms against foreign invaders as the BIS, AIS has been successfully applied to practical pattern recognition and anomaly detection tasks [16]–[19]. Accordingly, AIS provides an attractive option for improving the classification performance of fake news articles

by utilizing the *self/nonself* distinction. GAs, on the other hand, are search and optimization heuristics inspired by natural selection, where the strongest individuals are selected for reproduction to produce the next generation of offspring [20].

One of the BIS's most intriguing and adaptive immunological mechanisms is *self/nonself recognition*. It allows the BIS to identify cells that belong to its own body (*self/safe*) from the foreign cells (*nonself*). The *nonself* cells that BIS recognizes could be harmful cells originating from the body (such as cancer and tumour cells) or foreign agents causing diseases (such as viruses and bacteria). This recognition enables BIS to develop a defence mechanism against these attackers without harming its own cells. Based on the principle of *self/nonself* recognition, researchers advanced the AIS design by introducing the Negative Selection Algorithm (NSA) [21], [22]. This algorithm has already demonstrated its effectiveness in detecting anomalies [23], [24].

In brief, NSA involves creating a set of memory detectors through negative selection. Initially, immature detectors that match a self pattern are removed, and the ones that survive the negative selection process become mature detectors for *nonself* pattern. Then, a positive selection process is used for *nonself*-matching. Any sample pattern that matches a mature detector is identified as *nonself* and saved as a memory detector for future use. However, the original NSA randomly generates detectors in the first phase, which may not cover the *nonself* space and have overlaps [23]. To address this issue, various detector types and generation schemes have been proposed, but they tend to be computationally expensive. Inspired by the concept presented in [25], this work proposes a simple GA-based optimization scheme for NSA detectors to identify fake news articles online. Experimental results demonstrate the superiority of the GA-based approach over conventional detector generation methods and highlight its efficiency in detecting fake news.

The structure of the paper is as follows: Section II provides information regarding NSA as a background, followed by Section III, which discusses the proposed GA-based NSA model. Section IV presents the experimental outcomes, and Section V concludes the paper with points to future works.

II. NEGATIVE SELECTION ALGORITHM

The initial proposal by Forrest et al. [21] was for the Negative Selection Algorithm (NSA) to imitate the BIS's mechanism of T cell maturation, specifically through the negative selection of T cells in the thymus. From the information processing viewpoint, NSA offers a different approach for pattern recognition where information about the *nonself* set (in our case, fake news) is stored to recognize self set (in our case, authentic news). This approach can be described conceptually in two phases, as shown in Fig. 1.

Assuming an adequate problem representation is available:

- 1) The initial step involves identifying the set of patterns to be protected (*self*) and gathering a dataset comprising all the representative self samples. Afterwards, candidate detectors that adhere to the same representation are

Fig. 1: The Negative Selection Algorithm (NSA) process.

generated randomly and compared with the self set to determine if any matches occur. If a match is found, signifying that a randomly generated detector has been recognized by a self sample, it is discarded. Comparable to the negative selection of T cells, only those randomly generated detectors that are not matched with any element of the self set are saved as *mature detectors* in the mature detector set.

- 2) The algorithm in the second phase observes the system in use for the existence of *nonself* patterns. It evaluates the matching (*affinity*) level between the sample pattern and all components of the mature detector set comprising *nonself* patterns. The sample pattern is recognized as a *nonself* pattern whenever the matching level exceeds a specified threshold value. Eventually, appropriate action is initiated.

The effectiveness of *nonself* pattern recognition by the NSA detectors relies on two critical factors [26]: the extent of *nonself* space coverage and the level of overlap among existing detectors. As a result, the ideal detectors should cover the maximum *nonself* space and have minimal overlapping among each other. Typically, conventional NSA generates detectors through a random search, which results in an exhaustive and time-consuming trial-and-error process [27]. Furthermore, detectors generated through random search cannot be guaranteed to be optimal [25]. This work utilizes GA to optimize NSA detectors to achieve the best possible anomaly detection performance in the case of fake news identification.

III. THE PROPOSED MODEL

The main concept involves creating a set of mature detectors that encompass the entire negative space. The initial step consists in gathering samples labeled as “True” in the dataset (explained in Section IV) and using them as self patterns to define the positive space. Fig. 2 illustrates this, which depicts a two-dimensional example from [25]. In the figure, the black circles correspond to the self patterns and are centered around specific sample data points with a specific radius. Dotted circles represent the *nonself* patterns (detectors), each with a different radius. It is worth noting that the dimensions of the search space (for example, two in Fig. 2) will vary depending on the number of features in the problem domain. The primary aim is to generate the maximum number of mature detectors, each centered around a detector with a varying radius. The goal is to optimize two objectives: maximizing the coverage

by these detectors (negative/nonsel self space) and minimizing the overlaps among themselves. This ensures that any incoming nonself pattern, such as fake news in this work, is detected by at least one mature detector (i.e., lies within a dotted circle). However, similar to [25], this work employs a single objective GA, which mainly minimizes the overlapping among the detectors to cover the maximum negative space.

Fig. 2: Positive and negative detectors in NSA [25].

Assume that N self samples contain L features and are centered around $S_i = [x_1^i, x_2^i, \dots, x_L^i]$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$), with radii R_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$) defining their self-regions. The aim is to generate M mature detectors with centers $md_i = [w_1^i, w_2^i, \dots, w_L^i]$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, M$) and radii r_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, M$) so that the optimized detectors can cover the maximum nonself space without overlap. Specifically, for each detector j , we determine S_k as the center of its nearest self sample k :

$$|S_k - md_j| = \min_j^N |S_i - md_j| \quad (1)$$

Where $|S_k - md_j|$ and $|S_i - md_j|$ are Euclidean distances. If there is a self-sample i , such that $|S_i - md_j| \leq R_i$, the detector md_j becomes invalid since it overlaps with the self sample. To ensure that the detectors have the maximum radius r without any overlap with the N self samples, the radius of detector j , r_j , is chosen as follows:

$$r_j = |S_k - md_j| - R_k \quad (2)$$

Thus, we aim to search for the optimal md_j that offers the largest r_j to cover the nonself space. Accordingly, radius of the detector is the fitness of the GA, and larger valid radii detectors are given higher fitness for evolution in the GA (as shown in (2)). In our implementation, each run of the GA optimization loop results in only one optimal detector. In each successive iteration of the GA, the most recent best detector is added to the set of previously discovered best detectors and verified for its validity (i.e., whether it lies within the radii of the other detectors). If valid, it is added to the mature detector set; otherwise, it is ignored. To ensure that the detectors do not overlap, the optimal detector obtained in one iteration is considered a “new” self sample and included in the “varying” self sample set. It is important to note that after adding the best detector, the radii of the other detectors may change, so they must be recalculated. As per (1), the final set of mature detectors generated in this approach does not overlap and provide the maximum coverage of the nonself space.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

To evaluate the proposed GA-based NSA model, a publicly available dataset was utilized, which was compiled by Ahmed, Traore, and Saad [28]. The dataset comprises 12600 authentic articles and 12600 fake news articles, all obtained from real-world sources. The authentic articles were gathered from Reuters.com, a news agency website. In contrast, the fake news articles were sourced from a dataset available on kaggle.com containing articles from unreliable websites marked as such by Politifact, a fact-checking organization based in the USA. Each article in the dataset is described by five features: article text, article type, article title, article date, and article label indicating whether the article is fake or authentic.

The dataset was divided into training and testing sets using 5-fold cross-validation. In each validation cycle, 75% of the data was utilized for training, while the remaining 25% was used for testing purposes. We employed 25 detectors initially with a radius size of 2 for GA-based NSA. The GA had a population size of 30 and ran for 20 generations, with crossover and mutation probabilities of 0.7 and 0.3, respectively. For the random generating scenario, we also utilized 25 detectors with a threshold value of 1.

Fig. 3: Search space with self samples and generated detectors.

Fig. 3 presents the detectors generated by GA-based NSA (Fig. 3a) and NSA with a random strategy (Fig. 3b). To enhance their visualization, the detectors are presented in two dimensions and represented by black circles for self patterns and coloured circles for detectors. The figures demonstrate that GA-based NSA generates mature detectors with significantly less overlap than those generated by the NSA with a random generating strategy. While the mature detector set obtained by GA-based NSA (Fig. 3a) does not cover the complete negative space, it covers more negative space compared to the mature set generated by the random strategy (Fig. 3b). It is important to note that the GA-based NSA in this work had a single objective: minimizing overlap among mature detectors. Having taken this into account, the results obtained are highly promising.

TABLE I: Performance Comparison In Detecting Fake News

Model	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy
GA-based NSA	94.11%	100%	96.96%	98%
NSA (random)	45.65%	87.5%	60%	44%

Table I presents the classification accuracy achieved by the two approaches in detecting fake news articles, serving as evidence of the effectiveness of the proposed approach. The results clearly indicate that GA-based NSA outperforms NSA with a random strategy across all accuracy measures considered. The precision and recall values obtained by GA-based NSA are substantially higher at 94.11% and 100%, respectively. These findings demonstrate that GA-based NSA can almost perfectly distinguish between “True” and “Fake” news samples, with minimal risk of misprediction. The high level of accuracy (98%) achieved by the proposed approach supports its ability to predict and classify the majority of new samples accurately. The high F1 score (96.96%) obtained by the GA-based NSA further demonstrates its capacity to achieve high precision and recall for a significant proportion of unknown samples. Furthermore, this validates the effectiveness of the proposed approach when dealing with “real” fake news.

V. CONCLUSION

One of the primary challenges in identifying fake news is distinguishing it from trustworthy news. AIS-based techniques have demonstrated impressive performance in classification, pattern recognition, and anomaly detection applications. Building on this success, this work proposes a GA-based NSA, modeled after the BIS’s self/nonself recognition, to identify online fake news articles. The experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of this approach in accurately identifying and classifying news articles. The proposed approach generates mature detectors that exhibit minimal overlap among themselves. However, as a single-objective GA was employed to optimize the detectors, the mature detectors could not fully cover the negative space. Future research aims to use a multi-objective GA to maximize negative space coverage and minimize overlapping among detectors simultaneously. Ultimately, the goal is to develop an integrated online news identification system that automatically generates training data for identifying fake news on social media. Advancements in generative modeling, such as Generative Adversarial Networks, may help achieve this objective.

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An Evolutionary Ensemble Learning Method for Endpoint Quality Prediction in Steelmaking Process

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Abstract—To improve the quality of molten steel in steelmaking process, predicting the quality of chemical component in advance can provide accurate guidance for quality control, effectively reducing production risks and labor costs, and greatly improving production efficiency. This article briefly introduces the background of steelmaking process and the principle of XGBoost. A prediction model based on XGBoost is built, and then the differential evolution (DE) algorithm is used to optimize the parameters of the XGBoost model to improve its performance. Experimental results show that the XGBoost model with DE has better performance for the endpoint quality prediction in steelmaking process and can meet actual production demand.

Keywords—quality prediction; steelmaking process; data analytics; XGBoost; differential evolution algorithm;

I. INTRODUCTION

Basic oxygen furnace (BOF) is an important process in the iron and steel production [1-3]. Its main purpose is to smelt molten iron into high-quality molten steel, as shown in Fig. 1. The smelting process directly affects the type and quality of steel. Due to the characteristics of high temperature, complex physical and chemical reactions, and high energy consumption in the steelmaking process, the smelting state information in the furnace cannot be obtained in real time. The entire smelting process presents a dynamic black-box characteristic, which causes the mechanism model to be unclear or difficult to accurately establish, and the process brings great challenges to the recognition, control, and optimization of steelmaking process.

In view of this problem, combined with actual production data, effective modeling and solving of the smelting process through data analytics methods has enriched the theoretical research of smart steelmaking, and has important practical significance for ensuring safe production and improving product quality, and provides references for other process industries with black-box problems [4-5].

II. THE PROPOSED METHOD

In this article, the principle of XGBoost is first introduced, an efficient gradient boosting decision tree algorithm widely used in various machine learning tasks. By using the XGBoost algorithm to establish a prediction model, we can obtain accurate prediction results and the importance ranking of influencing factors, providing strong support for subsequent decision-making. Subsequently, differential evolution (DE) algorithm is used to optimize the parameters of the XGBoost model to improve its performance.

A. XGBoost

XGBoost [6] is a machine learning method based on gradient boosting, which is a type of ensemble learning algorithm that combines decision tree algorithms with gradient boosting algorithms. XGBoost is an implementation of the gradient boosting machine algorithm that uses CPU multi-threading for parallel computing, making it highly accurate and scalable. The algorithm is composed of two parts: the decision tree algorithm and the gradient boosting algorithm.

The decision tree algorithm is a classic algorithm in machine learning that can be used to solve classification and regression problems [7]. The algorithm creates a binary tree

Fig. 1 The reaction process of BOF steelmaking.

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structure starting from the root node, based on a judgment criterion, dividing the root node into two nodes, and recursively splitting each node in the same way until some condition is met. The creation of a decision tree involves three main steps: splitting feature and node selection, tree generation, and tree pruning. This method has the advantages of high interpretability and fast modeling speed.

B. Differential Evolution (DE)

Differential evolution algorithm is an optimization algorithm based on swarm intelligence theory [8-10]. It is an intelligent optimization search algorithm generated by cooperation and competition between individuals in a swarm. But compared with evolutionary computing, it retains the global search strategy based on population, and uses real number coding, simple mutation operation based on difference and “one to one” competitive survival strategy, which reduces the complexity of evolutionary computing operation. At the same time, the unique memory ability of differential evolution algorithm enables it to dynamically track the current search situation to adjust its search strategy. It has strong global convergence and robustness, and does not need to rely on the characteristic information of the problem. It is suitable for solving some complex optimization problems which are difficult or even impossible to be solved by conventional mathematical programming methods. Therefore, differential evolution algorithm is an efficient parallel search algorithm, so it is of great academic significance and engineering value to study its theory and application.

Since DE is a simple and effective global optimization algorithm for continuous search domain, this article adopts DE algorithm to optimize model parameters. The main steps of DE refer to the initialization of population, evaluation of the objective function, and the operations of mutation, crossover, selection. Among that, the optimized objective function of DE is expressed as follows:

$$F(\mathbf{z}) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - f(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{z}))^2} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{x} is the input sample, and y is the output sample, and N is the number of samples. $f(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{z})$ is the output of XGBoost as the predictive value, and \mathbf{z} is the optimized parameters including the maximum depth of each decision tree, the learning rate, the maximum number of iterations required for the ensemble stage of model boosting, the subsample parameter can be understood as the number of base learners required for model training, and the gamma parameter specifies the minimum loss function reduction value required for node splitting. The aim of optimization is to minimize $F(\mathbf{z})$ to obtain the proper model parameters.

III. EXPERIMENTS

In this section, the effectiveness of the XGBoost is validated for the endpoint quality prediction problems. Based

on the real-world data collected from steelmaking process, we test the performance of XGBoost-DE.

A. Experimental Data

In this article, the total 1310 data are collected from the real iron and steel plant. Where 80% of data are used to train the model, and 20% of data are tested. We have deleted some abnormal data from the obtained data. And then we have also complemented some missing data by the interpolation method.

B. Experimental Settings

The experiments for the XGBoost-DE are developed on a Windows platform with a 3.40 GHz core i7 processor and 16.00 GB of RAM.

C. Experimental Results

The article uses root-mean-square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and coefficient of determination (R^2) as performance evaluation criteria.

To show the effectiveness of the proposed method, XGBoost-DE is compared with XGBoost, as shown in Tables I and II. The results show that the proposed method achieve significant improvements in terms of temperature (T) and carbon content (C). This indicates that differential evolution algorithm has great advantages in dealing with large amounts of data and complex problems, and can improve model performance without increasing computational costs.

TABLE I.

COMPARISON RESULTS BETWEEN XGBOOST-DE AND XGBOOST FOR T

Indicators	XGBoost-DE	XGBoost
RMSE	11.1428	12.4795
MAE	8.8140	9.8532
R^2	0.2351	0.0406

TABLE II.

COMPARISON RESULTS BETWEEN XGBOOST-DE AND XGBOOST FOR C

Indicators	XGBoost-DE	XGBoost
RMSE	0.0173	0.0179
MAE	0.0133	0.0133
R^2	0.2192	0.1569

Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 show the predicted errors for T and C, respectively. The experimental results illustrate that XGBoost-DE has the small predicted errors, which can meet the actual production demand.

Fig. 2 The predicted errors of T.

Fig. 3 The predicted errors of C.

IV. CONCLUSION

This article proposes an improved XGBoost algorithm for solving the endpoint quality prediction problem in steelmaking process. XGBoost with DE is used to establish the prediction model. The experimental results show the proposed method can obtain the high accuracy and solve actual production problems. In the future, we will further study the multi-objective evolutionary learning method to better predict the quality of molten steel in steelmaking process.

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A multi-objective optimization scheduling for multi-energy system in iron and steel enterprise

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Abstract—Iron and steel industry is energy-intensive and faces the challenge of energy efficiency improvement because of the time-varying coupling characteristic of energy consumption and regeneration. This paper investigates the energy consumption and conversion among gas, steam and electricity in iron and steel enterprises, and studied optimization scheduling of this multi-energy system. A multi-objective optimization scheduling model of gas-steam-electric power was established, and an improved differential evolution algorithm based on offspring population species clustering was designed to solve the problem.

Keywords—multi-energy system; multi-objective optimization; differential evolution algorithm

I. INTRODUCTION

Iron and steel enterprises are resource-intensive, energy-intensive, and emission-intensive[1]. Steel production is not only a heavy energy user, but also a huge carbon dioxide emitter[2]. Fully recycling and utilizing surplus gas to reduce energy cost has been one of the ways to improve competitiveness of iron and steel enterprises. Most of the research on energy optimization in iron and steel enterprises focus on a single energy[3]-[5] or single-objective optimization. In this paper, a multi-energy and multi-objective scheduling model is proposed, which considers the coupling relationship among gas, steam and electricity, minimizing the economic operating cost of energy and the degree of deviation from the mid-level of gas holder. The differential evolution algorithm was used to solve the problem, and the infeasible individuals were repaired by reducing the degree of constraint violation[6], [7]. To improve the search ability of the algorithm, the K-means clustering algorithm was used to divide the offspring population in the iterative process, and random variation local search was designed for the offspring population. The performance of the proposed method is demonstrated using real-world data.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION AND FORMULATION

In typical iron and steel manufacturing process, gas is used to burn boilers to produce steam, which drives steam turbines to generate electricity. Energy network fluctuates frequently due to factors such as changes of production operation or maintenance plan. The layout of gas-steam-power system in iron and steel enterprise is shown in Figure 1. The whole system can be divided into gas subsystem, steam subsystem and power subsystem. The supply and demand of gas, steam and electricity in each production cycle need to be dynamically balanced. The buffer users of gas and steam have adjustment capacity, and the gas, steam could be used as power fuel for generating electricity so as to reduce the waste energy and reduce electricity purchase. Therefore, more and more steel and iron enterprises build their own power plants and use the surplus gas to heat boilers to increase the power generation.

Fig. 1 Structure diagram of gas-steam-electricity coupling system in iron and steel enterprises

A. Gas-steam-electricity System Modelling

Objective functions

The multi-energy coupling system in iron and steel enterprises involves complex production processes, various generation, consumption, buffer users and equipment. The purpose of this study is to improve the comprehensive utilization rate of energy, reduce the energy economic operating cost, and ensure production demands of gas and steam for normal production. At the same time, the stable operating of the energy system requires keeping the gas stored in the gas holder near the middle level.

Therefore, the energy economic operation cost target Z1 considered includes gas generation cost C_1 , gas consumption cost C_2 , gas storage cost C_3 , gas release cost C_4 , purchased power cost C_5 :

$$\min Z1 = \min(C_1 + C_2 + C_3 + C_4 + C_5) \quad (1)$$

Where,

$$C_1 = \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{i=1}^I x_{ti5}^u \cdot c g_i \quad (2)$$

$$C_2 = \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{k=1}^K x_{tik}^u \cdot c_i \quad (3)$$

$$C_3 = \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{i=1}^I \{0.5 \cdot (H_{t-1,i} + H_{t,i}) \cdot V_i \cdot c s_i\} \quad (4)$$

$$C_4 = \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{i=1}^I \{c f_i \max\{(g_{ti}^{gen} - \sum_{k=1}^K x_{tik}^u) V_i - H_i^1 V_i, 0\}\} \quad (5)$$

$$C_5 = \sum_{t=1}^T x_t^e \cdot p_t \quad (6)$$

The objective function Z2 represents the value of minimizing the deviation from the mid-level position.

$$\min Z2 = \min \left| H_{t,i} - \frac{H_i^1 - H_i^0}{2} \right| \quad (7)$$

Constraints

1) Power demand constraints

$$x_t^e + \sum_{i=1}^I x_{ti5}^u \cdot \eta_{0,i} + x_{t1}^u \cdot \eta_1 \cdot H^{stm} = D_t^e \quad t \in T, i \in I \quad (8)$$

2) Steam demand constraints

$$\sum_{l=2}^L x_{tl}^u = D_t^s \quad t \in T, l \in L \quad (9)$$

3) Gas balance constraints

$$V_i H_{t-1,i} + g_{ti}^{gen} = \sum_{k=1}^K x_{tik}^u + \max\{g_{ti}^{gen} - \sum_{k=1}^K x_{tik}^u + H_{t,i} V_i + H_{t-1,i} V_i - H_i^1 V_i, 0\} \quad t \in T, i \in I, k \in K \quad (10)$$

4) Gas tank location constraints

$$H_i^0 \leq H_{t,i} \leq H_i^1 \quad t \in T, i \in I \quad (11)$$

5) Steam balance constraints

$$\sum_{j=1}^J s_{tj}^{sen} = \sum_{l=1}^L x_{tl}^u \quad t \in T, j \in J, l \in L \quad (12)$$

6) Gas users limit constraints

$$a_k \leq x_{tik}^u \leq b_k \quad t \in T, i \in I, k \in K \quad (13)$$

7) Steam users limit constraints

$$c_l \leq x_{tl}^u \leq d_l \quad t \in T, l \in L \quad (14)$$

8) Calorific value constraints of gas mixing users

$$e_k \leq \frac{\sum_{i=1}^I x_{tik}^u h_i^{gas}}{\sum_{i=1}^I x_{tik}^u} \leq f_k \quad t \in T, i \in I, k \in K \quad (15)$$

9) Variable value range

$$x_t^e \geq 0; \quad x_{tik}^u \geq 0; \quad x_{tl}^u \geq 0 \quad t \in T, i \in I, k \in K, l \in L \quad (16)$$

III. MODE ALGORITHM BASED ON OFFSPRING SPECIES CLUSTERING

For solving the multi-objective model of multi-energy coupling system, multi-objective differential evolution (MODE) algorithm are improved by K-means clustering and local search strategy to enhance the quality of solutions.

A. Nonviable individual repair

MODE algorithm based on offspring species clustering (K-MODE) defines constraint violation degree $CV(X)$ to evaluate the quality of candidate solutions as follows:

$$CV(X) = \sum_{i=1}^k G_i(X) + \sum_{j=1}^l H_j(X) \quad (17)$$

where,

$$G_i(X) = \begin{cases} g_i(X) & \text{if } (g_i(X) > 0) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

$$H_j(X) = \begin{cases} |h_j(X)| & \text{if } (|h_j(X)| - \varepsilon > 0) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

To increase the number of feasible solutions, the repair strategy of non-feasible individuals is designed. During algorithm iteration, the relationship between different constraints is considered to guide the population to evolve in the direction opposite to the constraint violation. The repair strategy for infeasible individual is designed to deal with equality constraints. Take power demand constraint as an example, given threshold $\varepsilon=0.001$, repair ratio $\varepsilon=0.001$. For the repair ratio $r=0.5$ at time t , do it according to the following steps:

Step 1: The degree of violation of the power demand constraint is calculated when evaluating the quality of the solution ΔD :

$$\Delta D = x_t^e + \sum_{i=1}^I x_{ti5}^u \cdot \eta_{0,i} + x_{t1}^u \cdot \eta_1 \cdot H^{stm} - D_t^e \quad (20)$$

if $|\Delta D| > \varepsilon$, go to Step 2. Otherwise, stop.

Step 2: the repair method of x_t^e is

$$x_t^e = x_t^e - \Delta D \cdot r \quad (21)$$

Step 3: If x_t^e exceeds the upper and lower limits after repair, discard it. Otherwise, retain it.

B. Acceleration strategy

K-means algorithm is an iterative redistribution clustering algorithm based on square error. Firstly, it randomly selects k initial cluster central individuals, calculates the distance from any individual to k cluster central individuals. Then the principle of nearest distance is adopted to assign each individual to the closest cluster center, and the geometric center of each class is used as the reference point of the next iteration.

And, to enhance the search capability of MODE algorithm, a random variation local search strategy is adopted. In this strategy, random variation is carried out for the subpopulation individuals after the clustering of the above progeny species, the dominance relationship between the mutated individuals and the progeny individuals is evaluated, then the dominated individuals in the progeny population are replaced. The local search strategy for the j -th component $x_{i,G}^j$ of the current individual $P_{i,G}$ is defined as follows:

$$x_{i,G}^j = \begin{cases} x_{i,min}^j + (x_{i,max}^j - x_{i,min}^j) \text{rand}(0,1) & \text{if } (\text{rand}(0,1) \leq p) \\ x_{i,G}^j & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

The multi-objective differential evolution algorithm based on clustering technology is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 Flow chart of multi-objective differential evolution algorithm based on offspring population clustering.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

Algorithm parameters were set using the actual data. In order to compare the effect of the improved MODE algorithm, Hypervolume (HV) was selected as the evaluation index[8]. The algorithm was written in Python3.7 language, and MODE and its improved algorithm were written with the help of jMetalPy framework[9].

Figure 3-5 list the scheduling results of steam, power, and gas holders. After meeting the requirements of each process, the steam is distributed to the CDQ equipment for self-electricity as much as possible within the capacity. When electricity cannot meet the production demand, purchase occurs. The gas level is maintained in the middle to reduce the fluctuation of the gas.

Fig. 3 Scheduling result of steam

Fig. 4 Scheduling result of electric

Fig. 5 Scheduling result of gasholder levels

The fluctuation of three gas holders within 5 cycles is shown in Table I. It can be seen from the figure that the three gas holders gradually tend to their respective middle level with the increase of period and the fluctuation degree becomes smaller and smaller, which reflects the optimization results of the algorithm in the objective Z2.

TABLE I OBJECTIVE VALUE IN EACH SCHEDULING PERIOD

Objective \ T	1	2	3	4	5
Z1 (¥)	202265	184282	178685	200829	182148
Z2 (m)	30.04	6.64	11.26	8.28	3.07

The value of the objective of each cycle and the cost component of Z1 are shown in Table II, which shows the results of optimization objectives and provides references for scheduling decisions.

TABLE II SUB-ITEMS OF Z1 IN EACH SCHEDULING PERIOD

Cost \ Period T	1	2	3	4	5
Electricity purchase cost	78064	50933	38180	67617	51031
Release cost	0	0	0	14361	0
Gas storage cost	4002	3907	3309	2969	3213
Gas consumption cost	65940	35434	35207	36403	33981
Gas generation cost	54259	94008	101989	79479	93923

The minimum economic cost solution, minimum gas level fluctuation solution and trade-off solutions were selected. The trade-off results of MODE algorithm before and after improvement are shown in Table III. It can be seen that the strategy of minimum economic cost will cause large holding fluctuation. The minimum level fluctuation strategy can keep the level in the middle, but it will increase the energy economic operation cost.

TABLE III COMPARISON OF OBJECTIVE VALUE UNDER DIFFERENT STRATEGIES

Algorithm	Minimum economic cost strategy		Minimum holder fluctuation strategy		Compromise strategy	
	Z1	Z2	Z1	Z2	Z1	Z2
MODE	995335	179.57	1024287	86.49	1006156	117.32
K-MODE	922279	122.50	942249	55.17	933851	59.31

To further compare the advantages and disadvantages of MODE algorithm and K-MODE algorithm, the hypervolume index is used. The HV index by the two algorithms is output every 100 generations (shown in Figure 6). With the increase of the number of iterations, the HV value of the two algorithms tends to be flat, but the HV value of the K-MODE algorithm is significantly higher than that of the MODE algorithm.

Fig. 6 HV values during different algorithm iterations

The Pareto front obtained by MODE and K-MODE algorithms is shown in Figure 7. The quality of the Pareto solution set obtained by K-MODE is better than that of MODE algorithm. It shows that the K-MODE algorithm is more effective in solving the scheduling problem.

Fig. 7 PF obtained by different algorithms

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Virtual Worlds and Artificial Intelligence for Indigenous Engagement

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Abstract— The Alpena-Amberley Ridge (AAR) is a landform that is now 100 feet underwater in the Great Lakes – but 10,000 years ago, it was a unique dry land environment. Research on the AAR has documented some of the world's oldest hunting features including drive lanes and hunting blinds for targeting caribou. To better understand this submerged landform an immersive Virtual World (VW) model was created which includes AI caribou. The project collaborated with traditional caribou hunters from the Native Village of Kotzebue, Alaska, to assess the veracity of the VW model and to gain insight into the logic and placement of the ancient hunting structures. While the VW has helped investigate the prehistoric landscape, the collaboration with Native Alaskans has generated unexpected avenues to explore by incorporating traditional ecological knowledge into models of past environments and hunting behavior. We are now exploring other uses for the VW suggested by our community partners including its use in K-12 classrooms, and as a means of community engagement. In this paper an evolutionary learning algorithm, Cultural Algorithms, is used to predict optimal caribou pathways. The predicted patterns are compared to known structures and predictions by High School STEM students.

Keywords— Procedural Content Generation, Evolutionary Algorithms, Cultural Algorithms, Virtual Reality, STEM education.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Deep Dive Land Bridge simulation system was initially developed to aid underwater archaeologists in the discovery of ancient prehistoric sites located underwater in Lake Huron, one of the Great Lakes in the United States [1-3]. It utilized Artificial Intelligence and Virtual Reality to recreate the archaic semi-artic landscape and has facilitated the discovery of several ancient underwater sites [4]. The Alpena-Amberly Ridge (AAR) was above the Lake Huron water level for about 2,000 years from 10,000 B.P. to 8,000 B.P. Fig. 1 shows the location of the Land Bridge relative to the State of Michigan in the USA and Canada. The AAR is now 100 feet underwater in the Great Lakes – but 10,000 years ago, it was a unique dry land environment.

Research on the AAR has documented some of the world's oldest hunting features including drive lanes and hunting blinds for targeting caribou. To better understand this submerged landform an immersive Virtual World (DEEPDIVE) model was created. A

The key component of the Virtual World (VW) system are the caribou herds and their migration patterns through various biomes. Ancient hunter behaviors would have related to their ability to predict herd movements and exploit those predictions. Fig. 2 shows a caribou herd moving across the Land Bridge. Within the DEEPDIVE VW system was a Multi-agent planner, Pathfinder, whose job was to recreate optimal caribou pathways across the bridge. Those paths were then sent to the VR system to help guide the virtual herds. The DEEPDIVE system will be discussed in section 2.

While the Land Bridge VW program was initially designed as an aid for the discovery of submerged prehistoric sites, the system's potential as a means for understanding traditional hunting practices, its use as an educational tool became rapidly apparent in two ways. First, it could be used to record hunters' observations about potential uses of the ancient landscape. Traditional Alaskan hunters were invited to enter the Virtual World and describe what they saw. The project collaborated with traditional caribou hunters from the Native Village of Kotzebue, Alaska, to assess the veracity of the VW model and to gain insight into the logic and placement of the ancient hunting structures [5]. While the VW has helped investigate the prehistoric landscape, the collaboration with Native Alaskans has generated unexpected avenues to explore by incorporating traditional ecological knowledge into models of past environments and hunting behavior.

Second, these results indicated that the system might be successfully repurposed to be a valuable educational tool. So, we began to explore other uses for the VW suggested by our community partners including its use in K-12 classrooms, and as a means of community engagement. In order to test this

theory out the system was used as part of the STEM high school curriculum in Alpena Michigan. The first group of high school students used the Virtual Reality system for two weeks in the spring of 2022. Their goal was to identify areas of potential hunter activity.

As a result, this project combines archaeological methods with artificial intelligence, indigenous voices and community-based approaches. The goal of this work is to document how the DEEPDIVE AI system facilitated the collaboration between the various groups. In particular, we will focus on how the system served as a vehicle to make the results of the process transparent to the diverse group of stakeholders involved.

Fig 1 The Land Bridge.

Fig. 2 A caribou herd moving across the Land Bridge.

II. THE MULTI-AGENT PLANNING FRAMEWORK FOR THE DEEP DIVE SIMULATION COMPONENT

Figure 3 gives an overview of the overall Deep Dive system. It has four basic components: The Pathfinder MAP Simulation system; the Cultural Algorithm evolutionary optimizer (CA); the Graphical User Interface (GUI) for the simulation system; and The Virtual Reality (VR) system.

Fig. 3 The Overall Organization of the Deep Dive system.

The basis for the simulation system is Pathfinder, a Cooperative Multi-Agent Planner (CMAPP). There are several deterministic general purpose MAP solvers available [9]. They include MAPR (MAP Planning by Reuse), CMAP (Cooperative MAP), mu-SATPLAN (Satisfiability based planning), among others.

The CMAP, Pathfinder, used here was developed especially for the computational needs of this project. It is a monolithic, hierarchical Multiagent Planner based upon the A* Algorithm with the caribou agents as the target of the planning process. The planner uses a global heuristic to generate a single A* optimal path. The three algorithms comprising the Pathfinder approach are now briefly described:

Single Path A*: A* is a popular search-based pathfinding algorithm that's an adaptation of Dijkstra's Algorithm. The difference being an additional heuristic allowing it to attribute cost to actual and estimated distance from the goal. Since the algorithm calculated point by point it allows the caribou agents to traverse the landscape while focusing on effort, risk, and nutrition.

A*mbush: Another migration algorithm integrated into the system is A*mbush. A*mbush incorporates A* at its root. It uses the algorithm of A* but does so in separate waves instead of a single path. The number of waves is entered as a parameter, then the total herd size of Caribou is divided amongst the waves. The waves are then sent one after another with the next wave entering the landscape as the last one completes its journey. Each wave consumes a certain proportion of available calories, leaving the remainder for the waves that follow.

A*Dendriform: A*Dendriform is the final algorithm used in the path planner portion on the Deep Dive system. It incorporates A* at its root but also allows for branching during the exploration of the landscape. This means as the line of Caribou is traversing, they can divide on the spot allowing some of the herd to continue their path while the rest look for a separate path.

Fig 4. The Current Deep Dive GUI. The upper left gives the path produced by an algorithm. Bottom left gives the 4 basic parameters for the optimization.

Fig. 4 presents the GUI for the system. The upper left corner gives the map and displays the optimal runs produced. The wheel below the map displays the weights associated with each of the 4 basic components to be optimized: nutrition, risk, effort, and time. The user can dial in the weights for the

experiments and the results are generated on the map. A blow up of the map is given in Fig. 5 with the following color codes: turquoise, eskers (red), beach (yellow), white (tundra), and lake edge marsh (blue),

Fig. 5 The Land Bridge biomes.

The Cultural Algorithm (CA) component is employed to produce a set of weights that optimize group survivability for a particular herd and environment combination. The Cultural algorithm is a socially motivated algorithm developed in [11], and [12]. It's a means to solve problems in a complex system like the ones posed to the Deep Dive's path planner. It is described graphically in Figure 6. The CA is composed of a belief space and population space. Here the population is a set of experiments that employ different values weights for environmental parameters. The knowledge sources are housed in the belief space represent the knowledge of the population.

Individuals from the population are then influenced by belief space knowledge. Their resultant decisions are evaluated by their relative fitness. Top performers are accepted into the belief space and used to update the knowledge there. Here the knowledge sources determine the optimal weights priorities of risk, nutrition, time, and effort can have on the system.

Fig. 6 The Cultural Algorithm Pseudocode.

IV. RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The Cultural Algorithm was used to produce the optimal path distribution weight for three herd size sizes (8K, 15K, and 25K) that are representative of small, medium, and large herd sizes respectively during a fall migration. The environment represents the biomes that were present when the lake level was 55m below current sea level when the land bridge was known to be occupied by paleo-indians. Table 1 gives the resultant optimal weights.

The relative weights reflect two distinct strategies that separate the A*mbush and A*Dendriform from each other. For A*mbush time becomes very important since one wave follows another where the previous wave has already consumed a portion of the available resources. So with increased herd size search effort for food is now replaced by increased concern for starvation risk. Nutrition while still important is now less of a concern than moving the herd safely across the bridge.

The emergent strategy learned by the Cultural Algorithm for A*Dendriform is distinctly different. A*Dendriform can distribute the herd over the landscape in order to acquire new resources. Therefore, with increased effort it is able to collect more resources at the expense of time spent along the bridge. More grazing is likely to take place with smaller sized sub-herds more accessible to predation which is why risk weight has increased.

The learned patterns suggestion that the A*Dendriform strategy will be more viable in early Fall with more plentiful resources while in late Fall a phase shift to a more expeditious path across the bridge might take place.

Fig. 7: Portions of the land bridge crossed by individuals in a 25 K herd for the A*Dendriform strategy (on the left). Portion of the land bridge traversed by runs for the 25K A*mbush model.(on the right)

Fig. 7 gives the portion of the land bridge crossed by the 25K A*Dendriform herd using the CA optimized weights while Figure 8 provides the portion of the land bridge crossed by 25K A*mbush. Notice how the difference in weights is now expressed spatially in two related but different patterns of movement.

Fig. 8 overlays the runs of the two herd models with each of the 3 herd sizes. The color of a cell is the frequency that it was crossed over all of the runs, "the hit parade". The color scale on the right indicates how the frequency reflects the color. It is interesting to note that some areas, in red were exploited by both model and size combinations.

Table 1: Optimal Weights for Lake Biomes at 55m below sea level, around 9000 B.P.

	Ambush 8000	Ambush 15000	Ambush 25000	Dendri 8000	Dendri 15000	Dendri 25000	AVG	STD DEV
Effort	39	8	5	24	18	27	20.16	12.63
Risk	6	71	25	13	10	15	23.33	24.20
Nutrition	51	15	25	46	62	55	42.33	18.34
Time	4	6	45	16	10	3	6.54	5.31

migration patterns and incorporate knowledge about corresponding hunting strategies..

Fig. 8. The resulting Hit Parade data for the six CA optimized paths overlaid on top of each other. Red indicates the data points where all six paths passed. Colder colors indicate fewer paths, and dark blue is used to represent the outline of the landscape.

Fig. 9 The known and predicted sites overlaid on the most frequented pathways.

Figure 9 extracts the most frequented pathways produced by the CA optimized models along with locations of known sites and those predicted by the High School students. These results appear to validate the predictions of the model and most especially reflect the patterns that would have been produced by an A*mbush approach. Future work will examine Spring

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Niching Improves Recombinative Search

Revisiting the New York City Tunnels Problem

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ABSTRACT

We investigate an experiment from (Horn, 1997) in which a well-known diversity mechanism, fitness sharing, significantly improved the probability of finding the top five known solutions of the New York City Tunnels problem. We were intrigued by these results but the original publication provided too few details to exactly replicate the experiments. We tried a range of parameter values in our search for the “niching benefit.” We quickly found this benefit across a range of GA parameter settings. Despite the robustness of the niching search effect we could not replicate Horn’s high rate of success (at least for solution 1, the best-known) with a high crossover rate. Instead our implementation of the niching GA performed best for “middle values” of the probability of crossover (e.g., p_c from 0.2 to 0.8), with a sharp drop off in performance for small or large values of p_c . Overall our results support the general hypothesis of (Horn, 1997) with more fully documented controlled experiments, denser sampling, and two and half times the number of random seed runs per datum.

KEYWORDS

Genetic algorithms, optimization, fitness sharing, crossover, diversity maintenance operators, New York City Tunnels.

1 Introduction

Sometimes the simple genetic algorithm (sGA), using only selection, crossover, and recombination, converges too quickly. Good genetic material is not explored enough before selection replaces it by reproducing (i.e., exploiting) competing genetic material. And so many practitioners of evolutionary computation turn to diversity maintenance operators when applying GAs to hard optimization problems. In this paper we explore if and how to combine a diversity operator (fitness sharing) with selection and recombination and mutation on a known, hard problem in water distribution system design: the New York City Tunnels (NYCT) problem.

2 Background

The New York City Tunnels problem is a simplified model of a real world pipe network design problem, specifically for water distribution systems. Various techniques have been applied to finding a minimum cost design that meets the water pressure constraints. In the early 1990s a group from Adelaide University led by Angus Simpson first applied a genetic algorithm (GA) to the problem. The group was able to find three new feasible optima all of lower cost than all other solutions known at that time (or since; the problem is still open). But the best of the new optima, known as *solution 1*, the best-known solution to this date, at a cost of \$38.79 million, seemed to be very difficult to find for the simple GA. Most random seeded runs of the algorithm did not find solution 1. Since that time the Adelaide group has tried more advanced evolutionary computation techniques to improve the reliability of evolutionary search on NYCT, with mixed success. In 1995 Simpson spent a sabbatical year with the Illinois GA Lab (IlligAL) where he worked with Horn (Horn, 2023) to apply a niching operator to NYCT, in particular fitness sharing (Goldberg and Richardson, 1987). This effort seems to have resulted in significantly improved search performance on NYCT. However the results were never published (Horn, 2023) except as a few pages in a back chapter of Horn’s 1997 dissertation (Horn, 1997). In this paper we attempt to replicate those experiments.

Below we review the NYCT problem itself, as well as the previous work by Simpson, et. al. applying a simple GA, and then what little is recorded about the unpublished experiments by Horn and Simpson in 1995-6 (Horn, 1997; Horn, 2023).

2.1 The New York City Tunnels Problem (NYCT)

The New York City Tunnels (NYCT) problem is a water distribution network optimization problem developed by Schaake and Lai in 1969. In 1993 Murphy, Simpson, and Dandy successfully applied a genetic algorithm and discovered three optima that were previously undiscovered.

The goal of the NYCT problem is to redesign a pipeline network for distribution of fresh water throughout Manhattan, while minimizing installation costs and meeting minimum water pressure constraints at sixteen predetermined end nodes.

The old (existing) network consists of twenty-one underground pipes. For all twenty-one “links” a duplicate new pipe can be installed parallel to the existing one to increase capacity on that “link.” There are fifteen choices of new pipe diameter to choose

from. These fifteen choices, combined with the choice of not duplicating the pipe, allows us to code each of the twenty-one decision variables in four bits, resulting in a total chromosome length of $21 * 4 = 84$ bits; the total search space size is 2^{84} . The NYCT problem remains open.

The fitness function for the NYCT problem is computationally costly, as it involves a simulation of the candidate network's performance under a fixed load to determine pressure at each of the nodes. Pressure head constraint violations are penalized by adding a high cost to the total installation cost of the specified duplicate pipes. As a chosen pipe's diameter increases, the pressure also increases, but also results in a higher installation cost. The output of the fitness function is a total cost, including installation and penalties.

2.2 The Simple GA Applied to NYCT

In 1985 Morgan and Goulter found a new feasible low cost solution at \$39.20 million. In 1993 Murphy, Simpson, and Dandy (1993) used a GA with exponential scaling of the fitness function to find three new solutions, worth \$38.79, \$39.06, and \$39.17 (solutions 1, 2, and 3, respectively). A fourth solution at \$39.22 million and fifth at \$39.28 million were also found. The authors note that the GA usually converges to solution 2 or 3, which are very genetically similar.

2.2 Fitness Sharing

Fitness sharing was introduced by Goldberg and Richardson in 1987 [3]. Under fitness sharing, the objective fitness f_i of an individual i is degraded by the presence of nearby individuals:

$$f_{sh,i} = \frac{f_i}{\sum_{j \in P} Sh(i,j)}$$

Here $f_{sh,i}$ is the "shared fitness" of individual i . The sharing function, $Sh(i,j)$, is a decreasing function of the "distance" $d(i,j)$ between individuals i and j , as typically measured in genotypic or phenotypic space. A widely used sharing function is the linearly decreasing triangular sharing function:

$$Sh(i,j) = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{d(i,j)}{\sigma_{sh}} & \text{for } d(i,j) < \sigma_{sh} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

2.3 Fitness Sharing Applied to NYCT

A niched GA with sharing appears to be much more likely to locate the five top optima in a single run. Figure 1 illustrates a comparative run from 1997 between a GA with sharing and one without. For both cases, the GA parameters other than sharing are the same: a simple, generational GA with population size $N = 6000$, probability of single point crossover $p_c = 0.8$, no mutation ($p_m = 0.0$), and the fitness function was scaled by raising the objective fitness to the power $\beta_s = 20$ prior to sharing. The GA with sharing uses genotypic comparisons with $\sigma_s = 7$ bits. The GA was run with and without sharing for twenty different trials, each time terminating the run at 200 generations. Every individual created during a trial was examined and the number of trials (out of 20) in which a particular solution (1-5) is found was recorded. Calling this frequency of appearance "probability", the sampled probabilities of finding the top five known solutions in Figure 1 is plotted. Each plotted point

(k, p) is the percentage p of the twenty trials in which solution k is found.

The upper curve in Figure 1 plots the performance of sharing, while the lower curve plots the performance of the same GA with sharing turned off (i.e., a simple GA or *sGA*). It is clear that sharing exhibits a much higher probability of success in locating any of the top five solutions, but especially the more "difficult" solutions (1, 4, and 5).

Figure 1: Performance of sharing and crossover on NYCT from (Horn, 1997). (reprinted with permission)

3.0 Experiment 1: Role of Crossover in Niching

In this first experiment we focus on how much improvement, if any, sharing provides to GA search as we vary the rate of crossover from 0% to 100%. Originally, we attempted to verify the leftmost data points from Figure 1. These points show that "solution 1" (the best known solution with cost \$38.79 million) is found by the GA without sharing 25% of the time (that is five out of twenty random seed runs). Adding sharing improves this result to 75% (fifteen of twenty seeded runs). Both sets of runs used a crossover rate of 0.8.

Our runs however showed a success rate for sharing of only 38% (nineteen of fifty random seed runs) which is not much higher than our empirical success rate without sharing (28%), see Figure 2. While we knew of some differences between our version of the GA and sharing algorithms from (Horn, 1997) we did not think these would lead to such a large difference in success rate. (For example, Horn used single point crossover in 1997 while we used two-point. But two-point crossover usually outperforms single point.)

We thus decided to investigate other crossover rates to see if our implementation of a shared GA was able to achieve high (e.g., >50%) success rates for the \$38.79m solution.

3.1 Design of Experiment 1

In our new experiments we try to duplicate the algorithm and parameter settings used in (Horn, 1997) as possible. For example

we use no mutation, a population size of 6000, genotypic sharing (that is, we use hamming distance between two binary chromosomes), a niche radius (σ_{share}) of 7 bits, an α_{share} of 1.0, and a β_{share} (fitness scaling exponent) of 20. Some details of the algorithm are not found in (Horn, 1997) nor can the author recall them or find them in his notes (Horn, 2023), including what type of selection operator was used (e.g., tournament, proportionate, etc.). So here we choose what we consider to be “best practice” methods and settings, including binary tournament selection and two-point crossover. (Note that Horn’s 1997 dissertation DOES specify the crossover type as one-point crossover. We make a deliberate choice NOT to duplicate this one design choice because we believe that two-point crossover should always perform better than one-point, as it has no “end” bias.)

We also note here one other difference between our experiments in 2023 and those in (Horn, 1997): for each data point below we run the algorithm with a particular setting of the parameters on fifty different random seeds, while Horn used only twenty. (We are able to take advantage of faster hardware; the NYCT simulation is computationally intensive.)

In Figure 2 we summarize our first experiment. On the horizontal axis we vary crossover rate from 0 to 100% and on the vertical axis we indicate the probability of success (success being defined as discovering the \$38.79m solution at ANY time during the 200 generation run). Each data point is computed from 50 different random seed runs (the same 50 random seeds are used for EVERY data point in Figure 2). Thus the height of each data point is the percentage of fifty runs in which the \$38.79m solution appears at least once in 200 generations. The upper sequence (blue) connects the data points for the runs WITH SHARING while the lower (red) sequence plots the results of the runs WITHOUT SHARING (a.k.a., simple GA).

Figure 2: Performance (vertical axis) while increasing crossover probability (horizontal axis) both with sharing (blue, upper plot) and without (red, lower plot), on NYCT (new runs).

3.2 Analysis

Together the two plotted data sets in Figure 2 show the significant improvement in search capability that Horn describes in his dissertation, at least for the one solution of \$38.79m. And this difference, improving from a success rate of approximately 20% to approximately 80%, occurs over a range of crossover rates, but not the entire range. For low and high rates the probabilities of success drop, for both SHARING runs and NO SHARING runs (but more precipitously for the SHARING runs).

An important observation here (from empirical data only it must be noted) is that in this case the addition of fitness sharing results in a significant increase in search performance (as measured of course by the discovery of solution 1). We can speculate that this due to the maintenance of diversity allowing for more time to explore available genetic information.

A second important observation is that it does NOT appear to be the case that search performance improves monotonically with increasing crossover use. Indeed the success rate drops quickly once crossover reaches a rate of 75% or so. We don’t know why this is so. We can speculate that at low crossover rates there is not sufficient “mixing” of smaller, initial and early building blocks (exploration) before selection causes loss of diversity, despite the presence of niching, due to convergence to a smaller set of “species” each separated by at least a niche radius in hamming space (i.e., σ_{share} which is 7 bits in these runs). But at high crossover rates even our speculation ability fails us. Perhaps crossover at 80-100% probability is so disruptive that niched selection cannot maintain enough of the longer building blocks to further explore longer combinations of those blocks. We look to future studies to try to explain the degraded search at high p_c .

4.0 Experiment 2: Do Our Results Change with Mutation Rate?

In this experiment we investigate if and how much our results above change when we “turn on” mutation, that is, we use a non-zero mutation rate. We do not analyze a broad range of mutation rates but make a small foray into the realm of mutation-based exploration by re-running the experiment above but with a p_m of 0.001 (instead of 0.0). All other GA parameters are held the same. We then vary the crossover rate from 0 to 1.0 and perform two sets of experiments, one with sharing and the other without.

To be clear we are using standard bit-wise mutation: for each bit of each chromosome that is inserted into the next generation population, there is a p_m probability that we flip the bit. Thus we expect to mutate one of every thousand bits in the population, which in this case means $(1/1000) * 84 * 6000 = 504$ bits per generation. And once again our data points are averages over fifty runs each, using the same fifty random seeds as used in Experiment 1.

Figure 3: Performance of mutation (fixed at $P_m = 0.001$) and increasing crossover both with sharing (blue, upper) and without sharing (red, lower).

In this experiment we sampled only a few crossover probabilities. These data points are shown in Figure 3. Again, all parameters other than mutation probability are the same as in the runs for Figure 2. From these few data points (four for the SHARING runs, in blue, and five for the runs with NO SHARING, in red) we see similar results as in Experiment 1. Sharing seems once again to offer a significant advantage in the search for solution 1. And performance again seems best for crossover rates that are not too low nor too high.

Although this experiment looks at just one positive setting of mutation probability we do consider it to be evidence supporting the hypothesis that our observations in Experiment 1 generalize to some range of the common settings of mutation probability.

5 Conclusion

This study is limited to just a few parameter settings of a particular niching algorithm on a single optimization problem. But the NYCT problem is hard one, and it has been attacked and studied by different authors, so that we believe that it can be somewhat representative of realistic and hard problems for evolutionary search. As for parameter settings we tried to carefully choose them based on best practice and our own experimentation. But ultimately any generalization of the results in this contribution will depend on further controlled experiments, applications to other problems, and development and testing of predictive analytical models.

For now we can say that the simple genetic algorithm for pipe network optimization has been found to be significantly more effective with fitness sharing (a diversity maintenance operator) enabled. One experiment indicates that this could hold true regardless of whether mutation is enabled. Results were presented at numerous probabilities of crossover, comparing the algorithm’s success in finding the best-known solution for the New York City Tunnels optimization problem when fitness sharing is and is not enabled. It was been found that the genetic algorithm has a higher

success rate in finding the optimal solution within 200 generations, and consistently converges upon the optimal solution quicker at a given crossover rate when fitness sharing is enabled. These findings suggest a significant benefit in using fitness sharing on genetic algorithms applied towards optimization problems.

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Electricity Technician Dispatch Routing Optimization

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Abstract—The Multi-Depot Vehicle Routing Problem (MDVRP) is discrete optimization problem consisting of optimizing a set of routes while visiting a set of locations. We consider an application of the MDVRP in which we look for the optimal tours for technicians to provide services to their customers. Given that the MDVRP is a known NP-hard problem, we propose a hybrid solution that relies on clustering and metaheuristics. More precisely, our proposed method is structured in two stages. In the first phase, we use K-means clustering to identify the appropriate set of customers to be served by each technician, based on availability, demand, and proximity of customer’s location to each technician’s depot. We then consider nature-inspired techniques, Stochastic Local Search (SLS), Nearest Neighbor Algorithm (NNA), as well as exact methods to get the optimal route for each cluster (set of customers). To evaluate the performance of our solving method, we conducted a set of experiments on several problem instances. The results show the effectiveness of our method when SLS is used as a search technique.

Index Terms—Combinatorial Optimization, Nature-Inspired Techniques, Metaheuristics, Multi-Depot Vehicle Routing Problem (MDVRP)

I. INTRODUCTION

The Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP) is one of the most important combinatorial optimization problems in the field of transportation [1], [2]. In a typical VRP, vehicles with given capacity, have to deliver goods to a set of locations, starting from a given depot. The main goal is to optimize tour(s) cost while meeting capacity constraints and visiting each location exactly once [3]. The Multi-Depot VRP (MDVRP) is a variant of the VRP in which there are several depots from which vehicles start and return after providing services [4]. We call the Electricity Technician Dispatch Problem (ETDP) a specific MDVRP application consisting of optimizing a set of tours taken by technicians who are deployed to provide customer service in different geographical locations. The goal in a ETDP is to optimize the total cost related to the adopted tours while meeting the availability and demand constraints of technicians and customers, respectively.

The VRP is a generalization of the Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) which is considered as a NP-hard problem. In order to return an optimal solution to the TSP, a search algorithm with exponential time cost would be needed, $O(2^E)$ where E is the number of edges in the related network [4]. In order to overcome this difficulty in practice, metaheuristics and

machine learning techniques [5]–[10] have been adopted as alternative methods. While these techniques do not guarantee the optimality of the solution returned, they can be a good compromise in trading the quality of the outcome for the related processing time. Solving the MDVRP and the EDTP comes with an additional challenge as we are dealing with several tours, each with its own starting depot. To address this difficulty (in addition to the exponential time cost inherited by the underlying TSP), we propose a solution that works in two phases. We first use a variant of the K-means clustering to cluster customers according to their proximity to each depot, while taking into account their demand and availability of the depot assigned technician. We then apply a search method that consists in finding the optimal tour for each cluster. In this context, we consider the Branch and Bound technique (B&B) in addition to local search and nature-inspired techniques. The local search methods are the Stochastic Local Search (SLS) and the Nearest Neighbor Algorithm (NNA). For the nature-inspired techniques, we use the Whale Optimization Algorithm (WOA), the Genetic Algorithm (GA), the Ant Colony Optimization (ACO), and the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) method. To evaluate the performance of our solving method, we conducted a set of experiments on a set of problem instances from [11]. In the experiments, our search techniques are compared to adaptive large neighborhood search heuristic (ALNS) [12], a Hybrid Genetic Algorithm with Adaptive Diversity Control (HGSADC) [13], and a Hybrid algorithm called ILS-RVND-SP that combines a Iterated Local Search (ILS) based on a Variable Neighborhood Descent with Random neighborhood ordering (RVND) and a Set Partitioning (SP) method [14]. The results demonstrate the superiority of SLS over the other methods in terms of the quality of the solution returned and the related processing time

II. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

We use a 2-stage technique to solve the EDTP. In the first step, we use K-means method to find the appropriate clusters of customers. Clusters are formed according to the number of depots (considered as centroids) and each customer is assigned to the nearest depot. We use two variants of clustering, each of which will be explained in the following subsection. Then in the second stage, we apply Branch and

Bound (B&B) and several metaheuristics to find the best route for each cluster. Two categories of metaheuristics are used: local search and nature-inspired techniques. The local search methods are the Stochastic Local Search (SLS) and the Nearest Neighbor Algorithm (NNA). For the nature-inspired techniques, we use the Whale Optimization Algorithm (WOA), the Genetic Algorithm (GA), the Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) method, and the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) technique.

A. Clustering customers in a EDTP

We use two variants of K-means. In the first clustering approach, that we call Clustering 1 (Clust. 1), service centers (depots) are considered centroids, and the Euclidean distance of all customers is calculated with respect to all service centers. The number of formed clusters equals the number of service centers, and each customer is assigned to the nearest service center that is closest to it in terms of Euclidean distance. Thus, each cluster includes a service center and a set of customers. In the second clustering method, that we call Clustering 2 (Clust. 2), we adopt a similar approach with the difference that after adding customers based on road distance, if a cluster reaches its maximum capacity, the remaining potential customers (to be added to the same cluster) must be added to the next closest service center. In fact, in this approach, we have a capacity constraint check mechanism to control the service centers' capacity.

B. Discrete Version of WOA

WOA has been proposed by Mirjalili and Lewis [15] and is considered as a combination of two variants of PSO, namely the moth flame and the grey wolf techniques [16]. As the original WOA algorithm [15] was presented for solving continuous optimization problems, to solve the ETDP, we need to discretize this algorithm and redefine its operators.

Before we define the discrete versions of the WOA, which includes spiral motion and shrinking encircling in both exploitation and exploration phases, let us first presents the definition of a candidate solution. Each candidate solution represents a whale and contains k rows (number of available electricity technicians). After determining the route for each technician with one of the clustering methods, the customer navigation sequence is stored by them in a vector in each row. It should be noted that the beginning and end of this vector service is a service center from which the technician starts and returns to it, and these vectors do not necessarily have the same size. This results in a candidate solution (a whale) that includes the routes taken by each technician in each row. After generating an initial population by one of the clustering methods, we use a new operator called Swap Operation (SO) as reported in [10] to make changes to the WOA algorithm. This operator helps us move a candidate solution from one position to another in the search space. The authors also defined a Swap Operation Pool (SOP) as the number of customers (n), which is a set of random successive swap operations, and by navigating through this pool, we apply

different swaps to one solution. It should be noted that all SOPs in the SOP are unique [10].

After examining the SO operator, we use it in the equations of the WOA algorithm. For this purpose, we first generate a random number, A , that is in the range of $[0,1]$. A random number called p is generated to randomly balance shrinking and spiral attacks.

$$A = \begin{cases} 2a \cdot r - a & p < 0.5 \text{ (shrinking)} \\ e^{bl} \cdot \cos(2\pi l) & p \geq 0.5 \text{ (spiral attack)} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

An SOP is then generated by the number of customers, and for each SO in the SOP, we generate a number between $[0,1]$ and call it D . If the generated number is less than A , that SO is accepted, otherwise that SO is removed from the SOP. We then apply the resulting SOP to Best whale (in exploitation) or Random Whale (in exploration), and the next generation whale is obtained (both Best whale and Random whale are denoted with X^*).

$$X(t+1) = X^*(t) + A \cdot D \quad (2)$$

In each iteration of the algorithm, if the resulting whale has a better fitness function than the previous generation, we will update the Best Whale. A concrete example of all the mentioned steps is presented in the next section.

C. GAs for solving the EDTP

The genetic algorithm consists of several stages: starting from generating the initial population, selection, crossover and mutation. First a population randomly using permutation encoding. Each individual in the population represents a possible solution to the problem. The chromosomes are encoded using path representation in which the customers are listed in the order in which they are visited. For selection, we used a well known method called 'the roulette wheel selection' based on evaluating the probability for each individual (ratio of the individual fitness and total fitness). For the crossover, a point on both parents' chromosomes is picked randomly, and designated a 'crossover point'. The crossing process of two parents will result in two new off-springs each carrying a part. Crossover aims to produce a new population with a higher average fitness value compared to the previous population. We applied the following mutations following on the swap techniques we used previously [10]: node and sequence swap mutation and inversion mutation.

D. Ant Colony Optimization (ACO)

To solve the ETDP using ACO we have adopted a method with three stages. The first stage begins with randomly constructing the population of ants' candidate solutions. We use the parameters α and β to determine the relative importance of the weights of pheromone information (variable values of the candidate solution) and heuristic information. In the second step, a local search is performed to determine which of the pheromones should be updated. In the third step, we update and improve the pheromones identified in the previous step.

Consequently, bad candidates are decreased in a process called pheromone evaporation. These steps are repeated until the termination condition of the algorithm is satisfied.

E. Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO)

PSO is a population-based search method proposed by Kennedy and Eberhart [17]. The basic version of PSO starts by initializing a population of particles, called swarm, each with random position and velocity. At each iteration, all particles evaluate their own position and compares it to those stored in the past. The best position for each particle is then maintained, and shared with other particles so the global best is identified. Given both local and global best positions, particles positions are updated according the following velocity and position equations.

$$v_i(t+1) = w \otimes v_i(t) + c_1 \cdot R_1 \otimes (p_i - x_i(t)) + c_2 \cdot R_2 \otimes (p_g - x_i(t)) \quad (3)$$

$$x_i(t+1) = x_i(t) + v_i(t+1) \quad (4)$$

$v_i(t+1)$ (respectively $v_i(t)$ and $x_i(t+1)$) (respectively $x_i(t)$) are respectively the velocity and position at time $t+1$ (respectively t). p_i and p_g are respectively the position of the local and the global best. In equation 3, Variables R_1 and R_2 are random values chosen between 0 and 1. Acceleration coefficients c_1 and c_2 are used to allow a movement towards the local or the global best, while w favors more exploration. To apply PSO for solving the underlying TSPs of the EDTP, we redefine the distance between particles in terms of number of swaps as done in [10]. In this way, a particle moves towards its local best p_i (respectively global best p_g) by reducing the number of swaps between the two particles.

F. Stochastic Local Search (SLS)

We use a SLS method based on Kruskal's algorithm to tackle the ETDP problem. Kruskal's algorithm consists in finding a minimum spanning tree instead of returning a Hamiltonian cycle (of a given TSP). Thus, we adapt an SLS method which works by adjusting Kruskal's algorithm in order to end up with a TSP tour. First, all the edges are sorted in increasing order according to their costs. Then, starting with the edge of the least cost, edges are explored recursively one by one at a time, and are selected in such a way they do not cause a vertex to have a degree more than two, or result in a cycle unless the number of selected edges is equal to the number of nodes. Note that this SLS method guarantees a feasible solution to complete graphs where all the vertices are connected to each other with an edge (which is the case of the ETDP clusters), but it may not guarantee a solution to non-complete graphs.

G. Branch and Bound (B&B)

B&B was first introduced by [18] in 1960 to solve discrete programming problems related to operations research. Ever since, B&B and its variants have been adopted by the research community to solve various real-world combinatorial optimization problems including the well-known TSP which is

considered a unique case of the ETDP problem (i.e. the TSP is an ETDP with a single service centre). Various B&B variants [10] have been proposed to solve the TSP problem for the main purpose of minimizing the exponential time cost presented by the B&B algorithm, and addressing the extensive memory limitation required for the computation during search when solving relatively large-sized problems. These variants mainly differ in the procedure of estimating the Lower Bound, as well as the exploration strategy of candidate solutions during search (e.g. Breadth First Search, Depth First Search, etc.). Solving the ETDP using B&B is very similar to solving the TSP as the ETDP can be seen as a m-TSP (m depicts the number of service centers) where the common objective is to find a Hamiltonian Cycle satisfying the constraint of visiting every vertex exactly once while minimizing the total cost of the traversed route to achieve an optimal solution. The main difference is that in the ETDP, the total path cost traversed by the technicians is computed using the cost of each sub-path found from every cluster.

Our proposed B&B algorithm uses the Breadth First Search (BFS) strategy to enumerate all candidate solutions relying on the Lower Bound (LB) and Upper Bound (UB) parameters for pruning the infeasible and non-optimal solutions. Since we are dealing with a minimization problem, the UB is used to indicate the best most-recent solution found thus far during search which designate the solution' path cost. The UB is updated every time a consistent solution is found with a lower objective (lower path cost). The LB is an over-estimation and it is used to indicate the worthiness of exploring a given node in the search space. The LB is initially estimated by computing the sum of the two edges of least costs adjacent to every vertex divided by 2, since the overall sum for all vertices would be double the cost of the obtained tour because every edge is considered twice. At any node during search, the LB is computed according to the two edges with the least costs going from a given node while considering the weight of the currently traversed sub-path. Let us consider nodes $\{X, Y, Z\}$ where Y and Z are the two edges of the least costs adjacent to vertex X , the LB is the average cost of arcs (X, Y) and (X, Z) , as depicted in Equation 5.

$$LB(X) = 1/2 \sum_{COST} (Y, Z) \quad (5)$$

At any point during search, the pruning of non-optimal solutions occurs when the LB becomes greater or equal to the UB. In this situation, there will be no need to continue exploring the current path since we know for a fact that the current node will not lead us to a better solution than the one we already have. Otherwise, if the estimated LB is lower than UB, we need to keep exploring the current path because it may lead to an optimal solution.

III. EXPERIMENTATION

To assess the performance of the techniques we previously listed, we conducted a set of experiments on instances proposed by Cordeau et al. [11]. MATLAB programming

TABLE I
THE QUALITY OF THE SOLUTION RETURNED BY EACH METHOD

Inst.	n	k	m	Clust. 1 + ALNS	Clust. 1 + HGSADC	Clust. 1 RVND-SP	Clust. 1 + WOA	Clust. 2 + WOA	Clust. 1 + GAS	Clust. 2 + GAS	Clust. 1 + ACO	Clust. 2 + ACO	Clust. 1 + PSO	Clust. 2 + PSO	Clust. 1 + NNA	Clust. 2 + NNA	Clust. 1 + SLS	Clust. 2 + SLS	Clust. 1 + B&B	Clust. 2 + B&B
p01	50	4	4	576.87	576.87	576.87	576.87	576.87	556.70	557.78	576.87	576.87	581.51	556.88	590.91	604.24	556.87	549.51	359.34	372.14
p02	50	2	4	473.53	473.53	473.53	473.53	481.25	453.21	456.57	473.53	475.86	496.56	492.62	590.91	604.24	556.87	549.51	359.34	372.14
p03	75	3	5	641.19	641.19	641.19	641.19	701.54	633.95	625.44	641.19	644.46	652.02	618.79	742.59	703.37	707.18	643.44	426.21	470.36
p04	100	8	2	1006.09	1001.23	1001.04	1001.59	1001.59	1077.33	1057.62	1006.09	1020.52	1028.87	1044.61	815.87	792.01	796.53	788.38	-	-
p05	100	5	2	752.34	750.03	750.21	750.03	750.21	747.70	732.74	750.03	751.90	845.74	855.42	856.17	853.57	885.07	855.27	-	-
p06	100	6	3	883.01	876.50	876.50	876.50	876.50	865.91	887.12	876.50	885.84	917.79	913.18	852.86	850.84	791.03	784.41	-	-
p07	100	4	4	889.36	884.43	881.97	885.80	885.80	1032.52	919.23	885.80	891.95	923.65	965.93	859.61	955.84	781.38	872.58	-	-
p08	249	14	2	4421.03	4397.42	4393.70	4437.68	4437.68	4550.50	4341.36	4437.68	4485.08	4400.89	4130.38	3038.60	3083.95	2783.39	2857.89	-	-
p09	249	12	3	3892.50	3868.59	3864.22	3900.22	3900.22	3840.12	3448.33	3900.22	3971.59	3833.73	3740.39	2921.10	2946.61	2865.36	2867.53	-	-
p10	249	8	4	3666.85	3636.08	3634.72	3663.02	3663.02	3958.73	3459.27	3663.02	3747.62	3645.48	3593.82	3125.38	3232.76	2973.82	3116.77	-	-
pr01	48	1	4	861.32	861.32	861.32	861.32	905.78	814.42	817.29	861.32	861.32	849.27	828.79	1131.58	1160.18	984.89	1025.46	580.19	623.99
pr02	96	2	4	1308.17	1307.34	1308.53	1307.61	1315.41	1300.73	1269.26	1307.34	1321.21	1407.25	1429.41	1542.74	1657.30	1469.68	1688.21	-	-
pr03	144	3	4	1810.66	1803.80	1804.09	1806.60	1811.39	1792.24	1771.43	1806.60	1815.94	1947.24	2002.03	1903.34	2021.11	2023.53	2018.55	-	-
pr04	192	4	4	2073.16	2059.36	2060.93	2072.52	2072.52	2256.2	2113.12	2072.52	2072.52	2433.48	2546.66	2218.46	2372.51	2101.93	2255.52	-	-
pr05	240	5	4	2350.31	2340.29	2338.12	2385.77	2385.77	2379.17	2452.95	2385.77	2385.77	2700.55	2865.88	2249.97	2549.71	2234.55	2620.16	-	-
pr06	288	6	4	2695.74	2681.93	2685.23	2723.27	2723.27	2730.82	2746.71	2723.27	2723.27	2874.50	3169.63	2888.04	2778.95	2687.33	2880.42	-	-
pr07	72	1	6	1089.56	1089.56	1089.56	1089.56	1102.14	1150.51	1047.16	1089.56	1108.16	1060.42	1074.95	1321.43	1395.61	1358.82	1395.04	677.24	915.29
pr08	144	2	6	1675.74	1665.05	1665.08	1666.60	1685.64	1647.84	1770.05	1666.60	1686.21	1974.57	2011.28	1969.25	2114.20	1827.08	2096.14	-	-
pr09	216	3	6	2144.84	2134.17	2135.37	2153.10	2168.55	2229.30	2013.33	2153.10	2168.55	2431.62	2513.66	2501.05	2494.74	2096.10	2438.39	-	-
pr10	288	4	6	2905.43	2886.59	2882.41	2921.85	2921.85	2943.35	3272.16	2921.85	2921.85	3033.02	3524.48	2835.81	3212.80	2634.62	3188.17	-	-

language is used and each algorithm was run 10 times for each instance. The average is then reported. The experiments were conducted on a computer with an Intel Core i5-6200U with 2.30 GHz and 12 GB of RAM running under Windows 10 with 64 bits. All the parameters guiding the algorithms we have used are tuned, to their best using Chess Rating System (CRS-Tuning) [19]. CRS-Tuning has comparable merits comparing to Revac [20] and F-Race [21] while exhibiting several advantages [19]. For WOA, a and r are randomly selected from $[0,1]$ while l is randomly selected from $[-1,+1]$. In the case of GAs, a single point crossover is chosen with probability 0.8, and the roulette wheel method is adopted. For the mutation, we consider Swap Mutation, Sequence Swap Mutation, and Inversion Mutation, respectively with probability 0.1, 0.02, and 0.08. For ACO, α and β are respectively equal to 2 and 1. The pheromone update and evaporation rates are both equal to 0.1. For PSO, the acceleration coefficients c_1 and c_2 are both equal to 1.4, the inertial weight w is equal to 0.9. We have adopted the maximum CPU time as the stopping criterion as all our methods are implemented in the same programming language (MATLAB), are executed on the same machine, and are using the same programming environment. We could have used the number of Function Evaluations (FEs) [22], instead of CPU time, but this will require separating FEs in each of the methods that we use, which is a challenging process, as reported in [23], given that we are dealing with constrained optimization problems. To have a fair comparison, we have adopted the same population size for all the nature-inspired techniques. Indeed, FE is the most expensive part in a nature-inspired technique, and its related running time is directly affected by the number of individuals in a population.

The results of the comparative experiments (quality of the solutions returned) are reported in Table I. Our solving techniques are compared with an adaptive large neighborhood search heuristic (ALNS) [12], a Hybrid Genetic Algorithm

with Adaptive Diversity Control (HGSADC) [13], and a Hybrid algorithm combining Iterated Local Search (ILS) based on a Variable Neighborhood Descent with Random neighborhood ordering (RVND) and a Set Partitioning (SP) method [14]. In Table I, n is the number of customers, k is the number of available technicians (vehicles), and m is the number of service centers (depots). It should be noted that the best results obtained are shown in bold. As we can see in Table I, B&B fails to return the solutions for medium and large instances which is also justified by the literature [24], [25]. This is mainly due to the exponential time cost that this exact method suffers from. However, solutions returned by B&B are guaranteed to be optimal according to the chosen clustering technique (although they require a large amount of time, compared to the other methods). ALNS, HGSADC, and ILS-RVND-SP use Clust. 1 as a first step given that this clustering technique has the potential to include better solutions. This can be easily noticeable by the results returned by B&B. SLS returns better quality solutions than the other methods, followed by GAs and HGSADC. PSO, ACO, WOA, and NNA come next and still have competitive results.

IV. CONCLUSION

We propose a new method based on clustering and optimization techniques for solving the EDTP. More precisely, clustering is applied as an initial phase to identify the groups of customers to be served by each technician. Exact and approximate techniques are then used to find the best tour for each cluster. In regard to the approximate techniques, we consider both local search and nature-inspired methods. To assess the performance of our hybrid solving method and its underlying solving techniques, we conducted a set of experiments and reported the results. Overall, both local search and nature-inspired algorithms exhibit promising results, with SLS as the best method in terms of quality of the returned solution and the corresponding running time.

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Meta-Heuristic Algorithm for Model Order Reduction using the Nu-Gap Metric

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Abstract—This study examines the Nu-gap metric-based model order reduction problem and a meta-heuristic algorithm for its solution. The Nu-gap metric is a measure to evaluate the distance between two systems in a closed-loop configuration. Finding a low-order system that substantially approximates a high-order system in the sense of Nu-gap can therefore have practical implications. The nonconvex nature of this model reduction problem, however, makes it challenging to solve. To address this issue, a meta-heuristic-based approach that is superior at solving non-convex problems is proposed. The algorithm's efficiency is illustrated when compared to conventional Nu-gap model reduction strategies. Nonetheless, simply applying the Nu-gap to reduce the model complexity may result in a response error between the original and reduced-order models. The frequency response matching technique-based modified Nu-gap is therefore developed. In order to demonstrate that the proposed modified Nu-gap provides less response error, a benchmark problem for larger-order model reduction is taken into consideration for evaluation purposes.

Index Terms—model order reduction, Nu-gap, meta-heuristic algorithm, approximation

I. INTRODUCTION

In engineering fields, the model order reduction methodology is frequently employed as an efficient strategy for handling complex systems. This technique facilitates analysis and control design by providing low-dimensional models that are simpler to comprehend and manipulate. Several methods, such as H_2/H_∞ -based algorithms [1], [2], Hankel-based algorithms [3], and convex optimization-based methods, have been proposed. These methods, however, may not take into account the closed-loop behavior-related properties of reduced-order models. The ν -gap metric [1], which is a measure for evaluating the distance between two systems in a closed-loop setup, can cope with such drawback. Therefore, some model reduction methods based on the ν -gap have been proposed. The model reduction problem in the ν -gap metric is represented as Bilinear Matrix Inequalities (BMIs) and solved using Semi-Definite Programming (SDP) optimization as described in [5]. However, the Winding Number Condition (WNC), which is related with the Nyquist diagram in the ν -gap metric, is not taken into account in the technique, and the

procedure's performance is heavily dependent on the initial set of candidate solutions. On the other hand, an algorithm based on SDP and frequency response matching has been proposed [6]. It solves the problem by converting the nonconvex to the quasi-convex and introducing the central transfer function to account for WNC. Nevertheless, there are still issues like the restricted search space and the challenge in choosing a suitable initial solution set.

This study discusses the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO)-based model reduction algorithm. This method is primarily based on a meta-heuristic algorithm that is renowned for being excellent at solving a variety of non-convex problems. While minimizing the ν -gap and satisfying the WNC, the proposed technique identifies the unknown parameters of reduced-order models. The algorithm's efficiency is illustrated when compared to conventional Nu-gap model reduction strategies. Problems like the inability to include WNC [5] and the restriction of search space by indirectly solving WNC [6] can be solved since the proposed method can directly handle the non-convex WNC. In addition, compared to conventional approaches, the proposed algorithm based on the meta-heuristic optimizer is less dependent on initial sets of candidate solutions. Nonetheless, simply applying the Nu-gap to reduce the model complexity may result in a response error between the original and reduced-order models. Therefore, as an objective function to enhance the response matching-related property, the modified ν -gap is proposed. The proposed method is then used to solve the benchmark problem for model reduction for larger-order models. The conventional ν -gap and the modified ν -gap-based reduced-order models are presented, followed by simulations using the step input in a unit feedback configuration. The simulation result validates the enhanced response matching performance of the reduced-order model constructed using the modified ν -gap metric.

II. MODEL ORDER REDUCTION USING THE ν -GAP METRIC

A. ν -gap metric and closed-loop performance

The ν -gap is a metric that measures the similarity of two dynamical systems when they are coupled in the feedback loop with a stabilizing controller. Let $P_1(s)$ and $P_2(s)$ be linear time invariant transfer functions. Denote a normalized left coprime factorization of P as $P_1 = N_1 M_1^{-1}$, and a normalized

right coprime factorization of P as $P_2 = \tilde{N}_2 \tilde{M}_2^{-1}$. Also, let $G_1 = [N_1 \ M_1]^{-1}$ be the normalized left graph symbol of P_1 , and $\tilde{G}_2 = [-\tilde{M}_2 \ \tilde{N}_2]$ be the normalized right graph symbol of P_2 . The winding number condition is defined as

$$\det(G_2^* G_1)(j\omega) \neq 0, \quad \forall \omega \in \mathbb{R}, \quad \text{wno } \det(G_2^* G_1) = 0, \quad (1)$$

where $*$ denotes the complex conjugate transpose as $G(s)^* := \overline{G(-\bar{s})}^T$, and $\text{wno } g(s)$ represents the winding number about the origin of $g(s)$ when s follows the standard Nyquist D -contour. Then, the ν -gap between $P_1(s)$ and $P_2(s)$ is defined as follow:

$$\delta_\nu(P_1, P_2) = \begin{cases} \|\tilde{G}_2 G_1\|_\infty, & \text{if (1) is satisfied,} \\ 1, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the H_∞ -norm of a dynamical system. Note that $0 \leq \delta_\nu(P_1, P_2) \leq 1$ and $P_1(s) = P_2(s)$, if and only if $\delta_\nu(P_1, P_2) = 0$. Furthermore, the stability margin $b_{P,C}$ is calculated when the closed-loop system consists of the plant $P(s)$ and the controller $C(s)$ as

$$b_{P,C} = \begin{cases} \left\| \begin{bmatrix} I \\ C \end{bmatrix} (I+PC)^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} I & P \end{bmatrix} \right\|_\infty^{-1}, & \text{if } C \text{ stabilizes } P, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

In a closed-loop system, there are some formalizable properties relating to robustness and performance [3], [4].

Proposition 1:

- 1) $[P_1, C]$ is stable for all P_1 satisfying $\delta_\nu(P_1, P_2) \leq \beta$, if and only if $b_{P_2, C} > \beta$,
- 2) $[P_1, C]$ is stable for all C satisfying $b_{P_2, C} > \beta$, if and only if $\delta_\nu(P_1, P_2) \leq \beta$,
- 3) $\delta_\nu(P_1, P_2) \leq \|H(P_1, C) - H(P_2, C)\|_\infty \leq \delta_\nu(P_1, P_2) (b_{P_1, C} b_{P_2, C})^{-1}$, where $H(P, C) := \begin{bmatrix} P \\ I \end{bmatrix} (I - CP)^{-1} [-C \ I]$.

It is possible to determine the stability in a closed-loop system using ν -gap and stability margin when a plant is modified or perturbed. The ν -gap offers a bound on the closed-loop performance of plants connected to the same controller individually. In conclusion, $\delta_\nu(P_1, P_2)$ is a good measure of the difference between P_1 and P_2 , which are both to be controlled by the same feedback compensator with near unity gain [4]. Therefore, if a reduced-order model that closely approximates the original model in the ν -gap sense is obtained, the reduced-order model may be substituted for the original model. Furthermore, a controller designed for the reduced-order model is likely to work well for the complex original model as well.

B. Model Order Reduction employing the PSO Algorithm

The model order reduction problem is the identification of the coefficients of a reduced-order model. Given an original

m th-order model $P(s)$, the structure of reduced-order model $R(s)$ is fixed as

$$\frac{x_n s^b + x_{n-1} s^{b-1} + \cdots + x_{n-b+1} s + x_{n-b}}{s^a + x_{n-b-1} s^{a-1} + x_{n-b-2} s^{a-2} + \cdots + x_2 s + x_1} \quad (4)$$

where $a < m$ and $n = a + b$. The integer values a and b are set by the designer, and a can be estimated by referring to the original model's Hankel singular values (HSVs), which provide an energy measurement for each system state; i.e., the ratio of HSVs can be used to determine an appropriate order for a reduced-order model. Therefore, the objective function of the optimization problem for model reduction is to minimize the ν -gap, which is to be optimized by the design variable \mathbf{x} . Then, the design problem can be formulated as follows:

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}} f(\mathbf{x}) = \delta_\nu(P(s), R(s)), \quad \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{D} \in \mathbb{R}^n \quad (5)$$

where $\delta_\nu(\cdot)$ is calculated as (2), and \mathbb{D} denotes the search space which is given by the designer.

On the other hand, for minimizing response error between the original model and the reduced-order model in unit-feedback configurations, a novel objective function based on the modified ν -gap is proposed as follows:

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}} f(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^N sv(\tilde{G}_2 G_1(\omega_i)), \quad (6)$$

where $\omega_i \in [\omega_l, \omega_h]$, and the WNC in (1) should be guaranteed. Note that $sv(H(j\omega_i))$ denotes the singular value of the dynamic system $H(s)$ at the specified frequency ω_i . In (6), N is the number of sampling frequencies, while ω_l and ω_h represent lower and upper bounds of frequency, respectively. \tilde{G}_2 and G_1 denote respectively the normalized right graph symbol of $P(s)$ and the normalized left graph symbol of $R(s)$. This optimization problem, however, is difficult to solve since it is non-convex [6] and involves constraints on the WNC. Therefore, the PSO algorithm-based methodology, which is superior at solving non-convex problems, is proposed. The distributed PSO [8] for solving the considered optimization problems in (5) and (6) consists of the following steps:

Step 1: Set the initial iteration as $k = 1$ and design parameters of PSO algorithm such as n_p (population size), n_b (neighborhood size), k_{max} (maximum number of iterations), and $\vec{\mathbf{x}}_{min} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\vec{\mathbf{x}}_{max} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ (boundaries of the search space \mathbb{D}). The initial position and velocity vectors of each particle are computed as follows:

$$\vec{\mathbf{x}}_i^1 = \vec{\mathbf{x}}_{min} + r_1^k \times (\vec{\mathbf{x}}_{max} - \vec{\mathbf{x}}_{min}), \quad \vec{\mathbf{v}}_i^1 = \vec{\mathbf{0}}, \quad (7)$$

where r_1^k denotes a diagonal matrix whose elements are uniformly distributed in $[0, 1]$, and $i = 1, 2, \dots, n_p$.

Step 2: Evaluate the fitness value $F(\vec{\mathbf{x}}_i^k)$ of all particles by the objective function (5),(6).

Step 3: Update $\vec{\mathbf{x}}_{p,i}^k$ (the best position among the positions the i th particle has encountered up to the k th iteration), and $\vec{\mathbf{x}}_{b,i}^k$ (the best position obtained among the

Fig. 1 Convergence property of objective function values

TABLE I Result of example

	Objective function value: $\delta_{L2}(P(s), R(s))$			
	Best	Worst	Mean	Standard deviation
Tan et al. [5]	0.1106	0.7445	0.4543	0.1334
This paper	0.0965	0.0965	0.0965	0.00

i th particle's neighborhoods of j th particle at the k th iteration) through following formulation:

$$\vec{x}_{p,i}^k \leftarrow \arg \min_{\vec{x} \in \{\vec{x}_j^k | j=1, \dots, k\}} F(\vec{x}), \quad (8)$$

$$\vec{x}_{b,i}^k \leftarrow \arg \min_{\vec{x} \in \{\vec{x}_j^k | j=i-\frac{n_b}{2}, \dots, i+\frac{n_b}{2}\}} F(\vec{x}). \quad (9)$$

Step 4: Update the velocity and position vectors in accordance with the PSO update laws

$$\vec{v}_i^{k+1} = c_0 \vec{v}_i^k + c_1 r_{2,i}^k (\vec{x}_{p,i}^k - \vec{x}_i^k) + c_2 r_{3,i}^k (\vec{x}_{b,i}^k - \vec{x}_i^k), \quad (10)$$

$$\vec{x}_i^{k+1} = c_0 \vec{v}_i^k + \vec{x}_i^k, \quad (11)$$

where c_0 (inertia factor), c_1 (cognitive scaling factor), c_2 (social scaling factor).

Step 5: Return the optimal solution if the termination criterion is satisfied. If not, proceed to Step 2.

C. Numerical Examples

The major purpose of this section is to show that the suggested approach is competitive in the ν -gap model reduction problem when compared to existing methods. The BMI-based technique was suggested and used to tackle a number of model reduction difficulties in [5], one of which is as follows:

$$P(s) = \frac{s+2}{(0.0025s+1)^2(0.1s+1)(0.05s^2-1)}, \quad (12)$$

$$R(s) = \frac{x_1s+x_2}{s^2+x_3s+x_4}. \quad (13)$$

The objective of this problem was to find $\mathbf{x}_i = (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4)^T$ that minimizes $\delta_{L2}(P(s), R(s))$ [5], which was computed as (2) without consideration of the WNC. Their method has the disadvantage of not being able to manage WNC during the optimization process, as well as a significant reliance on the initial set of candidate solutions. Therefore,

Fig. 2 Convergence property of objective function values in each trials

TABLE II Best objective function values in each trials

	Objective function value: $\delta_\nu(P(s), R(s))$			
	Best	Worst	Mean	Standard deviation
Sootla et al. [6]	0.2896	1	0.7304	0.2824
This paper	0.0965	0.0965	0.0965	0.00

the comparison was conducted without WNC to discuss the problem of high dependence on initialization. On the other hand, the distributed-PSO [8] is introduced to handle the above problem. In this case, the number of particles is set as $n_p = 100$, and the maximum iteration number is $k_{max} = 1000$. The designed factors are set as $c_0 = 0.73$ and $c_1 = c_2 = 2.05$. The number of neighbors of the particles is set as $n_b = 10$. The search space is set as $\mathbb{D} := \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^4 : -10^3 \leq x_i \leq 10^3$. Then, the BMI-based algorithm [5] and the proposed algorithm are run with a random initial setting of variable \mathbf{x} . Fig. 1 depicts the variations in objective values over the 1000 iterations of 50 trials. This figure demonstrates that the proposed PSO-based method can find the optimal solution more reliably than the method proposed in [5]. This is further supported by a comparison of the results in Table I. These demonstrate that the suggested approach provides a solution that is more optimum and less dependent on the initial set.

Next, the strategy proposed in [6] is used to solve the problem whose objective function is set to (5). The basic technique of [6] is to solve the problem by minimizing γ as follows:

$$\delta_\nu = \sqrt{1 - 1/\gamma_{opt}^2}, \quad \gamma_{opt} \leq \gamma. \quad (14)$$

Thus, δ_ν in (5) is minimized as γ_{opt} is reduced. However, since γ provides an upper bound on γ_{opt} , reducing γ throughout the optimization process does not necessarily lead to a reduction in γ_{opt} . For the purpose of illustrating this issue, the procedure in [6] is executed 30 times with random initial values for variable \mathbf{x} , with one initial value containing the set acquired via the Hankel Approximation as explained in that research. The results are presented in Fig. 2 which demonstrates that during optimization, the objective function value γ constantly declines whereas the value δ_ν does not. Furthermore, the best

Fig. 3 Step response of full-order and reduced-order models in unit feedback

TABLE III Comparison of reduced-order models

Models	Objective function value		Response error	
	Best	Worst	ISE	IAE
ν -gap (5)	0.0014	2.9689	0.13×10^{-2}	1.5312
This paper (6)	0.0036	0.3809	0.43×10^{-6}	0.0524

objective function value δ_ν throughout all trials is inferior to the value of the proposed technique employing PSO given in Table II.

Although the proposed approach outperforms other conventional methods for solving the ν -gap model reduction problem, it has drawbacks such as response error in a unit feedback system. Therefore, instead of the ν -gap (5), the objective function (6) is developed in this study. The validity of the proposed objective function is proven by using the model reduction benchmark problem [9], which is a 48th-order building model. Because the system's Hankel singular values are computed as (15) in decreasing order, it may be appropriate to reduce the order to the fourth; for $i \in [1, 2, \dots, 48]$,

$$\sigma_i = (0.25, 0.24, 0.19, 0.19, 0.07, \dots), \quad (15)$$

The reduced-order model obtained by employing the objective function (5) is as follows:

$$R_{(5)}(s) = \frac{0.009s^3 - 0.058s^2 + 0.8153s - 3.687}{s^4 + 3.11s^3 + 195.3s^2 + 248s + 4314}. \quad (16)$$

On the other hand, the reduced-order model obtained using objective (6) is as follows:

$$R_{(6)}(s) = \frac{0.0139s^3 + 0.0942s^2 + 1.195s}{s^4 + 20.36s^3 + 314.6s^2 + 730.9s + 7587}. \quad (17)$$

To validate performance by comparing errors, the following standard performance indices are used: Integral Square Error (ISE) and Integral Absolute Error (IAE).

$$ISE = \int_0^\infty [P(t) - R(t)]^2 dt, \quad IAE = \int_0^\infty |P(t) - R(t)| dt,$$

where $P(t)$ and $R(t)$ are the unit step responses of original and reduced-order model, respectively. The step responses of reduced-order models with a unit-feedback structure are

then compared to the original 48th-order model in Fig. 3. This figure demonstrates that the response error between the original model and the reduced-order model obtained with ν -gap is significant. One of the reasons is that the ν -gap serves as a performance boundary rather than a direct correlation between models. In contrast, the proposed objective function (6) identifies a reduced-order model with step response in unit feedback that is more comparable to the original model. The result summarized in Table III also supports the above facts. These demonstrate that, in terms of response error in model reduction, the proposed objective function is preferable to the conventional ν -gap. Despite not being better at response matching, the ν -gap technique has the advantage of providing a closed-loop stability criterion. Therefore, designers can achieve the best results by utilizing (6) as the objective function and using a specific value related to the stability margin as a constraint in ν -gap (5).

III. CONCLUSION

A meta-heuristic algorithm for model order reduction utilizing the ν -gap metric is proposed in this study. The distributed PSO is used as the key tool for identifying the reduced-order model in both conventional and novel modified ν -gap metric-based optimization issues. The suggested algorithm's effectiveness is evaluated using the benchmark model order reduction problem, which reveals that it gives superior objective function values and relies less on the initial set of candidate solutions. Furthermore, an objective function based on our modified ν -gap metric provides an effective means of dealing with response error for unit feedback structures when model order is reduced. The validity of such a novel objective function is proven by comparing its performance to that of the usual ν -gap-based reduced-order model.

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Designing Photo-Voltaic Array Layouts using a Genetic Algorithm

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Abstract—This work deals with obtaining the best layout design of Photo-voltaic (PV) arrays to achieve the maximum benefit of captured solar energy. The arrays are composed of several PV cells that are connected by a cable grid. The most important aspect of planning the layout is to optimize the reduction of operational costs and at the same time, maximize energy capture. Three main variables of photo-voltaic arrays are addressed, the distance between PV panels to save unnecessary cables, the total shade on the array that affects by the distance between cells, and the angle-of-incidence from the irradiance. A Genetic Algorithm as a heuristic methodology of candidate solutions is used, which optimizes all variables simultaneously. The algorithm achieves the best solution by delineating a penalty and permutation to assess the fitness of the solutions. Each solution is evaluated by the energy it captures. Simulations and design examples are depicted to provide the systems competence.

I. INTRODUCTION

As part of sustainable development, natural gas, crude oil, and coal are being replaced with different types of renewable energy resources. For fossil fuel and nuclear resources to be successfully replaced, a combination of hydro power, Photo-Voltaic, wind, geothermal, and biomass-based resources are required. Hence, renewable energy portfolios are highly dependent on geographic location and weather conditions. Industry has made the PV power generators a feasible alternative energy resource that complements other energy sources in hybrid energy systems [1]. The trend of accelerated use of PV is associated with the efficiency of solar cells as well as improvements in the technology of solar panels. The Photo-voltaic modules use light energy from the sun to generate electricity through the photo-voltaic effect. The majority of modules use wafer-based crystalline silicon cells or thin-film cells [2], [3]. The structural (load carrying) member of a module can either be the top layer or the back layer. The PV grid is connected and performs as both a single operation in a distributed generation systems, or as an autonomous system. Such characteristics makes the PV systems a suitable alternative for mobile applications but also as a stand-alone power supply structure in isolated locations [4]. With the development of distributed systems, the generation of power from PV sources became a substantial resource of energy with high demand [5], [6]. Moreover, PV systems have become an alternative challenge for co-generation in urban environments. A supply of small loads such as office lighting (light-to-light) and residential comfort devices such as air-conditioned plants

[7], [8].

Alternative array interconnection topologies have been proposed for reducing mismatch losses [9]–[11]. Serial and parallel topologies are the two basic configurations as depicted in Fig. 1a and 1b, with the disadvantage that the current and voltage under mismatch conditions are below the desired values. Parallel-connected PV elements produce higher power during partial shading than serial-connected ones, since the overall current is the sum of the individual currents and voltage does not change much. There is, however, a greater flow of current in parallel connected elements, so power losses and voltage drops are higher and cabling is generally more expensive. Serial-parallel (SP) connections are the most common type in actual PV arrays. It is obtained by connecting solar modules in series to form a string (required to reach the voltage ranges of inverter inputs); the strings are then connected in parallel to increase the total current (as shown in Figure 1c). Figure 1d shows a Total-Cross-Tied (TCT)

Fig. 1: PV array topology: Series array (a), parallel array (b), series-parallel array (c), total-cross tied array(d), bridge-link array(e) and honey-comber (f) [10]

configuration consisting of paralleling modules so that their voltages are the same and their currents are added together; the paralleled modules are then connected in series. Despite the fact that SP and TCT modules provide the same power value under uniform conditions, the TCT topology reduces the overall effect of mismatch. By using the Bridge-Link(BL) topology, (seen in Fig. 1e), half of the interconnections of the TCT topology can be avoided, which reduces cable losses

and wiring installation time. In larger installations, the TCT arrangement may be easier to wire due to its simplicity. The TCT and BL topologies have been combined in the Honeycomb (HC) configuration (Fig. 1f), however, this configuration is less resistant to mismatches.

When designing PV layouts, two significant elements must be taken into account: First, the spectrum (spectral distribution) of sunlight as detailed in [12], [13]. Second, the optical characteristics of photo-voltaic modules or pyrometers defined by the solar angle-of-incidence (AOI).

A grid-connected PV array requires an optimized layout [10]. The number and configuration of inverters determine performance, reliability, and mismatch rejection, and have an impact on overall power costs and efficiency. Four architectural types are commonly employed [14]:

- Central-inverter architecture - all the arrays are connected to the input of the common unique inverter. This solution is usually simpler and cheaper but has the disadvantage that mismatch losses are higher. A single inverter is usually stored in a proper housing providing more stable environmental conditions.
- String-inverter architecture - every string has its own inverter thus performances under partial shading condition are increased, but relatively costly.
- Multi-string inverter architecture – a DC/DC boost converter is installed in each string. All the DC/DC outputs require a common DC bus, and is finally connected to the DC/AC stage. This solution combines both the advantages of the cheaper central-inverter architecture and the better performances of the string-inverter architecture.
- Micro-inverter architecture - each module has its own inverter and all the micro-inverter outputs are connected to a unique AC bus. The disadvantages are higher costs of each micro-inverter and limited reliability due to varying weather conditions.

A central inverter architecture was chosen, in this work, as it is easy to construct and affordable. Mismatch conditions and energy losses will be compensated by optimizing the layout configuration.

When designing PV arrays, the main challenge is to deal with a large number of possibilities and permutations in a large search space. [13] proposes a programmed configuration (PC) that selects a given configuration based on predefined rules. The changes are made based on the device and its characteristics as provided by a lookup table for limited array designs. An algorithm using sorting algorithms (SA) is developed in [15]. The search is considered acceptable when it meets a given criterion via two approaches. Initially, using a bubble sort algorithm to switch the adaptive PV arrays one at a time, then analyzing the total value. The second approach is based on predictions of the power levels in each row of the fixed solar arrays. In [2], Louwen et al. present a solution using brute force (BF) algorithm, which tests every possible configuration, thus taking a long time to compute. Various heuristics are described in [16]–[19], in addition, array interconnection

topologies for reducing mismatch losses are discussed in [10], [20], [21]. In [22] the zenith AOI is calculated taking into account the affect of solar spectral irradiance on the incidence angle. Since this method relies on pre-measured and empirical parameters, the solution is complex.

The aim of this work is to develop a design system based on constraints and requirements. The restrictions include the space PV panels must occupy, the characteristics of PV cells, the conditions in the real world, and mismatched shading between the panels. The purpose of this system is to determine the best panel layout and AOI for each panel.

A. Shading calculations

Due to the sun’s movement across the sky, light strikes the PV modules at different angles throughout the day, causing the solar zenith and azimuth to vary. There are also strong seasonal variations in the course of zenith and azimuth [23]. Both of these parameters are crucial for calculating how PV arrays should be configured. It is sufficient to know the precise angle to determine how much sunlight will be received throughout the year [13], [24]. To determine the AOI between the beam

Fig. 2: Shade Calculation Example

component of solar irradiance and the PV module surface, the solar zenith, azimuth, slope, and orientation of the PV module are combined, as depicted in Figure 2. AOI affects the amount of light coupled into PV cells, which directly affects the efficiency of the PV cells. Calculating the zenith angle requires knowing the latitude and the declination angle [2] and is calculated using Eq. (1)

$$\cos\theta = \cos\theta_z \cdot \cos\beta + \sin\theta_z \cdot \sin\beta \cdot \cos(\phi - \phi_z) \quad (1)$$

where θ is the AOI, $\cos\theta_z$ is the solar zenith, β is the PV module slope, ϕ_z is the solar azimuth and ϕ is the orientation of the PV modules (by definition $\phi = 0$ for a panel oriented to the south in the northern hemisphere). The latitude angle (defined below) ranges from 0 at the Equator to 90 (north or south) at the poles as detailed in Eq. (2)

$$\text{zenithangle} = \text{latitude} - \text{declination} \quad (2)$$

A celestial point is located on the celestial sphere by declination (δ), one of two angles in the equatorial coordinate system while the second angle represents the hour.

$$\sin\delta = 0.39795 \cdot \cos(0.9853(N - 173)) \quad (3)$$

Declination’s angle is measured north or south of the celestial equator Eq. (3) where N is the number of days calculated from

January 1. The shade of a PV cell is determined by a number of parameters, including its slope angle, AOI, distance from neighboring cells, and length and width. The shade for each solution or permutation is calculated by dividing the space by the number of solutions. Next, an estimate of the shade is made based on neighboring solution sequences.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Shade} &= \beta \cdot [A - D - B] \\ A &= \sin\beta \cdot \text{Length}_{\text{Cell}} \cdot \tan(90 - \theta) \\ B &= \text{Length}_{\text{Cell}} - \text{Length}_{\text{Cell}} \cdot \cos\beta \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Eq. (4) defines the function determines the shade between PV cells, where θ is the AOI, β is the slope angle, D is the distance between the cells and $\text{Length}_{\text{Cell}}$ either the cell's length or width, depending on the azimuth to the sun.

II. GENETIC ALGORITHM

Genetic Algorithms (GA) are Evolutionary Algorithms (EA) based on the principle of natural selection, recombination and survival of the fittest. [25]. GAs have the advantage of being stochastic and methodologically sound, In Addition, they perform parallel computations and offers flexibility, adaptation, and global search capabilities. GAs can be used to solve problems containing objective functions with multiple models and constraints.

GAs attempt to find the best solution to a problem by manipulating a population of candidate solutions based on fitness functions. They are based on a set of criteria that evaluates the solutions. A better solution is more likely to reproduce, thereby generating a new population. After several generations, fit individuals dominate the current population, increasing the quality of the generated solutions [26]. While an EA does not guarantee a global optimal solution, it usually finds extremely good and useful solutions to relatively complex problems. The offspring's population can be generated using a variety of genetic operators, such as crossovers, mutations, and reinsertions, among others. In this work, GA parameters were assessed and used to model the best solution framework based on a detailed analysis. The following is a basic genetic algorithm:

- Start: Generate a random population of n chromosomes (a suitable solution for the problem).
- Fitness: Evaluate the fitness $f(x)$ of each chromosome x in the population.
- New population: Create a new population by repeating following steps until the new population is complete:
- Selection: select two parent chromosomes from the population according to their fitness value.
- Crossover: with a crossover probability, cross over the parents to form a new offspring. If no crossover is performed, the offspring will be an exact copy of its parents.
- Mutation: with a mutation probability, mutate new offspring at each locus (the position of a gene in a chromosome).
- Replacement: Insertion: place new offspring in the new population.

- Test: If the end condition is satisfying, stop, and return the best solution in the current population.

Every generation (iteration) of evolution starts with a random set of individuals, which are examined and evaluated. Once the evaluation of the individual has been altered or mutated, the fitness of the objective function is evaluated.

A. GA Parameters: Solution Encoding

For this NP-hard problem, a permutation encoding procedure is used to represent a solution that can be simulated as a sequence of solutions [27]. In the toy problem example, a chromosome structure consists of nine cells, six of which are illustrated in Figure 3. Every Cell includes the following parameters: cell slope angle, cable distance to the next cell and shade percentage.

Fig. 3: Chromosome Representation

B. Evaluation Function

The evaluation function is the fitness of the objective function. Formulating the total fitness function involves the following steps:

- 1) Total mass of cable distance between cells, normalized between 0-1 using Eq. (5).

$$\sum_{\text{Each-cell}} \frac{\text{CellCableLength}}{\text{MaxValue} - \text{MinValue}} \quad (5)$$

- 2) Shading that each cell causes on the neighboring cells, using the distance between the cells, azimuth, AOI, and the cell's length/width. The values are normalized by dividing the shade length with the cell length as defined in Eq. (6)

$$\sum_{\text{Each-cell}} \frac{\text{CellShade}}{\text{MaxValue} - \text{MinValue}} \quad (6)$$

- 3) AOI of the cell which affects the shade relative to its neighbor PV cell. The AOI of the best performance is defined in Eq. (7)

$$\sum_{\text{Each-cell}} \frac{\text{ABS}(\text{cellangle} - \text{bestangle})}{\text{MaxValue} - \text{MinValue}} \quad (7)$$

- 4) Calculating the total penalty for each attribute. The total amount of distance is divided by the solution of the sequence length, and normalize using Eq. (8).

$$Distance_{pen} = \frac{TotalDistance}{SequenceLength} \cdot DistancePenalty \quad (8)$$

- 5) The AOI penalty calculated and normalized by using Eq. (9)

$$Angle_{pen} = \frac{TotalAnglediff}{SequenceLength} \cdot AnglePenalty \quad (9)$$

- 6) Shade penalty calculated by using in Eq. (10)

$$Shade_{pen} = \frac{TotalShade}{SequenceLength} \cdot ShadePenalty \quad (10)$$

- 7) Solution penalty is the sum using : Eq. (11)

$$Chromosome_{penalty} = Distance_{pen} + Angle_{pen} + Shade_{pen} \quad (11)$$

- 8) The fitness of a solution is proportional to its penalty, this means, that the lower the penalty, the better the fit. The highest possible penalty of each transition is 1. Dividing the total $Chromosome_{penalty}$ by the sequence length, results a penalty range between 0-1. This is calculated by using Eq. (12)

$$Chrom_{fitness} = 1 - Chrom_{penalty} \quad (12)$$

Two possible termination options exist: An a-priory number of generations determined, or a satisfactory fitness level. In this work a defined number of iteration is used, based on tests and simulations conducted and is discusses in section 3.

C. Selection, Crossover and Mutation

In this work the the Roulette Selection method was chosen, as it serves as a fitness proportionate selection.

Fig. 4: Mutation Rate simulation

Selection: This is achieved by dividing the fitness of a selection by the total fitness of all the selections, thereby normalizing them to 1. This avoids getting trapped in a local minimum.

Crossover: The single point crossover operator was chosen,

Fig. 5: Elitism simulation results

as from testing performed no critical differences were encountered by using any other crossover method. The single point was chosen random.

Mutation: The Reverse Sequence Mutation (RSM) is used by creating two random integers i, j such as: $i = \text{random}(0, \text{sequenceLength} - 1)$ and $j = \text{random}(i, \text{sequenceLength} - 1)$. Mutation is used with a certain probability, simulations were performed and compared different mutation rates to find the best results. Figure 4 depicts the comparison among different mutation values. Simulations were done using the following values: Azimuth=120, Latitude=31, Longitude=35, cell_length=5, cell_width=3, area size=20x20. The best mutation percentage value found was 0.1 which resulted the highest population fitness.

D. Replacement and Population Size

Replacement is the decision method in which individuals of the current population stay in a population and which are replaced for the next generation. In order to determine which

Fig. 6: Semi-Elitism simulation with various Modulo rates

method and values would result the best replacement, tests and simulation were conducted. The data-set used in the test is: Azimuth=120, Latitude=31, Longitude=35, cell_length=5, cell_width=3, area size=20x20. The two methods Pure Elitism and Semi-pure Elitism were tested, varying elitism rate, cycle and population size (only partial results are presented).

Fig. 7: Generation simulations with various values

Figure 5 depicts the Elitism results with population of 500 chromosomes in the population. It is obvious that the results do not converge and are not sufficient for the replacement task. Semi-Pure Elitism resulted in too rapid convergence, resulting in a local maximum.

In this work, a combination of semi-pure elitism and random replacement was implemented. In practice, a new chromosome was inserted randomly into the population and the less fittest was removed. Moreover, the method defined here, determines a certain number of generations which the semi-pure elitism will be performed, and a random replacement is implemented. Figure 6 depicts the results of performing the method every 2,3,5, or 10 iterations. As depicted in the figure, the use semi-pure elitism every third generation resulted the best fitness. To achieve the best population size and the number generation as a stopping criteria, simulations were done. The results are depicted in Figure 7 yielding that iterating 100 generation provides a sufficient stopping value.

Algorithm 1 details the pseudo code of Sequence Fitness Evaluation and results the Fitness Value for each candidate solution. The parameters of the algorithm relate to the fitness function calculations detailed in section 2.2. As part of the GA process, the fitness function serves as a key criterion for assessing design quality.

Fig. 8: Generation optimization Population size=1000, Generation size=100

III. CASE STUDIES AND RESULTS

In order to evaluate the final solution, the total shade of the design sequence is calculated by going through every cell and

Algorithm 1: Sequence Fitness Evaluation

```

Input:  $Angle\_Penalty = 0$ ;  $Dist\_Penalty = 0$ ;  $Shade\_Penalty = 0$ ;
1   CalculatingBestcombinedAOIandSpacelayout;
2   CalculatingBestShadeAOISolution;
3   for  $i$  in  $range(Constant\_Sequence)$ : do
4      $Temp.Angle = (Sequence[i].Angle - Best\_Angle)$ ;
5      $Angle.Penalty = Temp.Angle/GA\_Constant\_Angle\_Difference$ ;
6      $Angle.Penalty+ = Temp\_angle\_penalty$ ;
7      $Temp\_Shade = Sequence[i].shade$ ;
8      $Shade.Penalty+ = Temp - Shade$ ;
   end
9   CalculatingBestDistanceSolution;
10  for  $Range(Constant\_Sequence\_Length - 1)$ : do
11     $Temp\_Distance = Sequence[i].Distance\_to\_next / GA\_Const.Distance\_Dif$ ;
12     $Distance.Penalty+ = Temp\_Distance$ ;
   end
13   $Total\_Dist\_Penalty = (Dist\_Penalty/(GA\_Const.Sequence.Length - 1)) * Constant.Distance.Penalty$ ;
14   $Total.Angle.Penalty = (Angle.Penalty/GA\_Constant.Seq.Length) * Constant.Angle.Penalty$ ;
15   $Fitness = 1 - (Total.Angle.Penalty + Total.Distance.Penalty + Total.Shade.Penalty)$ ;
16   $Penalty = Total.Distance.Penalty + Total.Shade.Penalty + Total.Angle.Penalty$ ;
Output: Fitness Value

```

Results:

Best fitness: 0.871
Average fitness: 410.442

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Fig. 9: Design results for Population size = 1000, Generation size=100

calculating how it affects the other cells. The azimuth angle to the sun, slope angle of the cell, AOI, distance from the cell, and cell length and width are all considered, as detailed in section 1.1. According to the previous section, population size = 1000 and generations = 100 were the best parameters. The output display is also affected by the design space and

Fig. 10: Population size = 1000 Generation size=100 Area size = 20, normalized fitness value= 0.924 and average fitness value=851.077

Fig. 11: Population size = 1000 Generation size=100 Area size = 50, normalized fitness value= 0.921 and average fitness value=850.22

Fig. 12: Population size = 1000 Generation size=100 Area size = 100, normalized fitness value= 0.913 and average fitness value=786.45

azimuth, which are controlled by the user. The paper evaluates each design use case based on two factors: first, the GA by means of an optimization process, and then the design space by means of a shading factor.

Figure 8 illustrates the generative process of population fitness and how it improves with each iteration until it reaches a final solution with generation 100. Figure 9 shows the design space

and the resultant PV layout, as well as the result of two major assessing factors: First, the average fitness that indicates the algorithm's progressing in a positive generative direction and evaluates the improvement. This value is calculated relative to the number of generations, in this case 1000, expressing the confidence of reaching the best solution. Second, the best fitness value achieved and normalized between [0-1]. The system

Fig. 13: Population size = 1000 Generation size=100 Azimuth = 50, normalized fitness value= 0.892 and average fitness value=811.6

Fig. 14: Population size = 1000 Generation size=100 Azimuth = 300, normalized fitness value= 0.87 and average fitness value=793.75

preserves and indicates the best value achieved and yields its variable as planning criteria. In this example the normalized fitness value= 0.81 and average fitness value=441.23

The right side of the figure shows the actual design outcome of the design variables (detailed in Algorithm 1): the best AOI (written above the square), and the layout of the space (seen on the arcs connecting the panels). The layouts, angles and the distances are not symmetrical and result totally different values. Five case studies are presented, three where the area is constrained and two where the azimuth is defined by the user. The following examples combine the features described in Figure 8 and Figure 9.

Case study 1: Area size = 20x20 is depicted in Figure 10

Case study 2: Area size = 50x50 is depicted in Figure 11

Case study 3: Area size = 100x100 is depicted in Figure 12

Case study 4: Area size = 100x100 and Azimuth = 50 is depicted in Figure 13

Case study 5: Area size = 100x100 and Azimuth = 300 is depicted in Figure 14

All figures from Figure 10 to Figure 14 are the results for the five case studies, as explained above. In the caption, the fitness value indicates the quality of the solution.

By comparing Figure 10, Figure 11 and Figure 12, it can be seen that the convergence of the solution differs greatly. With an area of 20x20, it is very constrained, leading to a solution in the early stages and iterations do not result better solutions. Due to the small search space provided by the designer, the layout options are severely constrained. Figure 11 and Figure 12 provide larger layout spaces, i.e., a larger search space. Increasing the population fitness variants requires more computational resourcefulness as indicated by the number of generations needed for reaching a high fitness. Also interesting is the development of the graph.

When considering the PV layouts, the smaller areas are much more constrained and the shading has much higher impact on the solution space. In larger areas the fitness is achieved in a less constraint manner. Azimuth has the same influence on the design space attaining different results. As an example, the cable length between solar panels in a 20X20 area is considerably shorter than the cable length between solar panels in a 100X100 area.

Examining the computational complexity of the proposed approach yields the following results: space complexity is $O(N \cdot M)$, while N is the number of cells, and M is the number

of solutions The complexity is $O(M \cdot N \cdot N)$ where N is the amount of sub populations created. This efficiency in the system's computational complexity provides the ability and flexibility to implement the system without special computation adaptations.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

During the course of this work a novel and efficient flexible system for PV layout design was investigated. The system receives an input of the space at hand, characteristics of PV cells and various constraints. A range of true actual world characteristics serve for formulation the overall cost function, and yields the best design layout of panels and their AOI. A GA software was developed using heuristic optimization procedure which creates a random initial population and optimizes the solution until it reaches a dynamic user defined generations. This solution is then transformed into a practical real physical layouts. The method employs a penalty-based system that optimizes penalty evaluations, resulting in a higher improvement than the original best solution. Since fitness and penalties are interconnected in the solution, fitness increases throughout the generations, while penalties decrease. According to our evaluations, 100 generations will be sufficient to achieve a vast improvement without adding unnecessary complexity.

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Concurrent Real-Time optimization of detecting unexpected tasks in IoT design process using GA

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Abstract— In this paper we present a genetic algorithm for concurrent real-time optimization for detecting unexpected tasks in IoT design process. The process can be split into two phases which impact each other in real-time. Modification of one phase modifies the second one. The algorithm detects unexpected tasks as a connection of parts of predicted tasks. Therefore, there can exist more than one way to resolve the unexpected situation. The algorithm searches for optimal solution making concurrent optimization of two phases of the design process. Use of genetic algorithm helps also to eliminate connections of subtasks which do not give a good result.

Keywords— optimization, genetic algorithm, artificial intelligence, Internet of Things, unexpected tasks

I. INTRODUCTION

Development of new technologies requires development of new tools for optimization. In this paper we investigate an optimization problem which appeared in the Internet of Things (IoT) [1] design process. This problem is related to assignment of unexpected tasks for embedded systems [2][3][4]. Internet of Things (IoT) is a network consisting of connected “things” like: physical systems, sensors, communication protocols, embedded systems, etc. The elements of the network should be uniquely identified. One of popular methods of identification are RMID (Radio Frequency IDentification) tags [6]. Some elements of IoT network are able to perform/execute tasks. Such elements can be divided into two groups: Processing Resources (PRs) and Communication Resources (CRs). PRs are responsible for tasks execution. CRs provide communication between connected PRs. PRs can be further divided into two groups: Dedicated Resources (DRs) which are able to execute only one specific type of task, and Universal Resources (URs) which can execute more than one type of task. IoT concepts are widely used in “smart” solutions like smart cities [7][8], smart transport [9], smart houses [5][10] and many others [11]. The designers of IoT systems concentrate on communication [6] [12] and security problems [13][14][15].

The design methods, like for example [16], do not investigate unexpected situations and concentrate only on extending IoT network with new elements. When IoT network is designed, modifications to a new situation is not always possible as the network cannot be freely extended by new resources. The problem of unexpected tasks was described by Górski and Ogorzałek [2][4] but only for the case of embedded systems. The strongest constraint of their algorithm is that all of the information about unexpected tasks must be given. In [3] authors propose an algorithm to detect unexpected tasks for embedded systems. The algorithm finds unexpected tasks as connections of some numbers of subtasks of predicted tasks. The authors indicated that unexpected situation can be resolved in different ways, but did not search for optimal set of the subtasks. Therefore, the algorithm was

finding the first solution, not necessary the best one. In this paper we also concentrate on situation when unexpected tasks can be presented as a set of some numbers of subtasks of other tasks that need to be executed by the network. However it is not known at the beginning which set of the subtasks is better. What is more, it is not known which sets of subtasks can be even equal to execute unexpected task. Therefore, the problem can be divided into two phases. The first phase is responsible for finding number of subtasks necessary to solve unexpected situation. The second phase finds the optimal assignment of subtasks to the resources. However every subtask can be executed on many elements of IoT network which can consist of many resources. Every resource can have different values of optimizing parameters for each subtasks. Thus we would not have been able to find the optimal set of subtasks if those two phases would have been optimized separately. Moreover, separate optimization of those phases does not give the information about optimization criteria. Therefore, these two phases must be optimized concurrently. It has to be noted that optimization in each phase impacts the other in real-time. Further description of the problem is given in chapter 4.

In this paper we propose a genetic algorithm to solve the optimization problem of two concurrent phases which impact each-other in real-time during the IoT design process. Such algorithms [17] start with an initial population of individuals, and using genetic operators: selection, crossover and mutation generate new populations of individuals. Presented algorithm enables to eliminate connections of subtasks which do not solve unexpected situations. The algorithm chooses the best connection of subtasks and concurrently assigns them to resources. Genetic algorithms are known for being able to escape local minima of optimized function in the parameter space. Further, using genetic solution to the problem investigated in this paper can help to generate different set of subtasks to solve unexpected situation.

The paper is organized as follows: chapter 2 gives basic notations used in the paper, chapter 3 describes representation of IoT and the IoT design process. Chapter 4 contains general presentation of new optimization problem that needs to be solved. In chapter 5 the algorithm is described. Chapter 6 gives the description of experiments. In chapter 7 conclusions are discussed and future work is also considered.

II. BASIC NOTATION

PR – processing resource
DR – dedicated resource
UR – universal resource
CR – communication resource
 T_i – i number of task
 $G=(T,E)$ – task graph
 E – edge in the graph
 $e_{ij} \in E$ – egde between tasks T_i and T_j

- t – time of execution
- ts – starting moment of execution
- c – cost of execution
- tc_{i,j} – communication time between tasks T_i and T_j
- b – bandwidth of Communication Resource
- d – amount of data that need to be send between two connected tasks
- n – number of predicted tasks
- u – number of unexpected tasks
- v – number of processing resources
- m – number of universal resources
- o – number of dedicated resources
- Π – number of individuals in each generation

III. PRELIMINARIES

In this paper we use the concept of task graph G=(T,E) representation to describe behavior of an IoT network. Some elements of the network (especially embedded systems) execute tasks (T). Tasks are represented in the graph as nodes. Each edge e_{ij} ∈ E represents amount of data that needs to be transferred between two connected tasks T_i and T_j ∈ T. Fig. 1 presents an example of a part of task graph.

Fig. 1. Example of a task graph with inserted unexpedted tasks

Table I presents an example of a resource database for the part of the network described by the task graph form Fig.1.

TABLE I. RESOURCE DATABASE

	UR1 C=500		UR2 C=400		DR1		DR2	
	t	c	t	c	t	c	t	c
T1	150	7	125	5	30	150	20	350
T2	80	2	50	3	20	100	10	180
T3	300	22	350	19	100	300	80	450
T4	120	24	150	22	12	128	8	350
T5	230	32	200	28	55	45	63	40
T6	30	25	60	18	32	120	40	100
CR1, b=2	c=4		c=3		c=12			
CR2, b=10	C=5		c=4		c=18			

The example consists of 6 tasks: T1, T2, T3, T4, T5 and T6. Each task can be executed by a single resource. Resource can be a single element of the IoT or a part of an element. Tasks T6 T2, and T3, T4 are parallel and can be executed at the same time by different resources. Each CR has a bandwidth b which describes amount of data that can be transferred in a time unit. The tasks are characterized by two parameters: time and cost of its execution on each resource. DRs are fast but expensive. URs are cheaper but slower. The IoT designer must find the compromise between time and cost of the network.

The target IoT network must meet time constrains – all the tasks in the network must finish their execution before the maximum allowed time:

$$\forall_{e_{i,j}} ts_j \geq ts_i + t_{i,r_i} + tc_{i,j} \quad (1)$$

where:

$$tc_{i,j} = \left\lceil \frac{d_{i,j}}{b_{CR_{i,j}}} \right\rceil \quad (2)$$

where: CR_{i,j} is communication resource which connects PRs executing tasks T_i and T_j. If T_i and T_j are executed on the same resource transmission time is equal to zero.

Every task presented in the graph from Fig. 1 can be divided into some number of subtasks.

Unexpected tasks appear when IoT network is ready and no new element cannot be added to the network. They can appear at any moment of the work of the network and must be inserted into task graph. If the target IoT network consists of m universal resources, p communication resources, the task graph contains n tasks and there are u unexpected tasks, the total cost of the network (C'_o) can be described by the following formula:

$$C'_o = \sum_{i=1}^m C_{UR_i} + \sum_{j=1}^n C_j + \sum_{k=1}^p \sum_{l=1}^{P_k} C_{CR_k,PC_l} + \sum_{s=1}^u C_l \quad (3)$$

where: CR_k is a type of k-th communication resource, which is connected to P_k processing resource, and PC_l is a type of l-th PR connected to CR_k.

IV. NEW PROBLEM STATEMRNT

The problem which we investigate in this paper is the concurrent optimization of two phases which impact each-other in real-time. The first phase is responsible for providing the parameters to optimize. The second phase optimizes the parameters given in the first phase and checks if the selection made in the first phase was correct. Only the verification in the second phase can give the answer if the selection made in the first phase can even give a result. If not, the optimized parameters must be changed. However, if optimizing parameters are changed the optimization in the second phase must also be changed or even repeated from the beginning. Therefore, it is not possible to optimize the phases separately. However, in case of different choice of optimizing parameters how can we know which choice is better? To solve this problem we must assume that there exists at least one common parameter for each of the solutions which allows to compare the results. Therefore, as it can be observed, the optimization problem is multicriterial:

$$f(x) = \min(f(x_1), f(x_2), \dots, f(x_n)) \quad (4)$$

$$x_1 \dots x_n \in S \quad (5)$$

75 where: S is a set of possible solutions.

For better presentation of the problem let us consider a simple example. Let us assume that we would like to pick up an apple from a tree. There are several possibilities to do that. We can climb the tree, shake the tree, use a ladder or a tool. Every choice gives us different parameters to optimize. If we choose to climb the tree we can optimize the path. Choosing to shake the tree makes us optimize a point of shaking and a force. However, the main question is how to decide which way is better without picking up the apple? Therefore, there must be at least one parameter which is common for every choice. In that case such a parameter can be, for example, a time of getting the apple. The problem can be split into two phases. First phase chooses the way of picking up the apple. The chosen way specifies the parameters to optimize. The second phase optimizes chosen parameters. However, during the second phase it can be found that it is impossible to pick the apple according to the way chosen in the first phase. What is very important, such information was not given at the beginning of the process. In the analysed case, such a situation can appear if the decision was to climb a tree and after some distance it was observed that it was impossible to continue climbing. The second phase modifies the first one. Modification of the first phase (changing a way of picking up an apple) gives different parameters to optimize and thus immediately changes the second phase. Another question is: should all the processes be repeated in such a case or maybe it is better to connect performed steps with another way of obtaining the apple?

We believe that such an easy example gives a good insight into the problem that is investigated in this paper. In the next chapter we define the optimization problem for the IoT network design process.

A. Concurrent Real-Time Optimization in IoT Design Process

We assume that during work IoT network encounters unexpected situations. Therefore, the network must execute some unexpected tasks. There is no upfront information about those tasks. The only information which is given is associated with the target (what kind of data is needed to be obtained). Therefore, to solve this problem all expected tasks must be split into possible number of subtasks. In this paper we concentrate on situation where unexpected tasks can be solved as connection of some subtasks of other tasks. The optimization is divided into two phases. The first phase is responsible for choosing the number and the types of subtasks. The second phase gives the parameters to optimize and searches for their optimal values by making tasks assignment. Typical goals of optimization can be the cost of the network, time of execution of all the tasks, power consumption, etc. The optimization process of both phases must be done concurrently. Otherwise, if the phases would be optimized sequentially, the first phase could only concentrate on the number of subtasks. That information is not necessarily important for IoT designer. Without a selection of the subtasks, task assignment cannot be made. The second phase also verifies the choice made in the first phase. If anything changes in one of the phases it will affect the other one in real-time. To solve such a problem we propose to use a genetic algorithm. The algorithm is described in the next section.

V. THE ALGORITHM

During the work of IoT, unexpected situations are met. The only information which is given is the type of target data.

First, in accordance with genetic rules, the population of random genotypes must be created. The number of generated individuals (II) is controlled by α parameter and is equal to the formula:

$$\Pi = \alpha * s * v \quad (6)$$

Where s is a number of possible subtasks and v is a number of possible types of PR in an IoT network.

The genotype is a string which contains numbers of the resources for each subtask chosen in the first optimization phase. For each genotype subtasks are chosen randomly. Therefore, selected subtasks may be different for every genotype. The resources are also chosen randomly.

We characterize the IoT network by two parameters: execution time and cost of the system. We decided to search for the cheapest solution which satisfies the time constrains. After creating a genotype the values of time and cost are calculated. As it was mentioned in previous chapters some generated solutions are invalid. It means that for some of them, desired values were not obtained. Therefore, connections of subtasks in those solutions are not valid too.

In this paper we decided to use standard genetic operators: crossover, mutation, cloning and ranked selection. Solutions are ranked by cost. At the top of the rank list valid solutions are placed. However, invalid solutions are not necessarily passed over. Because some of the genotypes have different number of genes after crossover operation it is possible to obtain solution that is not valid. The algorithm stops after ϵ generations without better solution.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

According to our best knowledge this is the first paper which deals with concurrent real-time optimization in IoT design process. In table II we present experimental results for randomly generated graphs with 10, 20 30, 40 and 50 nodes. It is known from literature [18][19] that crossover operator in the genetic algorithm typically gives better solutions than mutation. Therefore in the experiments 70% of obtained individuals in each population are obtained by crossover, 20% by mutation and 10% by cloning. The rest of the parameters which control the evolution process were arbitrarily set for every experiment as: $\alpha=100$, $v=4$ and $\epsilon=5$.

TABLE II. THE RESULTS

N	T _m	Best results			Worst results		
		time	cost	gen	time	cost	gen
10	300	284	1600	5	290	1978	10
20	400	396	2649	15	303	3255	16
30	1000	975	2842	22	960	2852	19
40	1600	1175	4632	42	1156	5527	47
50	1500	1422	4538	39	1401	5121	44

To simplify computations we assumed that all of the unexpected tasks appeared after all predicted tasks were executed. Therefore, the initial cost and time of execution predicted tasks is known.

In most of cases with decreasing cost of the task execution, time of execution of all the tasks is rising. It can be observed for graphs with 20, 30 40 and 50 nodes. For the graph with 20 nodes the best result with cost equal to 2649,

the time of execution of all the tasks was equal to 396. In the worst case experiment the cost was equal to 3255 and the time of execution of all the tasks was equal to 303. For graph with 30 nodes solution with lower cost (2842) was characterized by time of execution of all the tasks equal to 975, meanwhile solution 15 time units faster (975) was 10 cost units cheaper (2852). For graphs with 40 and 50 nodes such difference was even greater. The cheapest solution for a graph with 40 nodes (4632) has time equal to 1422. Solution which is only 19 time units slower has cost equal to 5527 (almost 900 cost units more in comparison with the best result). The cheapest result for graph with 50 nodes (4538) was characterized by time value equal to 1422. The worst solution for graph with 50 nodes was 21 time units faster (1401) but almost 600 cost units more expensive (cost equal to 5121). Only for graph with 10 nodes the situation was different. In the best result not only cost of the system was lower (equal to 1600 for the best individual and 1978 for the worst solution) but also time of execution of all the tasks was lower (284 for the best result and 290 for the worst result). We suppose that such a situation could appear because of several reasons. According to formula (9), for graph with 10 nodes in each population 4000 individuals were generated. For other graphs much more results were created in every population: 8000 for graph with 20 nodes, 12000 for graph with 30 nodes, 16000 for graph with 40 nodes and 20000 for graph with 50 nodes. Because subtasks are chosen randomly it is possible that any solution of detected unexpected situation contains unnecessary subtask. After generating more results the chance of not existing unnecessary tasks is lower, but not equal to zero because of probabilistic nature of the algorithm. It can be also observed that the larger the task graph the more generations of individuals were created. This is because for graph with more tasks the search space is greater.

In table II we present the results of experiment in case when more individuals are created using mutation parameter and less using crossover. The number of individuals in each population and the stop condition is the same as in previous set of experiments. Therefore the parameters which control the evolution have the following values: $\alpha=100$, $v=4$, $\beta=0,2$, $\gamma=0,6$, $\delta=0,2$, $\epsilon=5$.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we present genetic algorithm to concurrent optimization in two phases which impact each-other in real time in IoT design process. The problem appears when IoT network must execute unexpected tasks and no information about the tasks is given. The algorithm is able to detect unexpected tasks and search for their better solutions. It is also able to eliminate connections of subtasks which do not give an acceptable solution.

Future work will concentrate on providing new algorithm to solve the presented problem. We will also concentrate on other aspects such as dependence on choice of constants and parameters for the problems of concurrent real-time optimisation and unexpected tasks in IoT design process. Another important issue is to connect presented method with other algorithms to obtain cheaper or faster IoT networks.

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On the Use of Machine-Learning based Surrogate Models in Continuous Optimisation

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Abstract—Heuristic optimisation is a popular tool for solving continuous optimisation problems. These algorithms explore the search space by sampling solutions, evaluating their fitness and biasing the search towards promising areas. For these algorithms to work, they normally need a relatively large number of fitness evaluations to explore the search space adequately. However, in some contexts (mainly in scientific and engineering problems) fitness evaluation requires the execution of an expensive function (sometimes, a whole simulation), drastically reducing the available number of evaluations. In these problems, the coupling of the optimisation algorithm with a machine learning-based surrogate model can alleviate this problem by using the information reported by the surrogate to decide whether a given candidate solution should be evaluated or not. However, using a surrogate model to assess candidate solutions impacts in the navigation of the search space because there is a degree of uncertainty in the evaluation of candidate solutions that might affect the optimisation process. In this paper, we analyse how different optimisation algorithms perform when using surrogate models on a set of continuous optimisation problems concluding that it helps the algorithms to improve their results even if the allocated number of fitness evaluations is very small.

Index Terms—Heuristic Optimisation, Machine Learning, Surrogate Models, Continuous Optimisation

I. INTRODUCTION

Evolutionary algorithms perform a stochastic search of the solution space by iterative sampling certain candidate solutions, evaluating these solutions, and selecting and recombining the best of them according to a fitness (quality) function. This fitness function is the driver of the search process, whereas the different types of algorithms determine the search strategy.

In many real-world problems, in particular in the domains of science and engineering, the fitness function is implemented by a computationally expensive calculation, such as a simulation process e.g., finite element calculations or fluid dynamics. One of the alternatives to speed up the process is using surrogate

models. A surrogate model approximates the actual fitness function using, for instance, machine learning algorithms, in which inference time is expected to be faster than the execution time of the fitness function itself. This faster execution comes at a price, which is the accuracy of the modelling compared to the results of the actual fitness function. Depending on how the surrogates are exploited (online vs. offline, regression vs. pairwise, as detailed in the next section), these accuracy limitations impact the overall performance of the search strategy. As a consequence, the exploration of candidate solutions to determine promising areas of the search space is affected by the quality of the modelling.

The objective of this work is to analyse the implications of using pairwise online surrogate models on different evolutionary and non-evolutionary strategies. Specifically, this paper compares the improvement of the results when fixing the number of maximum fitness evaluations and using this particular type of surrogate for different population-based strategies, particularly, Genetic Algorithms (GA), Differential Evolution (DE) and SHADE (a reference DE variant). This study also includes a preliminary analysis of the impact on a local search mechanism (one component of MTS, Multi-trajectory Local Search) as a comparative result and a discussion on the difference in performance.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section II describes surrogate-based optimisation and its alternatives as a mechanism to overcome the computational cost of performing actual fitness function evaluations, and details how pairwise surrogate model [1] addresses this problem. Section III presents the experimental scenario including the evolutionary algorithms under study. To follow, Section IV analyses the result of the experiment and the behaviour of surrogates in a local search algorithm. Finally, Section V concludes the work by summarising the most relevant findings.

II. EVOLUTIONARY ALGORITHMS AND SURROGATE MODELS

The iterative process of proposing candidate solutions, evaluating them and the recombination of the most promising ones is at the core of all evolutionary algorithms. The execution of a sufficient number of FFEs is a limiting factor of these methods when the function to optimise implies executing complex simulations that can take from several seconds to hours. Hence, an alternative is to use an approximate model of the fitness function as a surrogate, built from a representative set of previous solutions and exploited during the search process.

There are two approaches to the use of surrogates in an optimisation problem. First, offline surrogates generate a twin function that approximates the function to optimise. To this purpose, the search space is sampled (with the Latin Hypercube method [2], for example). Later, all the sampled points are evaluated. Then, a model that will replace the original quality function is trained. Finally, the optimisation is run using the approximate quality function instead of the original one as the objective function to optimise.

On the other hand, online surrogates create a model that acts as a filter during the optimisation process. This approach still requires an iterative process using the fitness function, but not for all the candidate solutions generated by the search strategy. When a new solution is created, the surrogate evaluates whether this solution is promising enough, and the actual fitness function is used to evaluate it only if a minimum quality is met. Additionally, the solutions that are effectively calculated can be used to retrain the surrogate model during the optimisation, improving its accuracy, in particular, in those areas in which the search process concentrates its efforts.

The most straightforward implementation of online surrogates is the use of regression models to approximate the result of the FFE. Based on its result, a new candidate solution is only evaluated if it is identified as an improvement. However, regression models assume that the effect of an error is evenly distributed in the sampling space, which is hardly ever the case. Elitism methods tend to compare two candidates or to create a ranking in order to identify a worthy candidate. In this case, a small error when candidates are close can affect the final decision, while a larger error when both are significantly different may not affect the decision.

As an alternative, the surrogate model can be reformulated as a classification problem. In these cases, the outcome of the surrogate model is not the estimated value of the fitness function but whether a candidate is better than a certain threshold value. There is previous literature on the use of classifiers to predict an improvement based on neighbourhood data, such as CADE [3] and its extension, CRADE [4], both using DE, and LLSO [5], that uses Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO) as the optimiser.

In this work, we have used a pairwise classification-based surrogate model to predict whether a candidate (challenger) is better than a reference solution (challenged). This approach was already compared in [1] against the traditional regression

and offline models, obtaining the best overall results. The outcome of this pairwise model is a preliminary evaluation of the elitism leveraged to detect which challengers are due to be evaluated. After this step, those promising candidates (better than their reference solution) are evaluated with the actual fitness function, and the search strategy performs the regular elitism phase.

III. EXPERIMENTAL FRAMEWORK

In this study, we compare four optimisation algorithms both run independently and coupled with a surrogate model. In [1], the authors compared regression and pairwise approaches to build surrogate models, concluding that classification models using decision trees obtained the best overall results. The reason behind this superior performance is the increase in the evolutionary pressure by being very restrictive in accepting candidate solutions. For this reason, we choose the pairwise approach as our surrogate model, that we combine with the following four optimisation algorithms:

- Differential Evolution (DE): this was the baseline algorithm used in [1] and thus has been included in this study as a reference.
- Genetic Algorithm (GA): we include the classic GAs proposed in [6] as the logic to determine which solutions are kept in the population significantly differs from the one used by Differential Evolution.
- Success-History based Adaptive Differential Evolution (SHADE): this algorithm, proposed in [7], is one of the most advanced and successful variants of Differential Evolution. The reason to include this algorithm in our comparison is to check if surrogate models can also improve the performance of advanced algorithms such as this one, and not only of simpler techniques, such as GAs and DE.
- First local search of the Multiple Trajectory Search algorithm (MTS-LS1): a completely different approach, a local search proposed in [8] that has obtained significantly good results in continuous optimisation problems, especially in large-scale optimisation. We wanted to check if this approach of machine learning based surrogate models can also be exploited by local searches.

The different algorithms, with and without the surrogate model, are evaluated using the well-known benchmark proposed in [9] for the SOCO'2011 special issue on the "*Scalability of evolutionary algorithms and other metaheuristics for large-scale continuous optimisation problems*". In order to adjust the experimentation to the inherent characteristics of the problems that are normally solved with the help of surrogate models, we have conducted the following changes to the usual experimental conditions of this benchmark: each configuration is run 15 times instead of the usual 25, for a fair comparison, the same run number is guaranteed to start from the same initial population, maximum fitness evaluations has been fixed to 15D (assuming that this is the most common scenario for computationally expensive problems) and problem size to $D = 50$. Finally, the values of the parameters used by DE, the

GA and SHADE can be found in Table I and the values of the MTS-LS1 algorithm are kept as in the original paper [8].

TABLE I
PARAMETERS VALUES FOR THE CONSIDERED ALGORITHMS

Parameter Values of DE	
strategy	rand/1/exp
F	0.5
CR	0.5
Parameter Values of GA	
crossover	BLX- α , $\alpha = 0.5$
crossover probability	0.9
mutation	gaussian
mutation probability	0.1
selection	tournament (size=3, prob=0.8)
elitism	full elitism
Parameter Values of SHADE	
memory size	5

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Overall Analysis

In this section, we present and discuss the results of the experimentation carried out. The results of each of the four algorithms with and without a surrogate model can be found in Tables IV and V, respectively. In these tables, we can see that, for a very limited number of fitness evaluations such as the ones allowed in these experiments (750) the MTS-LS1 (with and without the use of a surrogate) obtains, systematically, the best results. This seems logical to some extent as population-based algorithms invest a lot of effort exploring the search space (especially during the first iterations in which random initialization can spread candidate solutions very far away from each other), whereas the local search quickly tries to improve a single solution within its neighbourhood. For this reason, we have decided to discuss the results of the MTS-LS1 algorithm in a separate subsection and focus our first analysis on DE, GA and SHADE.

Table II presents the ranking of these three algorithms with and without surrogate models on the whole benchmark according to the Friedman test. The mean values of the 15 independent runs carried out per function and algorithm have been considered. Several conclusions can be extracted from the results presented in this table:

- The three considered algorithms improve their results when using surrogates.
- The improvement is bigger in the case of the basic DE and smaller in the case of SHADE.
- The relative difference in performance is bigger for the simpler algorithms (GA and DE). This is especially the case of DE, which seems to take more advantage of the pairwise surrogate model. This is probably due to the fact that pairwise comparisons are tightly coupled to the design of the DE selection mechanism, when a trial vector is compared with the corresponding target vector to decide which one will be kept in the population for the next iteration.

TABLE II
FRIEDMAN AVERAGE RANKING FOR DE, GA AND SHADE WITH AND WITHOUT SURROGATES

	Ranking
SHADE (with surrogate)	1.47
SHADE	1.74
DE (with surrogate)	3.00
GA (with surrogate)	4.11
GA	5.32
DE	5.37

To continue, we have statistically compared each algorithm with its surrogate-based counterpart. Table III summarises the results of this comparison. As can be seen, both DE and GA with a surrogate significantly improve the results of the algorithms without surrogate. In the case of SHADE, however, this comparison does not yield statistically significant differences, though the use of a surrogate clearly seems to benefit the algorithm. This is in line with the Friedman average rankings discussed before and seems to confirm that the advantage provided by the surrogate models is more pronounced the simpler the optimisation algorithm is.

TABLE III
P-VALUES FOR THE PAIRED WILCOXON ANALYSIS CONDUCTED AMONG THE DIFFERENT OPTIMISERS AND THEIR SURROGATE-BASED COUNTERPARTS

Algorithms compared	p-value
SHADE (with surrogate) vs. SHADE	$2.58E - 01$
DE (with surrogate) vs. DE	$1.91E - 06$ ✓
GA (with surrogate) vs. GA	$3.81E - 06$ ✓

✓ means that there are statistical differences with significance level $\alpha = 0.05$

In most of the functions, DE and the GA with surrogates outperform both DE and GA without them. This is the case for functions 1, 3-8 and 12-18, for which using a surrogate is more important than the selection of the algorithm. Sometimes, the differences are of several orders of magnitude, such as in functions 7 and 15 (Figures 1 and 2, respectively), whereas other differences are smaller, but consistent, such as in function 3 (Figure 3).

On the other hand, for the remainder functions (2, 9-11 and 19), both DEs (with and without surrogate) are better than both GAs, or vice-versa. Nonetheless, DE and the GA are still better when using the surrogate than when they do not. An example of this behaviour can be observed in Figures 4-6.

Regarding SHADE, it is the most powerful algorithm among the evolutionary alternatives that we have considered in our experimentation. The contribution of the surrogate in this algorithm is smaller compared to DE and GA, but still consistent, as shown in Tables IV and V, and Figures 5 and 6. In other functions, the contribution is more limited (Figures 2 and 3). Finally, it is infrequent that SHADE obtains better results than its surrogate-based counterpart (Figure 4) and, in those cases, the differences are quite small.

To conclude this analysis, it should be noted that most of the algorithms exhibit similar behaviour for most of the functions

Fig. 1. Convergence plot for function 7 and the three population-based algorithms (DE, GA and SHADE) and their surrogate-based counterparts. Y-axis represents the best fitness (in logarithmic scale) whereas X-axis represents the number of fitness evaluations.

Fig. 3. Convergence plot for function 3 and the three population-based algorithms (DE, GA and SHADE) and their surrogate-based counterparts. Y-axis represents the best fitness (in logarithmic scale) whereas X-axis represents the number of fitness evaluations.

Fig. 2. Convergence plot for function 15 and the three population-based algorithms (DE, GA and SHADE) and their surrogate-based counterparts. Y-axis represents the best fitness (in logarithmic scale) whereas X-axis represents the number of fitness evaluations.

Fig. 4. Convergence plot for function 9 and the three population-based algorithms (DE, GA and SHADE) and their surrogate-based counterparts. Y-axis represents the best fitness (in logarithmic scale) whereas X-axis represents the number of fitness evaluations.

in their convergence plots. Normally, there is a warm-up phase in which the performance of the algorithm with and without the surrogate is very similar. This makes sense as, during this early stage of the search, the machine learning-based surrogate does not have enough information to make accurate predictions. As the search progresses, the datasets used to train the predictive models (decision trees, in this case) increase both in size and diversity, and this allows the model to better capture the fitness landscape. This explains why, as the search progresses, the convergence curves of the algorithms with and without surrogates tend to split apart.

B. Behaviour of the MTS-LS1 algorithm

When we started the discussion of the results of this experimentation, we observed that the results obtained by the

MTS-LS1 algorithm were significantly better than those of the population-based approaches. We argued that including these results in our general analysis could distort the conclusions that we can extract on the behaviour of the population-based methods and thus we decided to treat them independently.

If we pay attention to the convergence plots of the MTS-LS1 algorithm, we can observe that the version using the surrogate model often converges much sooner than the one that does not use surrogates. For example, Figure 7 shows the convergence plot for function 2. We can observe how the local search, when using the surrogate model, prematurely converges and stops progressing after just a few fitness evaluations. Similar behaviour can be observed in other functions, such as function 6 (Figure 8) in which the local search with the surrogate model

Fig. 5. Convergence plot for function 10 and the three population-based algorithms (DE, GA and SHADE) and their surrogate-based counterparts. Y-axis represents the best fitness (in logarithmic scale) whereas X-axis represents the number of fitness evaluations.

Fig. 7. Convergence plot for function 2 and the MTS-LS1 algorithm and its surrogate-based counterpart. Y-axis represents the best fitness whereas X-axis represents the number of fitness evaluations.

Fig. 6. Convergence plot for function 11 and the three population-based algorithms (DE, GA and SHADE) and their surrogate-based counterparts. Y-axis represents the best fitness (in logarithmic scale) whereas X-axis represents the number of fitness evaluations.

Fig. 8. Convergence plot for function 6 and the MTS-LS1 algorithm and its surrogate-based counterpart. Y-axis represents the best fitness whereas X-axis represents the number of fitness evaluations.

progresses for a few more fitness evaluations before getting stuck again. Finally, there are other functions in which the surrogate has a smaller negative effect and the convergence plots are similar, although towards a worse final fitness function for the surrogate-based method. This is probably due to the overhead of using a method that is continuously failing its predictions. Figure 9 shows the convergence plots for function 9, that exhibits this behaviour.

Our explanation for the premature convergence of the MTS-LS1 algorithm when using a classification decision tree surrogate model is related to how local searches work. In many cases, these algorithms work by introducing perturbations in one variable at a time. When the classification model has to be trained, it is fed with pairs of solutions and a boolean

indicating whether the first solution is better than the second one or not. If both solutions only differ in one value, it can be very difficult for the decision tree to capture this subtle difference. If the model does not select that particular variable among the ones used to build the tree, it is impossible for it to decide among two solutions that only differ in that particular variable. This hypothesis requires, nevertheless, a deeper analysis of the classification trees learned during the search and also the usage of other machine learning models that integrate the information of all the variables, such as neural networks or support vector machines. However, these algorithms normally require a larger number of instances (and training time) than is available during the optimisation of problems of this nature, which converts this issue into a real challenge that will require careful analysis.

Fig. 9. Convergence plot for function 9 and the MTS-LS1 algorithm and its surrogate-based counterpart. Y-axis represents the best fitness whereas X-axis represents the number of fitness evaluations.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have presented the results of a study conducted on four optimisation algorithms (DE, GA, SHADE and MTS-LS1) that we have coupled with a machine learning based surrogate model that uses classification decision trees to decide whether one solution is better than another. The experimental results show that the surrogate model has a positive contribution to the performance of the three population-based methods (DE, GA and SHADE), whereas it does not improve the results of the local search. The problem with local searches is that they, normally, change one single variable at a time (this is true for MTS-LS1). This is translated into a poor coverage not only of the whole search space, but also of the neighbourhood of the starting solution as all the candidate solutions created from this starting point are very similar and thus the machine learning model might fail to capture the variable that makes one solution different (and better/worse) than another. To alleviate this problem, other machine learning algorithms that use all the variables during the learning phase could be considered.

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TABLE IV
RESULTS OF THE FOUR OPTIMISATION ALGORITHMS WITHOUT SURROGATES. VALUES HIGHLIGHTED IN BOLD ARE BETTER THAN THOSE OF THE SAME ALGORITHM USING SURROGATES.

		F_1	F_2	F_3	F_4	F_5	F_6	F_7
DE	Best	1.28E+05	-3.28E+02	4.77E+10	4.94E+02	1.02E+03	-1.19E+02	1.99E+07
	Worst	1.89E+05	-3.03E+02	1.40E+11	6.63E+02	1.50E+03	-1.19E+02	2.73E+17
	Mean	1.60E+05	-3.14E+02	1.05E+11	5.81E+02	1.24E+03	-1.19E+02	3.19E+16
	Std	1.84E+04	6.26E+00	2.51E+10	5.36E+01	1.25E+02	1.53E-01	7.29E+16
GA	Best	9.40E+04	-3.84E+02	4.51E+10	4.43E+02	9.62E+02	-1.19E+02	2.90E+10
	Worst	1.80E+05	-3.56E+02	1.44E+11	6.60E+02	1.45E+03	-1.19E+02	1.98E+19
	Mean	1.53E+05	-3.62E+02	9.65E+10	5.43E+02	1.19E+03	-1.19E+02	1.39E+18
	Std	2.31E+04	7.84E+00	2.70E+10	7.16E+01	1.43E+02	7.72E-02	4.93E+18
SHADE	Best	2.63E+04	-3.76E+02	5.57E+09	2.98E+02	7.60E+01	-1.23E+02	6.66E+01
	Worst	7.18E+04	-3.54E+02	2.44E+10	4.10E+02	3.95E+02	-1.19E+02	6.59E+09
	Mean	4.56E+04	-3.66E+02	1.24E+10	3.49E+02	2.14E+02	-1.21E+02	8.26E+08
	Std	1.18E+04	6.52E+00	5.36E+09	3.19E+01	8.24E+01	1.06E+00	2.11E+09
MTS-LS1	Best	1.43E+03	-4.08E+02	7.69E+07	-1.29E+01	-1.47E+02	-1.26E+02	2.19E+01
	Worst	1.16E+04	-3.84E+02	9.77E+08	3.78E+02	-6.34E+01	-1.19E+02	6.73E+01
	Mean	8.19E+03	-3.93E+02	5.54E+08	1.34E+02	-9.70E+01	-1.22E+02	5.36E+01
	Std	2.80E+03	6.45E+00	2.67E+08	9.54E+01	2.73E+01	2.22E+00	1.38E+01
		F_8	F_9	F_{10}	F_{11}	F_{12}	F_{13}	F_{14}
DE	Best	6.41E+04	4.42E+02	5.71E+03	4.49E+02	1.17E+05	5.43E+10	8.76E+02
	Worst	1.46E+05	5.38E+02	7.90E+03	5.19E+02	1.78E+05	1.19E+11	1.02E+03
	Mean	9.91E+04	4.98E+02	6.68E+03	4.91E+02	1.49E+05	8.45E+10	9.53E+02
	Std	2.23E+04	2.59E+01	5.00E+02	1.95E+01	1.60E+04	1.95E+10	4.40E+01
GA	Best	4.88E+04	5.31E+02	6.45E+03	5.11E+02	9.72E+04	3.48E+10	8.23E+02
	Worst	1.82E+05	5.80E+02	9.70E+03	5.59E+02	1.67E+05	7.19E+10	1.03E+03
	Mean	1.09E+05	5.57E+02	8.74E+03	5.42E+02	1.31E+05	5.31E+10	9.33E+02
	Std	3.38E+04	1.30E+01	7.77E+02	1.35E+01	2.02E+04	1.43E+10	6.99E+01
SHADE	Best	1.69E+04	3.47E+02	8.01E+02	3.52E+02	5.39E+04	1.37E+10	6.98E+02
	Worst	4.96E+04	4.34E+02	1.52E+03	4.55E+02	7.16E+04	2.39E+10	8.68E+02
	Mean	2.95E+04	3.81E+02	1.23E+03	3.93E+02	6.05E+04	1.87E+10	7.69E+02
	Std	9.77E+03	2.30E+01	2.16E+02	3.08E+01	4.75E+03	3.03E+09	3.99E+01
MTS-LS1	Best	4.91E+04	2.90E+02	1.37E+02	2.63E+02	4.32E+04	1.14E+10	5.63E+02
	Worst	1.43E+05	4.13E+02	1.07E+03	4.06E+02	5.24E+04	1.24E+10	7.20E+02
	Mean	9.40E+04	3.67E+02	7.04E+02	3.44E+02	4.75E+04	1.18E+10	6.46E+02
	Std	2.81E+04	3.88E+01	2.81E+02	4.06E+01	2.37E+03	3.06E+08	4.22E+01
		F_{15}	F_{16}	F_{17}	F_{18}	F_{19}		
DE	Best	5.69E+06	1.21E+05	5.38E+10	1.04E+03	2.03E+03		
	Worst	8.01E+12	1.67E+05	6.45E+10	1.13E+03	5.16E+03		
	Mean	6.53E+11	1.41E+05	5.64E+10	1.10E+03	3.27E+03		
	Std	1.98E+12	1.16E+04	3.20E+09	2.32E+01	9.60E+02		
GA	Best	1.97E+03	1.07E+05	5.34E+10	1.01E+03	3.78E+03		
	Worst	1.20E+14	1.44E+05	5.51E+10	1.07E+03	6.27E+03		
	Mean	1.04E+13	1.23E+05	5.39E+10	1.05E+03	4.70E+03		
	Std	3.00E+13	1.02E+04	4.59E+08	1.79E+01	6.13E+02		
SHADE	Best	2.95E+02	8.91E+04	5.31E+10	9.92E+02	3.55E+02		
	Worst	1.24E+04	9.80E+04	5.31E+10	1.04E+03	1.06E+03		
	Mean	1.64E+03	9.27E+04	5.31E+10	1.02E+03	6.90E+02		
	Std	2.91E+03	2.97E+03	8.74E+06	1.54E+01	1.87E+02		
MTS-LS1	Best	3.43E+01	8.86E+04	5.31E+10	9.55E+02	2.37E+02		
	Worst	2.04E+02	9.55E+04	5.39E+10	1.05E+03	3.98E+02		
	Mean	1.22E+02	9.07E+04	5.34E+10	9.96E+02	3.19E+02		
	Std	5.59E+01	1.70E+03	1.87E+08	2.24E+01	4.22E+01		

TABLE V
RESULTS OF THE FOUR OPTIMISATION ALGORITHMS WITH SURROGATES. VALUES HIGHLIGHTED IN BOLD ARE BETTER THAN THOSE OF THE SAME ALGORITHM WITHOUT SURROGATES.

		F_1	F_2	F_3	F_4	F_5	F_6	F_7
DE	Best	6.25E+04	-3.37E+02	1.43E+10	2.28E+02	2.49E+02	-1.20E+02	6.37E+04
	Worst	9.81E+04	-3.06E+02	4.88E+10	3.96E+02	6.40E+02	-1.19E+02	2.74E+11
	Mean	7.58E+04	-3.20E+02	3.03E+10	3.19E+02	4.74E+02	-1.19E+02	5.90E+10
	Std	9.22E+03	9.15E+00	1.03E+10	4.77E+01	1.10E+02	1.53E-01	9.24E+10
GA	Best	8.96E+04	-3.84E+02	3.70E+10	3.38E+02	5.89E+02	-1.19E+02	4.49E+08
	Worst	1.43E+05	-3.54E+02	8.88E+10	4.70E+02	1.02E+03	-1.19E+02	6.32E+16
	Mean	1.15E+05	-3.62E+02	5.35E+10	4.09E+02	7.79E+02	-1.19E+02	6.86E+15
	Std	1.84E+04	8.11E+00	1.39E+10	4.49E+01	1.19E+02	9.91E-02	1.65E+16
SHADE	Best	2.49E+04	-3.78E+02	5.52E+09	1.88E+02	6.74E+01	-1.23E+02	5.65E+01
	Worst	7.82E+04	-3.55E+02	3.40E+10	4.62E+02	4.93E+02	-1.19E+02	1.63E+06
	Mean	4.83E+04	-3.69E+02	1.36E+10	3.38E+02	2.35E+02	-1.21E+02	1.22E+05
	Std	1.33E+04	6.61E+00	6.29E+09	6.93E+01	1.24E+02	7.37E-01	4.05E+05
MTS-LS1	Best	8.73E+03	-3.34E+02	4.78E+08	6.48E+01	-9.39E+01	-1.26E+02	5.64E+01
	Worst	9.60E+04	-2.93E+02	1.29E+11	6.25E+02	8.07E+02	-1.19E+02	1.16E+08
	Mean	2.99E+04	-3.13E+02	1.64E+10	2.19E+02	1.34E+02	-1.21E+02	7.75E+06
	Std	2.87E+04	1.21E+01	3.31E+10	1.48E+02	2.67E+02	1.76E+00	2.90E+07
		F_8	F_9	F_{10}	F_{11}	F_{12}	F_{13}	F_{14}
DE	Best	5.90E+04	3.98E+02	3.18E+03	4.24E+02	7.87E+04	1.59E+10	7.03E+02
	Worst	9.80E+04	4.80E+02	4.57E+03	4.82E+02	1.07E+05	3.42E+10	7.87E+02
	Mean	7.87E+04	4.48E+02	3.98E+03	4.46E+02	9.12E+04	2.59E+10	7.40E+02
	Std	1.31E+04	1.97E+01	3.78E+02	1.50E+01	9.04E+03	6.18E+09	2.17E+01
GA	Best	7.15E+04	5.16E+02	7.19E+03	5.20E+02	8.26E+04	2.90E+10	7.54E+02
	Worst	1.26E+05	5.75E+02	9.48E+03	5.64E+02	1.13E+05	4.74E+10	9.19E+02
	Mean	9.66E+04	5.52E+02	8.20E+03	5.32E+02	9.82E+04	3.53E+10	8.36E+02
	Std	1.55E+04	2.10E+01	6.20E+02	1.13E+01	8.80E+03	4.19E+09	4.36E+01
SHADE	Best	1.54E+04	3.12E+02	7.74E+02	3.15E+02	4.95E+04	1.33E+10	7.19E+02
	Worst	5.39E+04	4.12E+02	2.03E+03	4.23E+02	9.66E+04	3.01E+10	8.81E+02
	Mean	2.53E+04	3.77E+02	1.20E+03	3.73E+02	6.53E+04	1.82E+10	7.84E+02
	Std	9.66E+03	2.99E+01	3.40E+02	2.49E+01	1.26E+04	4.87E+09	4.56E+01
MTS-LS1	Best	7.50E+04	3.50E+02	6.93E+02	3.27E+02	4.60E+04	1.15E+10	5.63E+02
	Worst	4.07E+05	4.97E+02	4.96E+03	4.74E+02	1.57E+05	1.69E+11	9.47E+02
	Mean	1.48E+05	4.09E+02	1.66E+03	3.88E+02	8.27E+04	3.97E+10	7.02E+02
	Std	7.77E+04	3.90E+01	1.24E+03	4.48E+01	3.90E+04	4.88E+10	9.79E+01
		F_{15}	F_{16}	F_{17}	F_{18}	F_{19}		
DE	Best	1.36E+04	9.36E+04	5.32E+10	1.00E+03	1.25E+03		
	Worst	4.64E+08	1.16E+05	5.54E+10	1.06E+03	2.64E+03		
	Mean	3.67E+07	1.03E+05	5.37E+10	1.03E+03	1.79E+03		
	Std	1.15E+08	5.88E+03	5.54E+08	1.52E+01	3.55E+02		
GA	Best	1.82E+03	9.85E+04	5.32E+10	1.00E+03	2.97E+03		
	Worst	2.73E+09	1.16E+05	5.41E+10	1.05E+03	4.96E+03		
	Mean	3.23E+08	1.07E+05	5.35E+10	1.02E+03	3.89E+03		
	Std	7.38E+08	5.20E+03	2.42E+08	1.47E+01	5.41E+02		
SHADE	Best	2.13E+02	8.81E+04	5.31E+10	9.79E+02	3.87E+02		
	Worst	2.36E+03	1.02E+05	5.32E+10	1.05E+03	8.98E+02		
	Mean	6.56E+02	9.24E+04	5.31E+10	1.02E+03	5.87E+02		
	Std	5.45E+02	3.33E+03	1.41E+07	2.12E+01	1.14E+02		
MTS-LS1	Best	9.49E+01	8.86E+04	5.31E+10	9.58E+02	2.79E+02		
	Worst	4.63E+09	1.46E+05	5.56E+10	1.05E+03	2.43E+03		
	Mean	5.14E+08	9.78E+04	5.37E+10	1.01E+03	8.27E+02		
	Std	1.22E+09	1.81E+04	6.94E+08	2.35E+01	7.21E+02		